

Project Number: 101058432

Start Date of Project: 01/06/2022

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable 5.2

Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work

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Work Package	WP5
Reviewed by	Project Management Board, Bob Jones
Due Date of Deliverable	31/03/25 (=M34)
Actual Submission Date	25/04/25
Dissemination Level	PU
Approval Status	
Version	v1.0

Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable describes the results of the work carried out under the four tasks of EOSC Focus WP5 - Sustainability of EOSC. The main text summarises the approach taken in the execution of the four main tasks. The full results for the work on resourcing models (T5.3) are available as a series of appendices.

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DOCUMENT LOG

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TERMINOLOGY

Glossary/Abbreviations	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation infrastructure
AC	Associated Country
D	Deliverable
DIS	Dedicated Implementation Structure
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud-Association
EP	European Partnership
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
HE	Horizon Europe
HPC	High Performance Computing
IEP	Institutional European Partnership
IKC	In-kind Contribution
ISAB	Industrial and Scientific Advisory Board
IKOP	In-kind Contribution to Operational Activities
JU	Joint Undertaking
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework

MO	Mandated Organisation
MS	Member State
MSP	Multiannual Strategic Programme
OS	Open Science
PID	Persistent Identifier
Q	Quarter
RDA	Research Data Alliance
REA	Research Executive Agency
RI	Research Infrastructure
SEP	Sustainable Exploitation Planning
SP	Service Provider
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
T	Task
TFEU	Treaty for the European Union
TNA	Transnational Access
VA	Virtual Access
WG	Working Group
WP4	Work Package 4: Monitoring and Impact Assessment
WP5	Work Package 5: Sustainability of EOSC

Table of Contents (ToC)

Executive Summary	1
1. Introduction	2
2. Rules of Participation (T5.1): Supporting the creation of the EOOSC Federation Handbook	3
2.1. Scope and structure of the EOOSC Federation Handbook	3
2.2. Creation process	4
3. Supporting the EOOSC-A in engaging the S/ACs (T5.2)	5
3.1. Support to EOOSC-A Mandated Organisations	5
3.2. A new narrative for EOOSC	7
4. Resourcing models for the sustainability of EOOSC (T5.3)	9
4.1. Funding models for EOOSC	9
4.2. Options for enhancing the financial sustainability of EOOSC	10
4.3. Platform business models and Sustainable Exploitation Planning methodology	11
4.4. Financial and sustainability aspects of Horizon Europe Partnerships and other types of collaboration	15
5. Expanding OS collaboration (T5.4)	19
5.1. Link with global Open Science initiatives and dynamics	19
5.2. Foreseen next steps	19
Appendix 1: Subcontracted work on business models for platforms	21
Appendix 2: Note on Virtual Access	77
Appendix 3: Institutionalised European Partnerships under Article 185 TFEU	84
Appendix 4: Institutionalised European Partnerships under Art. 187 TFEU: the example of EuroHPC Joint Undertaking	90
Appendix 5: The ERIC funding model	103

List of Figures

[Figure 1 – Screenshot of the country matrix](#)

[Figure 2 – Screenshot from the MOs Miro Board](#)

List of Tables

[Table 1 – Chapters of the EOOSC Federation Handbook \(status by Q1 2025\)](#)

[Table 2 – Conclusions of the platform analysis and changes suggested for the platform owner](#)

Executive Summary

This deliverable D5.2 of the HE project EOSC Focus (GA #101058432; June 2022 - May 2025) contains a summary of the activities of Work Package 5 of EOSC Focus in the period M19-M34 (December 2023 - March 2025). During this period, the work focussed on support of several aspects related to the development of EOSC, such as the EOSC Federation Handbook, the contribution of EU Member States and Associated Countries to EOSC, the sustainability of EOSC relative to service provision in the EOSC landscape, and the alignment with the global Open Science agenda.

Insights in relevant models of funding and governance as well as best practices in implementing them have been collected to provide the EOSC Partnership with a solid information base in the process of designing the future of EOSC post-2027. In particular, support was provided to:

- help EU Member States and Associated countries via the Mandated Organisations understand the EOSC landscape at national level, and the different approaches of the countries to the EOSC Federation, by providing them with information and a forum to discuss the implementation of the concept of EOSC Node at the national level,
- the creation of a new EOSC policy narrative,
- the preparation of overviews of funding vehicles that may be relevant for the sustainability of EOSC post-2027,
- the support of the EOSC Federation Handbook drafting, and
- the maintenance of links with other Open Science initiatives in the global landscape and enhancement of the overall global visibility of EOSC.

D5.2 is structured as a series of topical summaries of work conducted, following from the task structure of WP5, while for some of the topics covered the full reports are added as appendices.

1. Introduction

This deliverable D5.2 of EOSC Focus covers the work carried out by WP5 during the project period M19-M34 (December 2023 - March 2025).¹

For the Horizon Europe EOSC Partnership, the period covered was extremely dynamic². During 2024, the focus was placed on building up the EOSC Federation. In the spring, the discussions by the Tripartite Governance (EC, EOSC Steering Board representing the EU MS/AC, and the EOSC Association) on governance and funding models were put on hold. In the relatively stable period that followed, the WP5 team could focus on completing and processing the information gathered from different stakeholders during the first half of the project on relevant topics.

The WP5 team continuously adjusted its focus to the information needs that emerged from the development of the concept of EOSC as a federation of nodes and its implementation. Particular note was taken of the discussions taking place in the Tripartite Group³, established—among other tasks—to keep up the momentum for the process of building the EOSC Federation.

Given the dynamics, the priority for **Task 5.1** shifted to providing support for the delivery of the community-led development of the EOSC Federation Handbook.

Task T5.2 focussed on the collection of information from Member States and Associated Countries (MS/AC) and Mandated Organisations with the aim of supporting exchange of information on the approaches of the countries to the EOSC node concept and on supporting the EOSC Tripartite in creating a new policy narrative for EOSC.

Task 5.3 addressed the agreed topics, each aimed at answering questions potentially relevant for the future governance and funding of EOSC, and checked at regular intervals whether the work in preparation and the topics addressed were still relevant for the EOSC Partnership. The work led to the creation of a series of reports referenced in section 4 below, and included as Appendices. The work in T5.3 on financial sustainability of service provision in EOSC complements the work by Task 3.3, focused primarily on the sustainability of EOSC from an organisational and governance perspective.

The work in **Task 5.4** focused on the maintenance of the links with other Open Science initiatives in the global landscape and the enhancement of the overall global visibility of EOSC.

The sections below address the work carried out in the respective tasks in the project period M19-M34. The structure of the present deliverable follows the topic task structure for WP5 as specified in the EOSC Focus Grant Agreement:

- T5.1 Rules of Participation
- T5.2 Contributions from MS/ACs
- T5.3 Resourcing models for EOSC sustainability
- T5.4 Expanding OS collaboration

¹ EOSC Focus Deliverable 5.1, submitted in December 2023, <https://zenodo.org/records/10931890>.

² The dynamics in the process of establishing the EOSC Federation and the role of the Tripartite Group are described here: <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/>

³ <https://eosc.eu/news/2024/05/towards-a-fully-fledged-eosc-federation/>

2. Rules of Participation (T5.1): Supporting the creation of the EOSC Federation Handbook

EOSC Focus Task 5.1 directed its efforts in project period M19-M34 to supporting the creation of the EOSC Federation Handbook. In this section, we describe the content and evolution of the Handbook, highlighting the instrumental support in its development provided by T5.1.

2.1. Scope and structure of the EOSC Federation Handbook

To collect the understanding in the community of the notion of “EOSC as a Federation”, the EOSC Association proposed in late 2023 to develop a “handbook” that describes the organisational and functioning principles envisioned for the future EOSC Federation in practical terms, and started in early 2024 to prepare this as a community-driven (i.e. bottom-up) and voluntary effort towards establishing the EOSC Federation. The purpose of the EOSC Federation Handbook (or Handbook for short) is to create “a single reference document describing the EOSC Federation, its operational structure and responsibilities, its legal and governance framework, and its technical operations”⁴.

For this activity, EOSC-A appointed a chief editor to lead the editing process, and identified two assistant editors from EOSC Focus WP5 and one additional editor from the EOSC-A team to support the chief editor. The EC and the MS/AC contributed to the writing and reviewing process via the “Tripartite Group”. The first edition of the EOSC Federation Handbook was officially approved by the EOSC Tripartite Governance during its 7th meeting (Krakow, 25 March 2025).

The idea of a handbook or manual for the EOSC Federation was inspired by ELIXIR’s *Handbook of Operations*⁵ and the documentation created for GBIF⁶, both of which envisage to combine national nodes into seamless cross-border research infrastructures (RIs) based on a federation of services. Other sources of inspiration were the Data Spaces Blueprint⁷, which describes the governance and technical aspects of data spaces, and other initiatives by the Data Spaces Support Centre⁸. The collaborative nature of the Handbook’s development has made it possible to benefit from examples of RIs organised into federation-like systems in scientific communities.

The scope of the Handbook is currently limited to topics on which there is consensus in the community, refraining from matters that require more discussion and decisions by the Tripartite or the future EOSC Federation governance. The Handbook’s chapter structure as of Q1 2025 is included in Table 1. The latest public version can be found on the Handbook webpage.

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purpose, expected outcomes and measures of success 2. Governance 3. Operational structure and responsibilities 4. EOSC Federation and Node Architecture 5. Research Resources 6. Joining the EOSC Federation
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Table 1: Chapters of the EOSC Federation Handbook (status by Q1 2025).

⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>

⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/handbook-operations>

⁶ GBIF Secretariat (2019), *Establishing an Effective GBIF Participant Node: Concepts and general considerations*. <https://doi.org/10.15468/doc-z79c-sa53>.

⁷ <https://dssc.eu/space/bv15e/766061169/Data+Spaces+Blueprint+v1.5+-+Home>

⁸ <https://dssc.eu>

2.2. Creation process

Task 5.1 contributed from the start of EOSC Focus to the evolution of the “Rules of Participation” that resulted from the EOSC Executive Board’s Working Group on the topic⁹. During the first period, the work focused on understanding the implications of organising EOSC as a federation. The broader context was examined as well, together with proposed rules, specifications and other artefacts from earlier projects and working groups required for its implementation. The result of this activity was reported in the deliverable D5.1¹⁰, and encompassed

- a description of the essential characteristics of (techno-social-cultural) federations, and their applicability to the EOSC Federation;
- a list of components suggested to form the Governance Framework of the EOSC Federation.

Preparations for the Handbook coincided with the start of the work on the EOSC EU Node in early 2024¹¹. A tentative table of contents, created by EOSC-A (with support from T5.1), was discussed with all EOSC stakeholders in March 2024. At the meeting of the Tripartite Governance in April 2024, the mandate given to EOSC-A to lead the process of writing the Handbook was formally approved.

Two teams of volunteer writers and reviewers were selected by EOSC-A via an open call in May 2024. A first round of input was collected during the second day of the EOSC-A General Assembly on 28 May 2024: in three parallel breakout sessions co-organised by T5.1, attendees formulated around 150 questions about the EOSC Federation and EOSC Nodes that should be answered in the Handbook. The questions, together with the corresponding answers (if known), were mapped to specific chapters of the Handbook to identify where the writing effort should be focused.

The collaborative writing started in June 2024. Writers tackled one chapter at a time, discussing progress in the weekly meetings, with Reviewers convening on a monthly basis to provide feedback. The editors¹² processed the feedback received, and combined the draft text into a coherent format, removing redundancy and ensuring clarity. In October 2024 a first round of feedback was received through a community consultation on the draft of the three first chapters (introduction, governance, organisational structure). More feedback was received on the first full draft generated after review by the Tripartite Group and the EOSC EU Node consortium in December 2024. The EOSC-A chief editor prepared the final draft, taking into account all the feedback received and ensuring the final text reflected the views of the stakeholders. A first full version of the Handbook was produced in March 2025, and distributed to the first “wave” of Nodes at the EOSC Federation Build-up Phase Kickoff meeting on 17-18 March in Brussels. Further input will be collected from the Nodes later in 2025. Looking into the future, the Handbook will be updated once the rules and working procedures of the EOSC Federation are agreed by the EOSC Nodes and approved by the Federation’s governance.

Due to the support by T5.1 the generation of the first version of the Handbook could progress according to the timeline agreed within the Tripartite Governance. The T5.1 team will remain engaged until the task is passed on to the EOSC Gravity project in June 2025.

⁹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *EOSC rules of participation*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/30541>.

¹⁰ EOSC Focus D5.1: <https://zenodo.org/records/10931890>.

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-announces-winners-eosc-procurement>

¹² Details on the composition of the editorial team, as well as the writers and reviewers involved in the process, can be found in <https://eosc.eu/eosc-federation-handbook/>.

3. Supporting the EOSC-A in engaging the S/ACs (T5.2)

The main role of T5.2 in the second reporting period was to support the EOSC Association on the work related to the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation. This took shape along two lines:

1. Support the engagement with the EOSC Association Mandated Organisations in relation to the EOSC Nodes to be established in the different countries,
2. Contribute to the creation of a new narrative for EOSC to support the EOSC Steering Board members to make the case for EOSC with their governments and constituencies, and to clarify the options for funding and governance of future scenarios for EOSC.

3.1. Support to EOSC-A Mandated Organisations

EOSC Focus Task 5.2 supported the EOSC Association in preparing the activities related to engagement with the Member States and Associated Countries and the discussions related to the governance and sustainability of EOSC¹³. As the governance and future of EOSC post-2027 are activities steered by the EOSC Tripartite Governance, the T5.2 team adopted a flexible approach to support the EOSC Association in that endeavour rather than coming up with separate plans.

The first activity performed in the reporting period M19-M34 leveraged on the “country matrix”, created already in M1-M18, to support the EOSC Association and the EOSC Tripartite in understanding the situation of EU Member States and Associated Countries by providing information regarding the following topics:

- Engagement in EOSC: representation in the EOSC SB, existence of an EOSC-A Mandated Organisation (MO) and its role in the country, EOSC-A Members and Observers, organisations engaged in INFRAEOSC projects, and initiatives such as CoARA, CONOSC and EuroHPC JU;
- EOSC-related policies: participation in ERA¹⁴ actions, existence of national programmes for Open Science, Open Science policies;
- Financial investments: investments in EOSC or in Open Science programmes;
- Demographics: number of researchers in relation to the population size of a country.

In month M19 (December 2023), the matrix was used by the EOSC Association to establish the priorities under which the interaction with countries and site visits to discuss the future of EOSC post-2027 should be organised. The matrix served as reference to support the activities organised by the EOSC Association with the Mandated Organisations (MOs). Figure 1 provides a screenshot of the country matrix.

After the EOSC Tripartite issued a questionnaire in the summer of 2024 to capture the interest of European organisations in becoming an EOSC Node¹⁵, it became clear that many MOs were considering setting up a node of national or thematic scope.

¹³ Activities related to the community engagement of relevant stakeholders from different countries across Europe were addressed in WP2 under the responsibility of the regional hubs, and are reported in *D2.2. - Engagement Activities Review*.

¹⁴ European Research Area (ERA) Policy Agenda 2022-2024 <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024>

¹⁵ For details of this process, cf. <https://bit.ly/EOSC-Federation-buildup-phase>.

	Representation in Steering Board (SB) (updated 12.4.2023)	Name of the organisation representing in SB (updated 12.4.2023)	Mandated Organisation (MO) appointed (updated 12.4.2023)	Name of the Mandated Organisation (updated 12.4.2023)	Role of the Mandated organisation	Type of the Mandated organisation	Engagement policy	Number of EOOSC-A members (updated 12.4.2023)
Austria	Yes	Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research	Yes	ACONET Association		Association for Promotion of NREN (not the actual NREN)	The ACONET Verein Association has been appointed by the Austrian institutions, members of EOOSC	5
Belgium	Yes	Department of Economy, Science and Innovation (EWI)	Yes	Belnet	Representing members and non-members in the EOOSC-A. Facilitating communication	NREN	National structure: the interregional concertation group Open Science of the International	12
Bulgaria	Yes	Ministry of Education and Science	No	-	-	-		1
Croatia	Yes	University of Zagreb, University Computing Centre - SRCE	Yes	University of Zagreb University Computing Centre (SRCE)	Competence centre for information and communication technologies, as well as the centre for	e-infrastructure provider for science and education	SRCE and the Ruder Bošković Institute have participated in the NI40S-Europe project that facilitated	-
Cyprus	Yes	Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy	No	-	-	-		-
Czech Republic	Yes	Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MŠYS)	Yes	CESNET	Operation and development of the national infrastructure for	Association of universities	1) Programme J.A. Comenius (2021-27, total budget EUR 120 million) contains calls	4

Figure 1: Screenshot of the country matrix

To help them address the challenges they are expected to face in developing EOOSC Nodes, EOOSC-A organised from November 2024 meetings with MOs to discuss topics related to the EOOSC Federation, and in particular the preparations by the countries to implement the concept of “EOOSC Node”. The T5.2 team has supported EOOSC-A to chair the meetings with the MOs, preparing agendas, and providing information about the development of the policy landscape, technological and RI initiatives under development, etc., in the countries where the MOs are based. T5.2 also set up a Miro board¹⁶ to capture the relevant information about MOs and the EOOSC Nodes emerging in the countries.

By the end of March 2025, the following MOs have presented plans in their respective countries to build an EOOSC Node and join the EOOSC Federation: SURF (Netherlands); CESNET (Czech Republic); NFDI (Germany); HEAnet (Ireland); INRIA (France); GARR (Italy). The main takeaways from the meetings with MOs can be summarised as follows:

- MOs play different roles depending on the country. In some countries they match the potential future EOOSC Nodes (e.g. SURF and NFDI), whereas in others they are involved in the consortia set up to establish the national node (e.g. CESNET, GARR), but are not leading themselves. In other countries, MOs are not directly involved, at least in the initial phase.
- The plans to establish the EOOSC Federation differ between countries, and depend on the maturity of the MOs, their role in the country, engagement in EOOSC, and policy and funding support at national level. For example, the Netherlands and Germany have consolidated national Open Science and data infrastructure programmes that create a very good context and adequate conditions to achieve a structured approach to the EOOSC Federation.
- Countries with scattered national infrastructures tend to focus their effort on setting up the national environment for the future EOOSC Node. An example is the Czech Republic, which is working on the implementation of a national data infrastructure. In these countries, the potential EOOSC Node is usually managed via a consortium.

¹⁶ This is the link to the online version of the Miro board (only accessible for EOOSC Association Mandated Organisations): <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVLDA50sM=/>

- Coordination mechanisms at national level seem to be the key instruments to conceptualise the national node and interact with the relevant stakeholders. There is consensus that national EOSC Nodes of European RIs are important players to be engaged in the co-design.
- Countries are leveraging different funding instruments to support the node conceptualisation and early build-up phase: structural funds (e.g. the Czech Republic), or national programmes for Open Science or data infrastructures (e.g. Germany).
- MOs and countries are using different tools and methods to approach the conceptualisation of the node. One example is the RDA GORC model which, for example, SURF is using for the Dutch national EOSC Node.

Figure 2: Screenshot from the MOs Miro Board.

The meetings with MOs will continue after the end of EOSC Focus under the responsibility of the EOSC Association.

3.2. A new narrative for EOSC

T5.2 has also supported the creation of a “new narrative” for EOSC. The need for a new narrative emerged when the complexity of putting EOSC in the context of the broader landscape became clear. There was the need for a new narrative that governments and representatives of constituencies can easily understand. In order to do this, EOSC-A leveraged the publication of the report by Enrico Letta¹⁷ presented to the European Council in April 2024 on the future of the internal market, and published a reflection paper, with the support of T5.2 in drafting the content, elaborating on how EOSC can contribute to improve Europe’s competitiveness.

Starting from the analysis of how Europe has changed fundamentally since the Single Market was launched and its crucial importance in strengthening European competitiveness, the Letta report

¹⁷ Enrico Letta, *Much more than a market* (2024), also known as “The Letta report”, <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/ny3j24sm/much-more-than-a-market-report-by-enrico-letta.pdf>

provides policy recommendations for the future of the Single Market. One of the main recommendations is to create “a fifth freedom dedicated to research, innovation, knowledge and education” that supports policy and decision makers with evidence-based information necessary to deal with complex new scenarios. The “fifth freedom” makes reference to the other freedoms previously defined, i.e. the free movement of goods, capital, services, and people enabled by the Single Market. This is well aligned with the vision and aims of EOSC, thus providing an excellent opportunity to EOSC-A to produce a reflection paper. The reflection paper is available on the EOSC website¹⁸. Key messages include:

- EOSC’s mission and the broader political agenda are closely aligned with the vision of establishing a “fifth freedom” dedicated to research, innovation, knowledge, and education.
- EOSC supports European digital and data sovereignty by adhering to European relevant regulations like GDPR, ensuring secure data sharing and compliance with ethical standards.
- EOSC advances the Open Science movement and related policy initiatives to foster trust, equity and inclusivity in research.
- EOSC contributes by minimizing the economic costs of inefficient data management (estimated at over €10 billion annually) and fostering innovation through accessible, high-quality research data.
- EOSC enables economies of scale, offering researchers and businesses access to shared resources that complement those within their own countries or communities, supporting larger-scale projects with greater efficiency.

The reflection paper was presented to the EOSC Tripartite Governance and at the EOSC Symposium 2024. The paper was considered very useful by the EOSC SB and the EC, who asked for a new version, not specifically linked to the Letta report, but as a more general description of how EOSC supports policy initiatives and societal challenges. T5.2 has contributed with editorial support to the drafting of the new version, published in March 2025¹⁹. The paper addresses EOSC's impacts relative to:

- European digital and data sovereignty
- Security in research and data management
- Boosting European productivity and innovation
- Advancing social equity and inclusivity
- Fostering European leadership in artificial intelligence
- Strengthening European research infrastructure
- Addressing Grand Societal Challenges and enhancing Europe’s global scientific competitiveness

¹⁸ Materials related to the creation process of the reflection paper: <https://eosc.eu/news/2024/11/eosc-association-publishes-reflection-paper-on-letta-report/>

¹⁹ EOSC-A, *Why EOSC is pivotal for European competitiveness? Reflections of the EOSC Association on the Letta report* (2024). <https://zenodo.org/records/15083486>. Link to news item: <https://eosc.eu/news/2025/03/why-eosc-is-pivotal-to-european-competitiveness/>

4. Resourcing models for the sustainability of EOSC (T5.3)

4.1. Funding models for EOSC

Task 5.3 was conceived to collect knowledge on the topic of the financial sustainability of EOSC. The Federation, and the resource providers and users involved, need long-term funding models that ensure they can perform their tasks. Predictable and adequate funding models can help assure that the money “flows” where it is needed, and solve the question of how the costs of running the EOSC Federation will be paid for. It is expected that the enhanced collaboration opportunities and better access to resources brought by the EOSC Federation will increase the consumption of services, and consequently the associated costs are bound to rise, also for providers.

The results from the T5.3 work (partly in collaboration with WP4) carried out in M19-M34 are presented in this section. The insights obtained can serve as a basis for future discussions about how a financially stable EOSC Federation can be achieved.

Process

In the first months of 2024, representatives of the EOSC-A Board of Directors and T5.3 discussed how to progress from the preparatory work on the resourcing models described in deliverable D5.1²⁰. Agreement was reached on the role of T5.3 and the tasks to be carried out in support of the Board and the wider EOSC Partnership in the design of the future governance and funding model for EOSC. In this role, T5.3 has examined various legal models and funding mechanisms to identify the features and benefits which could be relevant for the future of EOSC.

Methodology

The activities in T5.3 have included desk-based research, interviews with selected representatives from RIs, e-Infrastructures, and work subcontracted to the company Boundaryless, covering:

- Viable business models for actors using the EOSC platform and Sustainable Exploitation Planning methodology;
- Financial aspects and treatment of in-kind contributions in Horizon Europe Partnerships under Article 185 of the Treaty for the European Union (TFEU);
- EuroHPC Joint Undertaking as an example of a European Partnership under Art. 187 TFEU, a possible legal form for EOSC;
- Virtual Access as a mechanism to fund cross-border provision and consumption (use) of services and resources;
- The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (or ERIC) model as a funding vehicle to sustain the operations of RIs, in particular the collaborative aspect of their relationship to enable cross-border scientific work, and including the role of in-kind contributions.

What is a platform? The term ‘platform’ is used to signify a place (virtual in the case of virtual platforms) that mediates between producers and consumers of (online) sources and which facilitates buying, selling, or more generally the exchange of products or services. It typically comes with a governance structure, protocols and standards. A platform may also enable cooperation towards a common goal by providing an environment to meet others with whom an interest is shared. EOSC exemplifies this concept as a digital platform created for the exchange of resources resulting from research activities and the facilitation of their (re)use, including data, tools, and services.

²⁰ Rey Mazón, M., Dietrich, M., Garavelli, S., Picard, J., & Robertson, D. (2024), EOSC Focus - D5.1 - EOSC Resourcing models, <https://zenodo.org/records/10931890>.

Summaries of the findings for each individual topic are provided in the remainder of section 4. For the full documentation created in the process, readers are referred to the appendices.

4.2. Options for enhancing the financial sustainability of EOSC

European Partnerships: pooling costs to pay for the costs of EOSC

While the final report by the EOSC-A Financial Sustainability Task Force²¹ formulated the principles guiding the design of the EOSC funding model and estimated associated costs, T5.3 has examined how these principles can be implemented using available financial and legal instruments for collective action, pending their reformulation in the forthcoming Framework Programme post-2027. A review of institutionalised European Partnerships under Articles 185 and 187 TFEU (the latter known as "Joint Undertakings") suggests that both models offer useful features for structuring EOSC funding. The choice between them, assuming similar instruments will be available, depends on several factors, including the potential involvement of private partners (currently exclusive to Joint Undertakings) and how in-kind contributions from members are classified.

RIs and Open Science services: Context and recommendations for long-term funding

Research Infrastructures play a pivotal role as providers of FAIR data and services within the EOSC ecosystem, making their financial sustainability integral to EOSC's long-term success. However, current RI funding is predominantly short-term and project-based, raising significant concerns among stakeholders about sustaining cross-border open science services. Extensive interviews and comprehensive research conducted with RI representatives revealed three interconnected funding challenges: (1) securing reliable, long-term financial commitments from EU Member States; (2) mitigating increasing budgetary constraints at national and EU levels; and (3) identifying a funding model that effectively balances open access mandates with economic viability.

These challenges arise within a demanding economic and geopolitical context. According to RI representatives, Member States (MS) face escalating pressures from:

- Persistent inflation and high energy costs
- Rising defense spending
- Europe's relative lag in digital transformation and artificial intelligence capabilities

These factors collectively constrain public budgets available for research investments, causing a critical funding gap and uncertainty about RI funding stability.

The EC historically has provided essential seed funding for RIs through Framework Programmes, while responsibility for long-term operational costs rests with MS. Nevertheless, EC funding priorities significantly influence national RI investments. Currently, all principal RI funding streams—including EU competitive grants, Structural Funds, membership fees, and in-kind contributions—depend substantially on EU support. National commitments frequently leverage EU-funded projects or co-funded programs, creating structural dependency. RI representatives underscored that if EU financial support declines, MS' ability to maintain their contributions may falter, threatening EOSC's viability.

²¹ Robertson, D., Meijer, J., et al. (2024), *Recommendations for a Financially Sustainable Post-2027 EOSC*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11317576>.

Based on insights from extensive stakeholder consultations and detailed analysis, three key recommendations emerged to avoid persistent reliance on short-term project funding and safeguard EOSC's long-term strategic vision:

1. Long-term joint EC–MS/AC funding for EOSC nodes: RI representatives strongly support establishing **non-competitive joint funding schemes** between the EC and MS/AC, with a longer time span²². These schemes should ensure sustained financial support for the ongoing maintenance, operation, and development of EOSC nodes, thereby enabling stable and reliable uptake of RI services.
2. **Harmonised assessment of RI contributions**: Stakeholders recommend developing a standardised assessment framework to consistently evaluate RI contributions to EOSC. Such a framework should prioritise scientific excellence while also incorporating socio-economic impact, alignment with national technological and societal objectives, and enhancing EU competitiveness.
3. Gradual adoption of **transaction-based revenue models**: RI representatives advocate introducing transaction-based revenue models (e.g., usage fees or data-service charges) to monetize certain EOSC outputs. This approach would promote stronger engagement with industry and generate additional revenue streams without compromising the neutrality and accessibility of fundamental research.

4.3. Platform business models and Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology

4.3.1. Procurement process

EOSC Focus subcontracted an analysis of the requirements of key customer segments for delivering and consuming research data services via online portals or platforms to validate and improve the resourcing models described in *D5.1 - Resourcing models*. The analysis subcontracted was anticipated in the DoA which listed as a WP5 action “to access specialist economics and accountancy expertise needed to consider, validate and improve resourcing models for Task 5.3”.

The request for proposals, issued in April 2023, aimed to identify a contractor with the right economics expertise to determine the features that the EOSC platform should have to attract end users and providers, and the business models for making the exchange through the platform sustainable for all involved. The company Boundaryless SL was awarded the contract, and the work was carried out between June and November 2023. The results are reported in section 4.3.2.

The preliminary results together with the findings on the business models described in D5.1, inspired an additional piece of work that enriched the outputs generated by WP4 regarding the methodology for helping consortia of EOSC-related projects to elucidate plans for the sustainable exploitation of their results. The main conclusions of this additional work are presented below in section 4.3.3. The detailed reports for both activities can be found in [Appendix 1](#).

²² European IP Helpdesk, Successful Valorisation of Knowledge and Research Results in Horizon Europe (2022). Link: intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu. This EU guide explains that project impacts are expected in the long term (~7 years) beyond project start, underscoring that Horizon-funded innovations need ongoing exploitation efforts well after the initial 3–4-year project.

4.3.2. Business models for EOSC as a service platform

As reported in D5.1, the work subcontracted aimed at identifying the characteristics which the “EOSC platform” should have to serve as a facilitator of transactions between providers and consumers of data-related resources. The underlying assumption was that EOSC will have better perspectives for becoming sustainable if the design of the platform implies attractive value propositions for the actors in the EOSC ecosystem, and if it promotes business models for the exchange of resources through the platform.

The use of the term “platform” employed when the work was defined in the spring of 2023 is still appropriate in the current understanding of EOSC, since it is still envisioned to function as an environment where providers and users exchange resources to obtain value from the transaction, which describes well what a platform does²³. The implementation of EOSC as a federation represents a realisation of the conceptual view provided by the “Minimum Viable EOSC”²⁴, but does not essentially change how the exchange of resources is done (via the Internet, roughly speaking), which is independent of the form adopted to enable it from the organisational point of view (i.e. the federation). The “virtual environment” formed by the technical solutions to share resources employed by the EOSC Nodes still constitutes a platform in the sense mentioned above.

The analysis focussed on the “value chain” of actions performed by three key customer segments in EOSC (researchers, research performing organisations, and service and data providers), to find out how the EOSC platform can facilitate transactions and add value, i.e. what are EOSC’s value propositions for these customer segments. The methodology applied is based on the assumption that once the desired functionalities are known, one can identify the tasks the platform needs to perform. It is then possible to select which functionalities may be turned into revenue streams to contribute to the platform’s sustainability. In addition, the analysis suggests the business models most suitable to help providers and consumers extract the maximum value of the transactions via the EOSC platform.

The relation between the characteristics of the EOSC platform and the business models for providers and end-users is illustrated in [Table 1](#) in Appendix 1. The table shows the combinations of actions facilitated by the platform, the relevant user segments, and the related business models. For example, the platform would benefit researchers (consumers of generic and thematic (i.e. discipline-specific) resources) and resource providers and aggregators, if it facilitated the “selling” and accounting of resource provision and consumption across borders, by offering tools for resource discovery and service accounting. The platform could provide this functionality using a freemium model.

To realise the full potential of the EOSC platform and enable the evolution of an efficient and sustainable ecosystem, the organisation governing the platform needs to evolve too. The actions suggested are summarised in the following table (Table 2):

²³ For more information on platforms, see e.g. Simone Cicero, *Exploring Ecosystems: The Patterns of Platformization*, <https://bit.ly/Patterns-of-platformization>, published in *Stories of Platform Design* (2018) <https://stories.platformdesigntoolkit.com>.

²⁴ European Commission: DG RTD, *Solutions for a sustainable EOSC – A FAIR Lady (olim Iron Lady) report from the EOSC Sustainability Working Group*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/870770>.

Conclusion from analysis	Action suggested
The EOSC governance needs to offer simple procurement processes and optimise the opportunities for users to compare between offers and providers.	Reduce paperwork by pre-qualifying providers and consumers; standardise services catalogues and on-boarding procedures to promote discoverability; facilitate aggregation of heterogeneous small providers where possible.
EOSC should have the authority and funding to decide about how money is spent on Open Science-related projects.	Establish the EOSC Federation and its Management Organisation under an appropriate instrument of the running Framework Programme with the necessary funds and decision authority.
The governance and the processes related to it must connect all the key stakeholders.	Design the governance of the EOSC Federation to be inclusive and involve all stakeholders.
Incentives are needed for EOSC to attract stakeholders.	Create an “EOSC index” to acknowledge active participation in the EOSC platform and increase researchers’ reputation in the ecosystem.
Promotion of standardisation and defragmentation is a critical success factor.	Completion and implementation of the EOSC Interoperability Framework.
The development of self-service and self-composable interfaces should be enabled.	Standardise interfaces, agree on metadata taxonomies for resources.
EOSC can progress towards sustainability by introducing revenue streams from transactions and service subscription fees.	Establish clear criteria for transactions on which markup is applied and implement it consistently.
EOSC (more precisely, the EOSC Federation Management Organisation) should be able to act as a centralised procurement office.	Ensure the necessary authority is given to the EOSC Federation Management Organisation by the EC and MS/AC to conduct procurement.
The cost of the EOSC Federation core federated services should be covered from revenues from transactions in the platform.	Select a funding model that is compatible with the form chosen for the EOSC Federation and that allows transaction fees to be charged.
EOSC needs to become a “super-platform” that coordinates and connects with other platforms.	Establish links and integrate with resource aggregators (EGI, GÉANT, OpenAIRE, EUDAT).

Table 2 - Conclusions of the platform analysis and changes suggested for the platform owner

These conclusions and recommendations, together with some quantitative details, the methodology adopted and the process followed during the task execution, are explained in detail in part 1 of [Appendix 1](#).

4.3.3. Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) Methodology

The work in T5.3 on sustainable business models for organisations delivering and consuming data and services in EOSC suggested, in a serendipitous way, that the contractors’ expertise could be

utilised to refine the Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology developed for the exploitation of results from EOSC-related projects. The sustainability of EOSC is understood to depend strongly on the successful exploitation of these results, as projects develop tools and services essential to implement Open Science. The work was done in collaboration between WP4 and WP5.

The responsibility to come up with pathways for post-project exploitation of results is left to project consortia (as in all EC-funded projects). However, often consortia do not dedicate substantial resources and lack the expertise to succeed in this task. To address this, several activities have been undertaken by EOSC Focus to support consortia in the exploitation of their output. In particular, the Horizon Europe Project Impact Working Group²⁵ (HE Impact WG) was established within the scope of Task 4.4 to support projects in planning the exploitation phase of their Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and maximising the impact of their work. The support provided was also meant to facilitate projects fulfilling their obligation to produce and implement sustainability plans, according to Art. 16 of the Grant Agreement.

A first step was to ask projects to identify their KERs together with the key challenges faced to ensure their (sustainable) exploitation. From these discussions, it became evident that projects require early-stage guidance to define clear exploitation pathways. This led Task 4.4 to develop the Sustainable Exploitation Planning methodology, first introduced at EOSC Winter School 2024 during the session on "Sustainable Exploitation of HE Projects' KERs for Impact".

The publication of deliverable D5.1 provided relevant concepts for the EOSC platform business models. This was achieved using Wardley mapping routines and a portfolio of business model choices, which were applied by WP4 to detail the exploitation process of KERs to a finer grain and diversify the project's options to achieve sustainability. T4.4's team tested the SEP methodology with the projects in the framework of the HE Impact WG, and conducted pilot exercises to fine-tune it. This culminated in a session on sustainability at the EC-REA meeting with INFRAEOSC projects in June 2024 where the key challenges faced by the projects, as retrieved from their application of the SEP methodology, were presented. A key factor is that the uncertainties around the governance and implementation strategy for EOSC hinder the definition of clear "destinations" (i.e. potential adopters or buyers) for their results and, consequently, prevent the definition of clear pathways for exploitation of KERs. The work is summarised in part 2 of [Appendix 1](#).

Clarity on possible destinations for project KERs has begun to emerge more recently, thanks to the rapid evolution of the EOSC landscape with the start of operations of the EOSC EU Node and the selection of the first wave of EOSC Nodes to form the EOSC Federation—accompanied with the writing of the EOSC Federation Handbook—together with the insights from the EOSC Winter School 2025, in which sustainability remained a central topic. An additional support measure has been suggested for consideration by the EOSC Tripartite Governance: the establishment of a roadmap to facilitate the uptake of project results within EOSC. These ideas will influence the evolution of the SEP methodology in the follow-up project EOSC Gravity. The synergies between WP4 and WP5 have thus helped projects increase the maturity of their ideas so that they are better equipped to face the challenges of exploiting their results sustainably, and have raised the attention paid to sustainability within the EOSC tripartite collaboration.

²⁵ For more details, see EOSC Association (2022), *Vademecum - A Handbook for Effective Collaboration within the EOSC co-programmed Partnership*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11047457>.

4.4. Financial and sustainability aspects of Horizon Europe Partnerships and other types of collaboration

T5.3 has collected information on funding and legal instruments employed under Horizon Europe: Institutionalised European Partnerships under articles 185 and 187 of the Treaty for the European Union, virtual access, and funding models employed by research infrastructures (and in particular the model of European Research Infrastructure Consortia, i.e. ERICs). The work was done in alignment with the EOSC-A Board, and with T3.3 - *Liaise with European Partnerships and other relevant initiatives*, also on European Partnerships, but with a specific focus on governance. The purpose of the analyses performed was two-fold:

- (i) obtain insight into how different stakeholders in the EOSC landscape use access to funding to achieve their goals, into the challenges they face, and into what works well, and identify the issues remaining to be solved for a well-functioning system;
- (ii) assess the suitability of current partnership instruments (pending their update in the forthcoming Framework Programme after Horizon Europe i.e. post-2027), and in particular of their financing and funding mechanisms, for the access to and usage of resources from (and for) research in the EOSC Federation, including the operation of tools and services.

This section presents the main conclusions from the studies conducted for each of the instruments.

4.4.1. Funding and legal instruments: Virtual Access and European Partnerships

In order to address complex challenges that require long-term collaboration with other partners, the European Union (via the EC) started in 2002 the European Partnerships (EP). Partnerships provide the legal framework to share the responsibility of managing and funding activities on a topic of strategic interest between the EC, EU MS governments, other public bodies, or private partners. This instrument is conceived to ensure the commitment of all involved by having all partners agree on a work programme, financial details, etc. After the experience in Horizon 2020²⁶, the definition and implementation process of EPs were updated so that under Horizon Europe they would remain fit for purpose.

An instrument complementary to Partnerships is Virtual Access (VA), a financial mechanism for reimbursing the costs of provision of services by RIs. A similar financial mechanism is used to compensate for the costs of several different forms of access to resources: trans-national access, remote access and virtual access. T5.3 studied VA as a financial mechanism to assess its relevance and potential for use in connection with EOSC.

Virtual Access as a Funding Mechanism

The Open Science agenda encourages secondary use of data and cross-disciplinary research, giving rise to demand for access to and use of resources by users outside of the resource providers' primary communities. Such usage is often cross-border and/or cross-domain, or even cross-institutional within a single country. However, in most domains resource providers are typically funded for access provision only within their primary user communities. Provision to other communities requires a mechanism to fund the extra costs incurred, in cases where the user is not otherwise eligible to

²⁶ For details on the assessment of (institutionalised) European Partnerships performed, see *Impact assessment for institutionalised European partnerships under Horizon Europe*, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/295096>

consume resources. The financial instrument used to reimburse the costs of trans-national, remote or virtual access may be relevant as a possible solution to address this need.

EOSC Focus thus studied the experience of the EOSC-hub²⁷ and INFRAEOSC-07 projects (C-SCALE²⁸, DICE²⁹, EGI-ACE³⁰, OpenAIRE Nexus³¹ and RELIANCE³²) with use of Virtual Access (VA) as a funding mechanism, and considered whether a VA-type instrument could provide added value in the context of EOSC. The work concluded that (i) it may be of interest to consider use of such a mechanism on a longer-term basis in the post-2027 EOSC, for example as part of a “programme”, whether a European Partnership or another legal form, for 7-10 years, and (ii) that it may be worth bearing this option in mind when considering the future legal model(s) for the post-2027 EOSC. Several possible strands of further work on this topic are identified, to which EOSC Focus may contribute in the remainder of the project (M35-M36). The full report is included as [Appendix 2](#).

Institutionalised European Partnership under Art. 185 and Art. 187 TFEU: common features

Task 5.3 has complemented work performed by EOSC Focus Task 3.3, reported in deliverable *D3.3 - Technical collaboration report with other European Partnerships and relevant initiatives*³³ by studying the structure and financial models of Institutionalised European Partnerships (IEPs) under Articles 185 or 187 TFEU. Both types of IEPs imply a larger and longer-term financial commitment from partners, requiring in both cases cash contributions from all partners (unlike Co-programmed EPs, which allow for the contribution from partners other than the EC to be in-kind). The total cash and/or in-kind contributions from non-EC members in an IEP equals at least 50%, and may reach up to 75% of the aggregated budgetary commitments.

IEPs grant their members a high degree of autonomy in shaping their strategy, annual work programmes, and call topics, but these are still subject to the approval of the EC.

IEPs under Art 185 TFEU

Institutionalised European Partnerships (IEPs) under Art 185 TFEU pool funding from EU MS/AC bodies (national, regional, or other) and the EC to fund research activities on a topic of strategic interest for both the Union and the countries. T5.3 explored the details of their financial setup, with attention paid to how the funding is implemented and how in-kind contributions from participating countries are counted towards the goals of the partnership. The key takeaways can be summarised as follows:

- This type of partnership can make a difference in topics with no strong interest from the private sector, or where the strategic character of the topic, or the complexity of challenge, makes it advisable to “retain” it under full control by public authorities.
- To ensure the success of Art 185 Partnerships, the EU and the countries need to align their priorities and strategies on the topic at hand prior to embarking on the rather lengthy process for their preparation and implementation.

²⁷ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>

²⁸ <https://c-scale.eu/>

²⁹ <https://www.dice-eosc.eu/>

³⁰ <https://www.egi.eu/project/egi-ace/>

³¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/openaire-nexus-project>

³² <https://www.reliance-project.eu/>

³³ EOSC Focus D3.3 will be made available on the EOSC Focus web page: <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/>

- Art 185 Partnerships depend on the appropriate topics being covered in the running EC Framework Programme, and the presence of suitable R&I programmes in the countries, or real commitment to implement them when the Partnership takes off.
- The activities funded by the Partnerships can be managed by either the entity responsible for implementing the Partnership (“Designated Implementation Structure”), or by funding organisations from participating countries.
- Activities towards goals aligned with those of the Partnership that are funded and managed by national research programmes are counted as in-kind contributions (these are known as “Participating States Initiated Activities” or PSIAAs).
- The full report is included as [Appendix 3](#).

IEPs under Art. 187 TFEU – EuroHPC Joint Undertaking

T5.3 studied the structure and financial model of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (JU) as an example of an Art 187 IEP. The work indicates that the EuroHPC JU successfully acts as the vehicle for achieving the EuroHPC objectives. Key cornerstones of the model are:

- The dedicated JU Regulation providing the required procurement framework;
- Capacity is free at the point of use, avoiding cross-border issues related to purchasing or consumption;
- The EU is allocated 50% of the computing capacity to support EU policy aims;
- The 50% EU funding contribution provides an incentive to countries to participate and acts as “glue”;
- Countries benefit from increased compute capacity at a lower risk than if they acted individually;
- A policy and legislative programme provides a wider framework in support of EuroHPC.

The study, included as [Appendix 4](#), suggests that use of a JU as a possible legal model for EOSC post-2027 is worthy of some consideration due to the specific legal protections and allowances which can be afforded under this model. Additionally, or alternatively, a possible analogy may be drawn between EuroHPC and a future EOSC legal entity as a legal and funding vehicle (not necessarily a JU) to coordinate efforts and pool resources at European level, to develop and deploy services to exploit the full potential of research data. The note suggests that such an analogy is worth further exploration.

4.4.2. Funding models for European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs)

The sustainable exploitation of Key Exploitable Results (KER) from EOSC-related projects³⁴ depends to a great extent on the sustainability of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) involved in the projects, and in particular of European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) and INFRAEOSC Science Cluster projects³⁵ that brought together RIs from all key ESFRI domains.³⁶ These pan-European RIs together with their nodes will be among the leading service providers in the EOSC Federation. As a consequence, their challenges to become sustainable are relevant to EOSC’s sustainability.

³⁴ Ilaria Nardello, Ari Asmi, René Buch, and Erik-Jan Bos (2022), *Delivering for EOSC: Key Exploitable Results of Horizon 2020 EOSC-related projects* <https://zenodo.org/records/7401539>.

³⁵ The impact of the 2019 INFRAEOSC cluster projects and in particular the model of collaboration among the five science clusters is summarised here: <https://science-clusters.eu/>.

³⁶ For more information on the ESFRI domains and the monitoring working groups, see <http://www.esfri.eu/working-groups>

In some distributed RIs, access to data and tools is already federated. As the EOSC Federation will be set up in a comparable manner, the main findings regarding the underlying financial models of ERICs and other distributed RIs are presented here. A more detailed analysis is included in [Appendix 5](#).

Main conclusions

Diversity of income streams is needed for ERICs to fund their activities. Not depending on any single specific source reduces the risks of funding cuts, although it can significantly increase the amount of administrative work required.

Dependence on membership fees and in-kind contributions to sustain the central office operations can put an ERIC at risk if there are changes in the countries' funding priorities. ERICs should ensure that their activity and scope contribute to the scientific agenda of the member countries.

Nodes within an ERIC rely to a large extent on long-term funding commitments from MS/AC. This can provide stability, but links their evolution to the national political cycle, which may lead to difficulties in case of misalignment between national priorities and the plans of the ERIC. Disparate levels of commitment between countries can also be challenging for the cohesion of the ERIC and for a stable service delivery.

EC funding will remain essential for any implementation of the EOSC Federation, as it ensures more equal access opportunities and supports the long-term sustainability of services and facilities, including those by RIs. However, the ERIC model comes with significant challenges due to the funding uncertainties inherent to competitive granting programmes and the fluctuating political commitment of member countries. The uncertainty in the funding of EOSC nodes may negatively affect the sustainability of EOSC.

Regarding in-kind contributions from MS, the EOSC Federation has to decide on the basis of which model activities funded by them or other stakeholders should be counted as investment into building and operating the EOSC Federation. Unification of criteria for accounting and valuation would be a good step in this direction. The information collected by EOSC-A on in-kind contributions to the EOSC Partnership from member and non-member organisations may provide a good basis.³⁷

Open questions

- If successful, EOSC is likely to significantly increase the demand for data services from RIs across Europe. It is not clear how or by whom the consequent increased costs of RI operations and maintenance will be funded, given mounting resource constraints faced by MS/AC.
- Providing access to data and services free at the point of use places significant financial demands on ERICs, which may strain membership fees. This is also a concern for the (free) cross-border provision of services, which may lead to high usage by non-member countries and raises concerns about the cost-benefit balance.

³⁷ EOSC-A is committed to report the IKCs annually. See: <https://eosc.eu/monitoring-reporting/additional-activities-in-kind-contributions-to-the-eosc-partnership/>

5. Expanding OS collaboration (T5.4)

By the end of the previous project period, work under T5.4 led to an overview of relevant OS-related initiatives and organisations around the globe involved in the shaping and implementation of the global Open Science (OS) agenda and the development of OS Commons. Among other things, the overview includes information on regional ecosystems for research infrastructures, regional and global platforms for the exchange of digital services that can help advance scientific excellence and citizen science, and knowledge exchange regarding research data management practices beyond the borders of continents.³⁸

In the project period from M19 onwards, this information has served as a basis for EOSC-A and EOSC Focus to plan communication with organisations from other continents to ensure EOSC and the EU strategy have a strong voice and visibility in the relevant parts of the global OS landscape.

5.1. Link with global Open Science initiatives and dynamics

Representatives of the EOSC Focus team (including but not limited to the WP5 team) have sought opportunities to monitor the international dynamics related to the Open Science agenda and to inform actors from other continents on the EOSC developments. Several invitations have been accepted for participation in events and meetings addressing OS topics with global relevance and/or highlighting developments in regions outside of Europe:

- Giving a presentation on EOSC in a panel session at the Arab event on Open Science at the ASREN/e-Age24 conference in Tunis, December 2024 ([link](#)).
- Delivery of a keynote on the implementation of the EOSC vision at the AustralAsian e-Research Conference, Melbourne, October 2024 ([link](#)).
- Participation in the institutional site visit organised by the International Alliance of Universities (IAU), Utrecht, April 2024 ([link](#)).
- Organisation of an international panel (Initiatives for data and service federation that can connect local and global practices) in the context of the International Data Week of the 21st plenary meeting of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) in Salzburg, October 2023 ([link](#)).
- Participation in the IAU 2024 International Conference in Tokyo, Japan, that introduced the IAU's report "Open Science, Challenge for Universities", as the first deliverable of its Open Science Expert Group ([link](#)).

5.2. Foreseen next steps

To strengthen the collaboration towards a global interoperability framework that could facilitate the emergence of global Open Science Commons, several routes could be further explored. Topics to prioritise: generic and discipline-specific standards, models for the harmonisation of practices and organisational interoperability, international alignment of the rewards and incentives frameworks.

The following steps have been suggested by representatives of the EOSC community and stakeholders:

³⁸ The overview was reported EOSC Focus milestone MS10 ([link](#)).

- Consolidated formal and informal exchange with organisations such as CONOSC³⁹, OSCER⁴⁰, the UNESCO Global Open Science Partnership⁴¹, IAU⁴², ISC⁴³, GOSC/CODATA⁴⁴ and the Research Data Alliance (RDA)⁴⁵;
- Follow-up exchanges with the international parties that have participated in the international panel organised by EOSC Focus in M16 at the SciDataCon event organised in the context of the International Data Week of the 21st RDA plenary in Salzburg;
- Exploration of suitable modalities for collaboration between EOSC-A and the European chapter of the RDA.

³⁹ The Council for National Open Science Coordination (CoNOSC) is a network of national Open Science coordinators in the UN-European region. Url: <https://conosc.org/>

⁴⁰ OSCER stands for Open Science Commons Executives' Roundtable. Url: <https://www.oscer.info/>

⁴¹ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>

⁴² International Association of Universities. Url: <https://www.iau-aiu.net/>

⁴³ International Science Council (ISC). Url: <https://council.science/>

⁴⁴ Global Open Science Cloud. <https://codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work/global-open-science-cloud/>

⁴⁵ Research Data Alliance (RDA): <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

Appendix 1: Subcontracted work on business models for platforms

Part 1: Work related to Task 5.3

Written by Luca Ruggieri and Andrea Valeri (*Boundaryless SL*), summarised and edited by Dale Robertson (*EGI Foundation*) and Miguel Rey Mazón (*Graz University of Technology*)

Abstract

This appendix contains a summarised version of the work carried out by the company Boundaryless SL under subcontracting to develop business models for EOSC and the organisations foreseen to interact through the “EOSC platform”. Boundaryless SL was awarded the contract after completing the procurement process described on [section 4.3.1](#) of the main text (page 12).

Table of contents

1. Key actors and roles in the EOSC ecosystem	21
2. Value propositions, value chain, and analysis of the “as-is” system	22
3. Transforming EOSC’s value chain to envisage the future: the “to-be” system	24
4. Platform Strategy Models (PSMs)	30
5. Supporting key entities to achieve sustainability	31
6. List of relevant business models for the EOSC ecosystem scenarios	31
7. Combined result	35
8. Final recommendations	42

1. Key actors and roles in the EOSC ecosystem

To find sustainable business for the entities in the EOSC ecosystem, Boundaryless applied the “platform thinking” methodology to analyse the landscape in which they will operate. The method involves identifying first the key actors, and grouping them into roles. What is relevant is not who they are, but which actions they perform. In the next step, the main needs (or “value-driven behaviour”) of the roles and the interactions between them are identified. The methodology streamlines the complexity of the EOSC ecosystem, abstracting from the significant number of actors and stakeholder types. This approach aims to produce a more resilient, future-proofed design: new actors who wish to participate in EOSC (as user or provider) will be able to do so by “plugging in” themselves in the business models that correspond to their role in the system.

The analysis was performed with an awareness of the current lack of a sustainable business model for EOSC, focusing on addressing the sustainability challenges faced by many of the key actors, services and resources in the ecosystem.

In the first part of the analysis, we identified several “principles” applicable to relationships between roles, based on the idea that, in order to achieve sustainability, EOSC should become a *platform* that embraces and enhances the dynamism, diversity and collaborative potential inherent in the

ecosystem, aiming to ensure a robust, adaptable and sustainable environment for Open Science. The principles can be summarised as follows:

1. **Central role of key entities:** Research Infrastructures (RIs), including single-site (e.g. GENCI (Grand Equipement National de Calcul Intensif) in France⁴⁶ or the Binnig and Rohrer Nanotechnology Center in Switzerland⁴⁷), multi-site or distributed (e.g. LifeWatch ERIC⁴⁸), and international organisations (e.g. CERN⁴⁹) are crucial, serving multiple roles and acting as integrative hubs. This central position is pivotal for crafting business models that exploit their diverse engagements for systemic value creation.
2. **Interdependency, collaboration, and adaptability:** The ecosystem is marked by a strong interdependency and collaboration among entities, which often shift between producer and consumer roles. This highlights a vibrant and adaptable ecosystem. A platform strategy, by facilitating these interactions, can effectively address challenges like fragmentation, diversity, and variable scales. It is a resilient and adaptive response to the rapidly evolving needs of the EOSC environment.
3. **Balancing specialization with generalization:** The mixture of specialised and generalised entities in EOSC points to the need for business models that balance depth (through specialization) with breadth and innovation (through generalization). The ecosystem can self-manage these types of requests, by un-managing interactions.
4. **Leveraging enabling roles of funders and aggregators:** Funding bodies and aggregators play a critical enabling role. Business models should leverage these entities not just for financial support, but also as key players in integrating and catalyzing activities across the ecosystem.

Based on this preliminary analysis, the main roles which should be studied further, as key providers or consumers of value in the EOSC ecosystem, are:

1. *Researchers and research performing organisations* as consumers of value (services and data);
2. *Service providers and data providers* as main providers of value.

2. Value propositions, value chain, and analysis of the “as-is” system

The next step in the methodology is to analyse key interactions and use cases amongst the key players to produce a map of “areas of needs”. The map focuses on whether, and to what extent, the needs are currently satisfied, whether they are time-based (i.e. involve a sequential ordering before/after), and whether they are “enabling-enabled” by (i.e. value-driven). This is mapped onto a Wardley Map to show the current value chain.

The value chain map (Figure 1) shows the “value propositions” that the actors in EOSC seek to satisfy through interactions with other entities. For researchers, this means the actions they need to perform in the course of their work that bring value to them, and to which EOSC could potentially add value.

The map shows on the horizontal axis the “maturity level” of a value item from genesis to maturity, i.e. whether it is perceived as a commodity or rather a utility, with intermediate states as custom-built and

⁴⁶ <http://www.genci.fr/en>

⁴⁷ <https://www.zurich.ibm.com/brnc/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.lifewatch.eu/>

⁴⁹ <https://home.cern>

product/service, and the vertical axis represents the value's visibility perceived by researchers.

Some of the value propositions in the Wardley Map are already performed by researchers in the context of EOSC, but EOSC could still add value in some areas, e.g. improving efficiency, helping to save costs, offering additional central services to researchers, establishing standards, or contributing to improve the user experience.

WARDLEY MAP

AS-IS

Figure 1: AS-IS System

These other value propositions for researchers can enhance the overall value proposition of EOSC itself perceived by researchers. In more detail, they are:

1. "Talent" Management: Focuses on the recruitment, development, and retention of research talent. The outcome is a skilled and innovative workforce.
2. Research Setup: Involves preparing and establishing the framework and environment for conducting research. The outcome is an operational and helpful setting for research activities.
3. Interoperability (of process, tools, documents): Ensures that different systems and organisations can work together efficiently. The outcome is seamless integration and communication across data and platforms.
4. Reputation Management: Manages the perception and reputation of the researcher. The outcome is enhanced credibility and authority in the field.
5. Research Management: Oversees the planning, execution, and tracking of research projects. The outcome is efficient and effective research progression.
6. Data Management: Involves organizing, storing, and maintaining research data. The outcome is reliable and accessible data for analysis and decision-making.
7. Toolchain Management: It is related to the selection and integration of a suite of tools for the

- research process. The outcome is an optimised and effective toolset for research tasks.
8. Data Sourcing: Pertains to the acquisition of data necessary for research. The outcome is a robust dataset for research analysis and insights.
 9. Algorithms / ML Development: Involves creating algorithms and machine learning models for research purposes. The outcome is advanced analytical capabilities and insights.
 10. Reporting and Dissemination: Focuses on communicating research findings and information. The outcome is the widespread distribution of knowledge and results.
 11. Accounting / Reporting Management: Manages financial aspects and reporting requirements. The outcome is financial accountability and compliance.
 12. Best Practices Wiki Management: Involves creating and maintaining a repository of best practices. The outcome is a centralized knowledge base for optimal research methods.
 13. IT Integration & Connectors (e.g. API, interfaces): it deals with the technical aspects of integrating various IT systems. The outcome is interconnected and interoperable IT systems.
 14. IT / SW / HW Development: Involves the development of software and hardware. The outcome is tailored IT solutions to support research activities.
 15. Open Standards: Promotes the use of Open Standards. The outcome is the facilitation of collaboration and compatibility within the research community.
 16. Services/Resources Provisioning: Involves the allocation and distribution of services and resources required for research activities. The outcome is the timely and efficient provision of necessary resources.
 17. Services/Resources Procurement: Deals with the acquisition of services and resources needed for research. The outcome is the secured availability of required resources.
 18. Training and Upskilling: Focuses on the development and enhancement of skills for researchers. The outcome is a more capable and proficient research team.
 19. Funding Management: Manages the financial resources required to support research activities. The outcome is well-funded research projects with adequate resources for execution.
 20. Research Conclusion: Encompasses the finalization and wrap-up of research projects. The outcome is the completion of research with clear results and conclusions, as well as the storage of the outcomes of research projects.
 21. IT Core Services (IaaS, Storage, etc.): Provides fundamental IT infrastructure and storage solutions. The outcome is a robust and reliable IT backbone for research activities.

3. Transforming EOSC's value chain to envisage the future: the "to-be" system

Once the EOSC ecosystem has been analysed to find out the value propositions for researchers, the value chain is modified using the Platform Design methodology to produce a map of the "to be" value chain, i.e. how it WOULD look like (or how it would be desired that it looked like) if the insights obtained from the methodology were applied to improve the value propositions. The transformed Wardley Maps shows how the EOSC value chain can be reshaped to have more impact and greater efficiency to perform research activities: comparing the updated with the original Wardley Map shows that, in general, the effect of applying the Platform Design methodology is to move researchers' activities to greater standardisation or commoditisation (i.e. to the right of the map). This would render activities more uniform and recognisable, and more widely applicable; importantly, activities would ultimately become cheaper by increasing their user base. In summary, improving and "tidying up" the value chain

produces a more efficient and productive landscape. The main principles of such a transformation are:

1. Arenas⁵⁰ that provide general purpose value, commodity services, or activities not depending on the specific vertical content, should be moved to the product or commodity areas: it is better to procure them from the market and promote standards and interoperability, instead of investing in them.
2. Arenas which can become "white label" solutions, accruing intellectual property or competitive advantage, so that vertical niche players can use them and apply them to specific use cases, go in the product area.
3. High value, context specific value arenas, stay in the custom built. This means that their value resides in the capability of providing custom, tailor-made solutions for niche needs.
4. Everything that is a repeating function, should be turned into a standardised one, or offered through standard channels or interfaces (reducing transaction costs), so it should be crossing the line of commodity.
5. Standardization of shared services: for components common across multiple products, apply the "Standardization of Transactions" principle from Platform Thinking (Platform 3).
6. Focus on integration and collaboration: where there are overlaps, foster integration and collaboration between different product teams. This approach is in line with creating efficient socio-technical systems that emphasize flow and responsiveness. Provide the "meta-tools" other teams can use to contextualize the shared elements to their use cases.
7. Main user experience needs to be guided in the search for coherence. Personalisation can occur at the single service level. This typically stays in the custom built area.
8. Build trust and identity within the ecosystem: develop mechanisms for reputation and trust among the different components of the value chain, encouraging collaboration and quality assurance.

These principles allow to identify "transformative movements" on the value chain, which in turn lead to identify three different types of future "structures":

1. *Shared service platforms*: these provide enabling capabilities that all members of the ecosystem can consume, to reduce the inefficiencies and efforts in the ecosystem value production and also as a common way to guide and grant coherence;
2. *Operating System or Context services platform focus*: they provide enabling functions that are part of the competitive advantage of the ecosystem, and also aggregate "white label" solutions that can be further contextualized in the vertical, niche high specialization areas;
3. *High specialization services*: these services cluster all activities of high customization, like research, that account for unique value creation and knowledge advancements

Further examples of the three types, as main drivers for transformation, are the following:

1. Shared services platform(s) focus

- Standardize shared services and processes: Focus on components that are common across multiple products, apply the "Standardization of Transactions" principle from Platform Thinking

⁵⁰ An "arena", in Platform Design terminology, designates a sub-system where entities interact with each other to achieve their goals. Each relevant arena of the ecosystem can be analysed to determine the tasks involved in the interactions, so that the roles played by the different actors can be identified.

(Platform Play #3). Standardize these shared services to improve efficiency and interoperability. Examples include IT/Cloud services, interface layers among different groups, and technical and legal support (website, repositories, data protection, privacy and compliance, licensing, etc.).

- Foster integration and collaboration: Where there are overlaps, promote integration and collaboration between different teams. This approach is in line with creating efficient socio-technical systems that emphasize flow and responsiveness. Provide the "meta-tools" other teams can use to contextualize the shared elements to their use cases. Examples include business and market analysis, user experience (UX), interoperability with industry standards and common interfaces.
- Treat data as a shared asset: Centralize data management as a foundational infrastructure, ensuring consistency and accessibility across all products.
- Give priority to security and privacy: Establish robust security and privacy measures as non-negotiable aspects of the shared infrastructure.
- Develop and maintain trust in the ecosystem: Build mechanisms for reputation and trust, essential for quality assurance and collaboration within the product area.
- Outsourcing or partnership management for commodity services: For components that are commodities, consider outsourcing or partnerships to focus resources on product development.

2. Operating system or context services

Empower with meta-Tools for Innovation and Customization: Provide tools that enable teams to innovate and customize shared elements, fostering a culture of adaptation at the product level.

- Leverage crowdsourcing for expertise and innovation: Create a shared layer for collecting expertise or labor for tasks like training and verification of algorithms and machine-learning (ML) models, or software core components.
- Guide Main UX for coherence while allowing personalization: Ensure a coherent user experience across custom-built solutions, with personalization tailored to individual customer needs.
- Hard and complex developments and tech processes, where the main experience can be standardized and guided, but the final output will depend on the context of application.
- Capability or talent pools, where a group of experts can be developing a common design system, a common set of practices and standards or guides, and some expertise is needed at contextualized level to apply the best practices (e.g. training of an algo, UX and service design)

3. High specialization services: custom built area of the Wardley Map

Focus on core competencies and unique value propositions: Concentrate on developing in-house capabilities that represent the unique value and competitive advantage of custom-built solutions. Elements that are critical to your competitive advantage should be kept in-house and refined, akin to embedding complex processes in SaaS (Platform Play #4).

- Spot expertise-intensive services: Highlight and develop services that require deep expertise, such as advanced ML model training, as part of the high-value custom solutions.
- Focus on User Experience and Efficiency: For components that directly impact the user experience, prioritize personalization and efficiency, as suggested in the "Personalization of Experience for Users" platform play (#1 and #2).

When these principles are applied, the result is the TO-BE map that represents the target value chain, i.e. what the EOSC strategy should be to achieve an efficient ecosystem (see Figure 2).

The following describes all the arenas/value propositions in the transformed (or evolved) value chain. Not all arenas have been moved from their AS-IS position: in the figure, those that changed place in the value chain are indicated by an orange colour, while those that remained in the same position are indicated in green.

1. Research & management (not moved): Central to orchestrating (i.e. coordinating) research efforts and managing output. It is the main custom-built value generated and managed by research bodies. This arena remains in the custom-built area due to its critical, context-specific role that cannot be standardized.
2. Talent management (i.e. researchers) (moved towards commodity): Involves attracting and nurturing talent, according to reputation, to the resources needed or available, to the capacity offered by/for the research body or research aggregator. This arena should be moved closer to the commodity area, indicating more standardization is needed in talent management practices across the research industry.

Figure 2: TO-BE map

3. Reputation management (moved towards product): Manages the perception of the quality and output of research performed by a researcher.
4. Best Practices wiki management (moved towards commodity): a repository of standard operating procedures and insights. The displacement towards commodity indicates its evolution into a repeatable and standard resource

5. Training and upskilling (moved towards commodity): Enhances skills and knowledge of the workforce needed to use research resources at their best. This arena has been moved towards commodity, showing that training content needs to become more standardized and widespread.
6. Data sourcing (moved towards product): The process of acquiring data/datasets for research. The shift reflects the fact that data sourcing is still dependent on context and is therefore (and will probably have to remain) a highly specialized function.
7. Algorithms / ML development (moved towards product): Develops bespoke algorithms and machine learning models. *Orange*: Moves into a serving specialized function in the ecosystem to provide high-skill support to research. It is not a commodity because of its high value and specialized nature.
8. “Toolchain” management (moved towards product): Selection and maintenance of a suite of tools to facilitate research. The displacement reflects that toolchains can be standardized and provided to niche players.
9. IT / SW / HW development (moved towards commodity): Specialised IT solutions including software and hardware are becoming more standardized, which justifies the move of this arena towards commodity/utility.
10. IT integration & connectors (e.g. APIs, interfaces) (moved towards commodity): This needs to become a commodity to ensure different systems work seamlessly together in a standardised way.
11. Services/resources provisioning (moved towards product): The allocation and distribution of resources (provisioning) is still specialized, but the process can be packaged based on best practices.
12. Research setup (moved towards commodity): The activities carried out in preparation of a research project (or activity) should be standardised, therefore becoming a commodity.
13. Reporting and dissemination of research results (not moved): The reporting or dissemination of the results obtained in research should remain as in the AS-IS value chain by following best practices already identified and practiced by researchers.
14. Accounting / Reporting management (not moved): Financial tracking and compliance often match common regulatory and organisational requirements. Changes could be made here to ensure the harmonisation of practices across the EU, but this would not change the position in the value chain.
15. Data management (moved towards commodity/utility): The basic principles of organising and storing research data (including its discovery, sharing and reuse) should become standardised.
16. Research conclusion (moved towards commodity): Finalising research and summarising findings. *Orange*: Despite the unique nature of concluding different types of research activities, this process can be standardized to foster the consolidation of insights, and the storage, and reuse of results.
17. Interoperability (Process, Tools, Documents) (moved towards commodity): Allows for seamless operation across systems. The shift reflects the need of standardising interoperability.
18. Open standards (not moved): Promotes uniform standards. Open standards are inherently meant to be commoditised and universally adopted, serving as foundation for various activities.
19. Services/Resources procurement (not moved): Acquires operational and research services and resources. This arena stays closer to commodity, suggesting that procurement is a more

- standardized function that can be handled through general market solutions. EU-wide harmonisation and flexible processes can make it more standardized and, hence a commodity.
20. Funding management (moved towards commodity): Oversees financial resources for research. implying that funding mechanisms need to be increasingly standardized and could be managed as a routine function with established best practices.
 21. IT core services (IaaS, storage, etc.) (not moved): Provides essential IT infrastructure services, maintained as a commodity due to established utility models in the IT industry. Not moved, as these core services are already considered commodities within the IT industry, often provided through established utility models.

4. Platform Strategy Models (PSMs)

This section describes how EOSC can improve the interactions within the ecosystem. Following the mapping of the activities in the value chain, three different platform strategies were developed. This section presents here how these can be supported and enabled by EOSC, their impact on different actors, and their different value scopes. The PSMs show how EOSC can have a positive impact on the ecosystem, and how it can become an attractor for all research activities and services. To be sure, other PSMs are also possible, but the three summarised here involve activities considered to be of particular importance and interest for EOSC stakeholders.

Platform Strategy Model 1: Researcher support and Open Science promotion

Figure 3: Platform Strategy Model 1. Click on the image to access a full-size version (online).

In this strategy model, the primary goal of the platform is to aid researchers in their research activities. More specifically, it aims to empower researchers by enhancing their reputation, helping them to increase their productivity, and facilitating their access to digital (FAIR) resources. The platform should be designed to promote Open Science by integrating training, reputation management, data discovery and sharing, and enable (and facilitate) collaboration. The scope of this PSM can be summarised with

the sentence “It’s all about the content”: the focus here is on datasets, performing research, research outcomes, and dissemination and publication of results.

Platform Strategy Model 2: Empowering Smaller Research Centers

Figure 4: Platform Strategy Model 2. Click on the image to access a full-size version (online).

PSM 2 focuses on the services and how they are exchanged in the EOSC ecosystem by “elevating” smaller research entities to the level of larger institutions by standardising operations, providing robust infrastructures, and integrating advanced tools and methodologies. This model aims to create a competitive and collaborative research environment that contributes significantly to global knowledge advancement. The scope of this PSM can be summarised with the sentence “It’s all about the container”: the focus is on services, datasets management, AI/HPC, and monitoring.

Platform Strategy Model 3: Federated Coordination of EOSC

PSM 3 focuses on the governance aspects of EOSC as a federation of nodes, enhancing the role and efficiency of national RIs (and other entities at national level) within the EOSC framework as promoters of high-quality Open Science, and facilitators of collaborations within the EU and beyond.

As the main governance solution for the federated nodes in EOSC, this strategy can be considered as the “glue” that connects all the active bodies in the ecosystem. It emphasises the importance of harmonised standards and practices, the efficient use of funding, and the development of shared digital resources. It also highlights the importance of coordinating the federated aspects of EOSC and the adaptive development of new functions, assets, and capabilities.

In order to provide a value proposition that incentivises entities to participate in EOSC, the “new patterns of research funding” would have to be linked to the governance. For this scenario, PSM 3 presents how EOSC could steer the development of the Federation by distributing funding, using data on relevance and impact as evaluation criteria. This would enable EOSC to extract the full value of

project results. The scope of this PSM can be summarised with “It’s all about governance, coordination, and funding”.

Figure 5: Platform Strategy Model 3. Click on the image to access a full-size version (online).

5. Supporting key entities to achieve sustainability

This section consolidates the insights from the preceding analysis to focus on how EOSC can provide a space to support key entities to achieve sustainability. In addition, where possible, we have highlighted how EOSC itself can also become sustainable beyond the current funding period, relying on small “rates” taken from the overall value orchestrated in the ecosystem. The activities in the to-be value chain are grouped according to the maturity level they are expected to achieve in the future. The lists are to be considered as guiding examples, and are not exhaustive nor prescriptive.

Shared Services (blue rectangles): services that are fundamental and support the ecosystem as a whole. They are enabling functions that EOSC should provide to generate opportunities in the entire ecosystem. Most of these functions should be provided “free to use” to the consumers of the services (for instance, funded or prepaid by EOSC or by the EU Commission), or offered in pay per use but with a very low margin, essentially at the basic running cost of the service:

- Funding Management
- Research Setup
- Research Conclusion
- Reporting, Dissemination
- Accounting / Reporting Management
- Data Management
- Interoperability (Process, Tools, Documents)
- IT / SW / HW development

- Toolchain management
- IT Integration & Connectors (e.g. API, interfaces)
- Services / Resources Procurement
- IT Core services (AAI, Storage, etc.)
- Open Standards
- FAIR

Context. Services

Context Services (yellow rectangles): services that are standardized and can be offered by different providers. These are high expertise services that can be developed as general purpose, white label solutions that other entities can use, extend, or integrate. They can be understood as a kind of operating system for the orchestration of the value generation or exchange among the key entities. They include:

- Best Practices Wiki management
- Training and Upskilling
- Algorithms / ML development
- Data Sourcing
- Services / Resources Provisioning
- Reputation Management
- Talent Management (i.e. researchers)

High Specialization Services

High Specialization Services (green rectangle): Highly specialized services developed for specific or unique requirements. They are typically in the Custom Built area of the value chain map, to signify that the value they express resides in the capability to apply these services to a new custom case and generate unique or advanced content. They include:

- Research activities execution
- Management of the research activities
- Peer reviewing of results, verification of previous studies, etc.

Some common patterns associated to each of the three types of artefacts can be identified:

- *Shared services can be developed by EOSC directly or by partners.* Typically, it is the main legal entity that assures the budget to cover these services. Wherever possible, they should also have a pay per use component, proportional to the real use workload requested by clients.
- *Context services can be developed by external partners, under the supervision of the EOSC “coherence layer”.* The services developed can be pay-per-use, or be also the result of EU funding schemes, or provided by RPOs, Service providers, universities, research institutes, to scale the adoption of successful research.
- *High specialization services, whose main entities are the key roles around the research projects, can be accounted similarly to the current schemes of research funding.* They can be sustained through RFO and EU calls: EOSC does not directly intervene here, but can drive the policies and best practices to foster Open Science and improve EU’s research competitiveness.

Associating use cases with the three types of organizational artifacts

A more detailed list of activities can be associated to the three types of organizational artifacts:

Shared Services:

- Apply for funding.
- Being supported in the research activity, from domain/context experts
- Compare and approve research projects, distribute funds.
- Consume thematic services to refine, improve, contextualize datasets.
- Find a one-stop shop for datasets, including traceability and quality assurance of the data
- Monetize (underutilized fixed) assets (hence improve visibility of their assets and streamline options for booking, leasing, and/or access)
- Negotiate better deals with providers, thanks to the aggregation of demand
- Sell Cloud services
- Sell custom, domain contextualized services
- Selling and Accounting, for cross borders "clients"
- Setup research activities, and coordinate research projects
- Streamline choice, procurement, access to horizontal services, such as PIDs, AAls...
- Turn data into interoperable assets, and trace the reuse
- Work with the research teams to identify the emerging needs for thematic, horizontal, infrastructure services and asset consumption

Context Services:

- Apply for funding.
- Being supported in the research activity, from domain/context experts
- Compare and approve research projects, distribute funds.
- Consume thematic services to refine, improve, contextualize datasets.
- Find a one-stop shop for datasets, including traceability and quality assurance of the data
- Negotiate better deals with providers, thanks to the aggregation of demand
- Sell custom, domain contextualized services
- Selling and Accounting, for cross borders "clients"
- Streamline choice, procurement, access to horizontal services, such as PIDs, AAls...
- Turn data into interoperable assets, and trace the reuse
- Work with the research teams to identify the emerging needs for thematic, horizontal, infrastructure services and asset consumption

High Specialization Services:

- Being supported in the research activity, from domain/context experts
- Consume thematic services to refine, improve, contextualize datasets.
- Find a one-stop shop for datasets, including traceability and quality assurance of the data
- Sell Cloud services
- Sell custom, domain contextualized services
- Setup research activities, and coordinate research projects
- Turn data into interoperable assets, and trace the reuse
- Work with the research teams to identify the emerging needs for thematic, horizontal,

infrastructure services and asset consumption

6. List of relevant business models for the EOSC ecosystem scenarios

The previous sections presented the evaluation of the current state of the EOSC ecosystem, provided three examples of where an EOSC platform strategy can be deployed (i.e. the three PSMs), and grouped activities performed in the platform illustrating the value propositions. This section now consolidates potential business models that entities can use to benefit from the deployment of EOSC and how EOSC can become sustainable by facilitating interactions and enabling services. The list of possible business models of relevance to EOSC includes:

1. Service Subscription: Customers pay a recurring fee for ongoing access to a product or service, monetized through monthly or annual subscription fees.
2. Expert Consulting: Professionals provide advice and problem-solving, monetized by charging clients an hourly rate, project fee, or retainer.
3. Cross-border marketplace: Selling goods and services across international borders online, with revenue from sales transactions, shipping, and handling charges.
4. Service Fee: Charging a fee for each service rendered, which can be fixed or percentage-based, monetized through direct payments for services.
5. Volume Discounting: Offering reduced prices based on the quantity purchased, generating revenue through increased sales volume.
6. Group Buying: A model where buyers come together to buy in bulk for discounts, monetized through sales to groups and potentially service fees.
7. Project Management Services: Providing structured management services for projects, monetized through fixed price or size-based service fees.
8. Grant Administration: Overseeing grant funds in accordance with grant conditions, monetized by charging a management fee as a percentage or fixed charge.
9. Grant Funding: Providing financial support through grants, typically not directly monetized but may involve administrative fees.
10. Project Evaluation Services: Assessing project performance and outcomes, monetized through consulting fees on a project basis or subscription for ongoing evaluation.
11. Data as a Service (DaaS): Making data accessible over the internet, monetized through subscription fees, pay-per-use, or tiered access levels.
12. Pay-per-use: Customers only pay for the services or resources they use, encouraging flexible pricing based on actual consumption.
13. Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS): Providing virtualized computing resources, monetized through usage-based billing for compute, storage, and network resources.
14. Platform as a Service (PaaS): Offering a platform for application development, monetized through subscriptions or usage-based fees for access.
15. Funding Consultancy: Advising on funding opportunities, monetized through a percentage of funding secured, fixed consulting fees, or a retainer model.
16. Asset Leasing: Renting out assets for a specified time, monetized through leasing fees structured as monthly payments.
17. Asset Sharing Platforms: Enabling the sharing or renting of assets, monetized through transaction fees, subscriptions, or a percentage of each rental.
18. Open Data Licensing: Providing free access to data under terms that allow use and distribution,

- monetized through licensing fees for commercial use.
19. Data Sharing Agreements: Formal agreements for data sharing, monetized through one-time or recurring fees for access or membership models.
 20. Consulting Services: Offering expert advice to improve performance, monetized by charging on a per-hour, per-project, or retainer basis.
 21. Co-development: Collaboratively developing products or technologies, monetized through shared revenue models, upfront fees, or equity stakes.
 22. Cloud Service Subscription: Subscriptions for cloud-based services, with options for pay-per-user or tiered pricing models.
 23. Usage-based Billing: Charging based on the volume of service or product used, with tiered pricing for different usage levels.
 24. Custom Service Development: Developing tailored services, charged through project-based fees, hourly rates, or value-based pricing.
 25. Premium Service Subscriptions: Offering enhanced features for a higher subscription fee, providing access to exclusive or advanced features.

7. Combined result

In Table 1 below, all the information is merged. The final results presented in the table connect the key roles with the key use cases, the key business models, and the sustainability patterns (for the role and for EOOSC as well), and to evaluate if the business model is a new one (requiring proper implementation plan), or if it is an existing one. In the latter case, the last column indicates how EOOSC can improve the value exchanged in that interaction

D5.2 – Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work

Table 1 - Business models for activities by actors in the EOSC ecosystem

Impacted Entities	Use Case	Type of use case	Applicable Business Models	Contribution to the Sustainability for EOSC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer of Thematic Services ● Service Provisioning Units ● Aggregators of Research Entities ● Thematic Service Providers 	<p>Support of research activities from domain or context experts</p>	<p>Shared Services / Context. Services</p>	<p>Service Subscription, Expert Consulting, Consulting services</p>	<p>Take rate/fees on consulting fees, on subscriptions;</p> <p>Partner's onboarding fees for thematic service providers AND/OR Fee for posting/advertising services.</p> <p>EOSC can aggregate data about its members and share insights to Thematic Service Providers behind a fee (this also partly addresses the "Work with the research teams to identify the emerging needs for thematic, horizontal, infrastructure services and asset consumption" arena).</p> <p>Data monetisation ("pay per report") thanks to analysis and intelligence of FAIR data repositories.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer of Thematic Services ● Consumer of Horizontal Services ● Consumer of data ● Data producers ● Horizontal Service Providers ● Service Provisioning Units ● Aggregators of Research Entities ● Thematic Service Providers 	<p>Selling and Accounting, for cross borders 'clients'</p>	<p>Context. Services</p>	<p>Cross-border e-commerce, Service Fee, Subscription</p>	<p>Freemium (concierge fees)</p> <p>Advertising</p> <p>Participation to the tender (if/when available), success fee</p>

D5.2 – Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work

Impacted Entities	Use Case	Type of use case	Applicable Business Models	Contribution to the Sustainability for EO SC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumer of Thematic Services Consumer of Horizontal Services Consumer of data Data producers Horizontal Service Providers Aggregators of Research Entities Infrastructure Providers 	Negotiate better deals with providers, thanks to the aggregation of demand	Shared Services / Context. Services	Volume discounting, Group buying	<p>Take rate/fees, membership fees - Implication for growth: joining EO SC is tangibly more advantageous than continuing the operations outside of it</p> <p>Cost Savings at EU finance & control level</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Provisioning Units Aggregators of Research Entities 	Setup research activities, and coordinate research projects	Shared Services / High Specialization Services	Project management services, Grant administration	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aggregators of Research Entities Research Funding Organizations 	Compare and approve research projects, distribute funds.	Shared Services	Grant funding, Project evaluation services	Direct Funding from the EU: Cost Savings at EU finance & control level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumer of data Data producers Service Provisioning Units 	Find a one-stop shop for datasets, including	Shared Services / Context. Services	Data as a Service (DaaS), Subscription for access, Data Sharing Agreements	<p>Membership fees</p> <p>Pay per report / Pay per data</p>

D5.2 – Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work

Impacted Entities	Use Case	Type of use case	Applicable Business Models	Contribution to the Sustainability for EOSC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aggregators of Research Entities 	traceability and quality assurance of the data			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumer of data Horizontal Service Providers Service Provisioning Units Thematic Service Providers] 	Consume thematic services to refine, improve, contextualize datasets.	Shared Services / Context. Services	Service Subscription, Pay-per-use, Consulting Services, Premium Service Subscriptions	Take rate/fees, membership fees Advertising
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consumer of Horizontal Services Horizontal Service Providers Service Provisioning Units Aggregators of Research Entities 	Streamline choice, procurement, access to horizontal services, such as PIDs, AAls,...	Shared Services / Context. Services	Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS)	Take rate/fees, membership fees if they are provided by third parties. Volume discounts. Direct Funding from the EU
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service Provisioning Units Aggregators of Research Entities Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) 	Apply for funding	Shared Services	Grant application services, Funding consultancy	Direct Funding from the EU Cost savings at Finance and Control at EU level

D5.2 – Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work

Impacted Entities	Use Case	Type of use case	Applicable Business Models	Contribution to the Sustainability for EOSC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer of Thematic Services ● Consumer of Horizontal Services ● Service Provisioning Units ● Aggregators of Research Entities ● Infrastructure Providers 	<p>Monetize (underutilized fixed) assets (hence improve visibility of their assets and streamline options for booking, leasing, and/or access)</p>	<p>Shared Services</p>	<p>Asset leasing, Asset sharing platforms</p>	<p>Take rate/fees, membership fees (e.g. recurrent yearly subscription), Consulting Services (EOSC Concierge Services?)</p> <p>Fixed fees on commoditised/productised products</p> <p>Fee/subscription to list offerings to procure custom-built products</p> <p>—</p> <p>Lab/asset on demand: pay per use / booking fee Fee to publish the asset (the two parties will arrange the terms of agreement outside of EOSC)</p> <p>Fee for matchmaking (in case EOSC mediates the transactions, provides templates and standards for the agreements)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer of Thematic Services ● Consumer of data ● Service Provisioning Units ● Thematic Service Providers 	<p>Turn data into interoperable assets, and trace the reuse</p>	<p>Shared Services / Context. Services</p>	<p>Open data licensing, Data sharing agreements</p>	<p>Take rate/fees, membership fees</p> <p>Advertising</p> <p>Consulting Services (EOSC Concierge Services?)</p>

D5.2 – Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work

Impacted Entities	Use Case	Type of use case	Applicable Business Models	Contribution to the Sustainability for EOSC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer of Thematic Services ● Consumer of Horizontal Services ● Consumer of data ● Horizontal Service Providers ● Service Provisioning Units ● Aggregators of Research Entities ● Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) ● Infrastructure Providers 	<p>Work with research teams to identify emerging needs for thematic, horizontal, infrastructure services and asset consumption</p>	<p>Shared Services / Context. Services / High Specialization Services</p>	<p>Consulting services, Co-development</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer of Horizontal Services ● Horizontal Service Providers 	<p>Sell Cloud services</p>	<p>Shared Services / High Specialization Services</p>	<p>Cloud service subscription, Usage-based billing</p>	<p>Take rate/fees, membership fees, advertising (?)</p>

D5.2 – Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work

Impacted Entities	Use Case	Type of use case	Applicable Business Models	Contribution to the Sustainability for EOSC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consumer of Thematic Services ● Consumer of Horizontal Services ● Consumer of data ● Data producers ● Horizontal Service Providers ● Service Provisioning Units ● Aggregators of Research Entities ● Thematic Service Providers 	<p>Sell custom, domain contextualized services</p>	<p>Shared Services / Context. Services / High Specialization Services</p>	<p>Custom service development, Premium service subscriptions</p>	<p>Take rate/fees, membership fees, advertising</p>

8. Final recommendations

Based on the methodology employed and the analysis performed, a summary of the insights gained together with recommendations are presented below. The recommendations are formulated for the scenario in which the EOSC ecosystem is already financially and economically active, with all entities consuming or providing value. The business models already applied by supply and demand counterparts are consistent, and it is not expected that EOSC will introduce any innovations to them, since they are good enough to grant sustainability for the parties. While the single entities are responsible for their sustainability and financial profit and loss, and EOSC cannot fundamentally change that, it is necessary to devise scenarios for their activities carried out in relation to EOSC, so that they, and EOSC itself, can become self-sustained.

Under these provisions, the recommendations on the platform business models that can help EOSC and the actors in the ecosystem achieve sustainability can be formulated as follows:

1. EOSC can make a difference in the marketplace between service providers and consumers by
 - a. **simplifying procurement processes**, reducing the bureaucracy by pre-qualifying parties, standardizing services catalogues and the onboarding procedures. EOSC could introduce pre-commercial procurement to coordinate and help purchase resources, by implementing the suitable norms and tools provided by the EU Procurement Code, including Public Private Partnerships and Pre-Commercial Procurement, to deal with the high expectations and strong flexibility required in the research world;
 - b. **improving and guiding the comparison among similar offers and providers** to educate consumers of value in the choice of the solutions;
 - c. **helping providers to publish their offering in a joint catalogue**, to guide and simplify decision making by consumers, to improve the fitting between providers and consumers and thus increase matching opportunities. This will help increase the quality of the services, satisfaction levels, and positive results (also in terms of good use of financial resources) of the initiatives funded by the EU;
 - d. working at procurement across EU Member States, favouring the **creation of super-suppliers**, i.e. aggregate heterogeneous small providers, and promoting the assembly of complementing partners to provide more complex services and solutions to satisfy the increasing demand for articulated needs;
 - e. **promoting the discoverability of services and service providers** in the ecosystem.
2. It is fundamental to **work on incentives to attract stakeholders** and let them perceive clearly that interaction through the EOSC platform will be better (more convenient, faster, long-term value creation) than doing the same activities outside. Researchers and their aggregators or proxies, as main consumers of value, would be more attracted EOSC is able to provide direct value solutions to their main needs: primarily, improve their reputation based on objective data and data-driven measurement. **This could be implemented by introducing an “EOSC index”** to gradually be integrated with, or even replace, the *h*-index. This index could be connected to the reuse of datasets or publications. A set of relevant, actionable, and comprehensive metrics that EOSC can shape, standardise and “condense” into a final measurement could increase its influence and the rate of (voluntary) adoption by entities and researchers, and contribute to enable direct funding as a format beyond Horizon Europe (see 10).

3. Given the fragmentation and complexity of the services ecosystem, the impact of EOSC on sustainability of individual entities cannot be direct. This can be compensated by **focussing on providing “guidance, standardization and defragmentation”** to increase the transparency and effectiveness of investments and service exchanges. For example, EOSC requires the introduction of some sort of “Service Provider Aggregation” since, at the present time, the provider community is fragmented. Currently, this role is performed by four large aggregators (GÉANT, EGI, EUDAT and OpenAIRE) that serve as a confluence and support for individual operators that contain a vast amount of knowledge that is essential to EOSC. Without them, there is a risk that all EOSC related services cannot be effectively provided. EOSC should take an active role in supporting the aggregation of service providers.
4. **EOSC should work in the development of self-service and self-composable interfaces** to help consumers of value to become autonomous and capable of finding, configuring and procuring the services they need. To do this, EOSC’s role would be to standardize the interfaces, work at taxonomy level to help consumers and providers understand how to develop compatible and standard services already integrable in the service catalogue available to consumers.
5. EOSC can improve its sustainability by introducing the following revenue streams:
 - a. When it acts as mediator of transactional exchanges (i.e. every time the business models attached to the use cases from the family of pay per use, product or service purchase, time and material procurement, etc. are used, and where it can be established a “canonical unit”, or a standard measurement of value that can be priced for the goods and services sold, e.g. GigaBytes for storage units, requests per second for cloud-based services request rates...), **EOSC could apply a markup or a take rate on top of transactions.**
 - b. When EOSC or any of the partners provide subscription or paid access services that cannot be measured in terms of quantity or volume, **EOSC could ask for a small amount of the subscription fee** by acting as a license dispatcher, a community building service centre, a customer service centre, an educational facility, etc.
6. **EOSC can aggregate multiple, smaller entities, and act as a centralised procurement office**, negotiating volume discounts on behalf of smaller entities that would not have this negotiation power if isolated.
7. Thanks to the aggregation of all the exchanges and transactions, **EOSC can enable “higher order business models”**, for instance connected to data intelligence, reporting, data aggregation, data sharing mandates, exploiting the availability of larger volumes of information.
8. With such a central hub role in the ecosystem of services around Open Science, **EOSC should be given the authority and funding to decide how money is spent on Open Science-related projects.** The evaluation of research projects could be based on the reputation of researchers and on results obtained in previous research projects supported by a “reputation index” (i.e. the “EOSC index” of point 4 above), for instance by measuring the accuracy and the appreciation the datasets produced, evaluated by the scientific community.
9. Most of the elements mentioned above can be scaled across EOSC by **investing in the governance processes to connect all the key stakeholders** and guide the continuous standardization of interfaces, service blueprints, taxonomy, and incentives offered to the entities. This will empower EOSC to become a centre of data driven policy making efforts.
10. **Isolating the service “core” and “marketplace” layers can lead to problems, since both layers are intertwined.** Core/Basic functions are fundamental because the entire operational model

relies on those components and modules to be executed, but their marginality leans towards zero. Therefore, the platform strategy chosen by EOSC should cover their cost with other sustainability streams from transactional or learning sustainability models.⁵¹ If EOSC core includes only basic services, it will be difficult for it to achieve sustainability. If the EOSC platform is implemented as currently intended, there is the risk that there are too few single-value (i.e. bespoke or problem-specific) services, which would neither guarantee that the user-base reaches critical mass nor that EOSC as a whole achieves long-term sustainability. There seems to be some confusion and overlap between various EOSC elements, the platform elements are highly interconnected and, adding to or removing a functionality from the EOSC, could make a huge difference to users. This points at the need of introducing training for users about the use and functionality of EOSC.

11. If the current plans—with the improvements suggested by this analysis—are taken forward, **EOSC has all the elements to become a “super-platform” that coordinates and connects with other platforms (e.g. GÉANT) that would yield mutual benefits**. EOSC would benefit from gathering data about user behaviour (i.e. everyone signed up in the platform, irrespective of the role played in the ecosystem), to gain understanding—and eventually control—of what actually happens in the ecosystem. This could eventually lead to additional sources of revenue. The risk here is that it can take some time to make researchers’ rankings based on different platforms “portable”, since coordinating reputation (i.e. assessment) systems across countries or disciplines poses considerable difficulties. However, by coordinating a Europe-wide platform, EOSC would have access to important data flows that could be reused to provide better services, and be shared with other (national or international) platforms and third-parties, potentially monetising them. At the initial stage, the EOSC platform should relay, include and aggregate the existing service aggregators, and give them more chances to improve and scale across national borders. In a second stage, the platform can optimise resources and promote a “re-bundling” of the aggregators on better value-driven rules.

⁵¹ See e.g. John Hagel (2015), *The Power of Platforms*, Business Trends series, Deloitte University Press. <https://www2.deloitte.com/za/en/pages/strategy-operations/articles/the-power-of-platforms.html>.

Appendix 1, part 2: Planning the Sustainable Exploitation of Key Exploitable Results in EOSC-related Projects

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	45
1. Introduction	46
2. Scope of the document	47
3. How to read this document	48
4. SEP Methodology – Sustainable exploitation for HE EOSC-related projects	48
4.1. Application of the SEP methodology	49
4.2. Overall Analysis of Results	50
4.3. Project-specific considerations (examples)	53
4.4. Impact generated by the SEP application	56
4.5. Lessons Learned from the SEP application and next steps	57
5. Wardley Maps	57
5.1. Business Models against Wardley map position	59
5.2. Wardley Mapping application to KERs – Examples	63
5.3. SEP Integration with Wardley mapping routines –a step-by-step guided approach to the combined use of the methodologies	66
5.4. Lessons learned from the Wardley mapping application and next steps	67
6. Conclusions	67
7. References	67
Annex I: Sustainable Exploitation Planning Survey (version: 2.1)	69
Annex II: Guiding questions to map KERs onto the Wardley Maps	74
Annex III: Connecting MRL with the SEP Quadrants	75

Executive Summary

Planning the exploitation of key results is a requirement for projects under Horizon Europe. As emerged during the initial EOSC Focus HE Impact WG meetings (WP2), projects often leave this exercise to a late stage in the project lifetime; and they would benefit from support for this essential activity.

EOSC Focus Task 4.4 has endeavoured to take projects related to the development of EOSC through an exploratory journey of the potential for sustainable exploitation of their results, and has devised the Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology to support the management of the envisaged

exploitation process. The methodology evolved in time according to the feedback received during its pilot application with several HE INFRAEOSC projects stemming from HE Impact WG; it was further enhanced by the integration of the concepts delivered by EOSC Focus WP5 in the deliverable *D5.1 - EOSC Resourcing Models*, and through the discussions at the 2025 EOSC Winter School.

The SEP can become the basis for a strategic management approach that the EOSC-related project consortia apply to manage the exploitation of their results, during and after the project's end. It can also support projects in their reporting obligations to the EC, by creating a convincing narrative for the description of how their KERs can continue to be exploited after the project's funds run out.

The legacy of this experience will be taken on by the HE EOSC Gravity project, creating a continuum in the EOSC-A support action towards the HE INFRAEOSC projects in their KER-sustainability planning, towards impact

1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe Project Impact working group (HE Impact WG) was established in May 2023 within the scope of work of the EOSC Focus project, with the support of WP4 Task 4.4. The group held several meetings to collect and analyse Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the EOSC-related HE Projects, and discuss the projects' issues related to the sustainable exploitation of their results. A clear need emerged for the projects to obtain support in the early definition of "avenues" for the exploitation of their KERs, to ultimately sustain their trajectory towards an impactful project delivery.

T4.4 addressed this need by delivering the Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology presented in this report. The methodology aims to support the projects in planning how to maximise the potential of their products, to be taken up for a broader use and generate the desired impact after the project's lifetime. The methodology has the form of a questionnaire articulated in sections (input-process-output) to characterise the elements of the exploitation model for project KERs.

The methodology was inspired by the work carried out by WP4 team members in other EU projects on planning the sustainability of Research Infrastructures, ERICs, and Technological Core Facilities^{52, 53, 54, 55}. Building on those established methodologies for business modelling, T4.4 defined the SEP methodology to suit the needs of the EOSC-related projects. The methodology was conceived as a self-reflecting tool, with an educational approach, to support the projects in autonomously planning the exploitation of their KERs and help them fulfil their reporting obligations to the EC.

The questionnaire was presented to the projects, including discussion, during the "HE Impact session" at the first EOSC Winter School in January 2024. Following those conversations, the SEP was adapted to make it more suitable to the environment of EOSC-related projects. It was further transposed to the EU-Survey platform (Annex I) to allow for a more interactive tool and better user experience. The

⁵² Cornet et Nardello (2022), D1.5 "Policy Paper on the sustainability of the ENRIITC Network", The European Network of Research Infrastructures and Industry for Collaboration (ENRIITC), H2020 INFRAINNOV-02-2019, Grant Agreement Number: 871112

⁵³ Nardello, I. (2019) D4.4 Report and proposal for model sustainability business plans for ERICs - Horizon2020 - ERIC Forum Implementation project,

⁵⁴ Nardello, I. (2021): D6.2 'Business plan for an ecosystem of mature European Marine Biological Stations - H2020 project: Association of European Marine Biological Laboratories Expanded (ASSEMBLE Plus), Grant Agreement: 730984

⁵⁵ Nardello I. et al. (2017), "EMBRC-ERIC business plan"

survey results were analysed by the WP4 team and discussed with respondents, to facilitate their understanding of the results and of the methodology as a whole. The work produced by WP5 in their deliverable *D5.1 - Resourcing models*⁵⁶ was employed to enrich the SEP with a self-guided approach to position the project KERs in the “exploitation space” (represented in the so-called Wardley maps), which provides choices for potentially suitable business models that would then be fully outlined using the SEP methodology. In the future, the SEP survey could be automated to increase the efficiency of the analysis. It was not possible to implement this during EOSC Focus, due to budget constraints.

2. Scope of the document

Planning the exploitation of key results is a requirement for projects under Horizon Europe (Grant Agreement, article 16). This planning would maximise the potential of the KERs to be taken up and used in the future, thus having better chances of generating the desired impact after the project’s lifetime. The HE Impact WG meetings of 2024 brought to light that the projects often leave this exercise to a late stage in their lifetime; and: that the project would benefit from a measure of support for this essential activity.

In response to the emerging need for support by the HE projects, Task 4.4 has endeavoured to take the projects through an exploratory journey of their result’s exploitation potential and has created a methodology (SEP) to support the definition and implementation of the exploitation process. The exercise would underpin a strategic management approach that the project consortium may apply, to exploit their products, during and after the project’s end.

3. How to read this document

The document is composed of the following sections.

- Introduction to the SEP methodology	Chapter 4: - SEP Methodology – Sustainable Exploitation for the HE EOSC-related projects	Here, the reader is introduced to the proposed methodology.
- Pilot application of the SEP and analysis of the results	Chapters 4.1 and 4.2: - SEP application - Analysis of SEP results	Here, we describe the application of the SEP to a group of HE INFRAEOSC projects and draw some considerations from the overall analysis of the results as well as examples of project-specific analysis
- Enhancing the SEP with the use of Wardley Maps	Chapter 5: - Introduction to Wardley maps - The Four Quadrants approach - List of KER-exploitation models - Examples of Application	Here, the reader is introduced to the Wardley mapping technique, adapted to the HE INFRAEOSC project environment. This chapter also provides examples of applying the Wardley mapping to KERs, to help the reader become more practical about how to use the method.
- SEP Integration with Wardley mapping	Chapter 6: - Integration of SEP with Wardley	A step-by-step guide to the combined use of the proposed methodologies

⁵⁶ Rey Mazón, M., Dietrich, M., Garavelli, S., Picard, J., & Robertson, D. (2024). *EOSC Focus - D5.1 - EOSC Resourcing models*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931890>.

routines	maps	
- Conclusions	Chapter 7: - Conclusions	Lessons learned and considerations for the future
- Support to the use of the methodologies, tools and techniques proposed	Annexes: - I: Sustainable Exploitation Planning questionnaire (v. 2.1) - II: Guiding questions to map the KERs onto the Wardley Maps - III: Connecting MRL with the SEP Quadrants	Details of the methodologies proposed: - Guiding questions to enter the KERs into the Wardley space - Full SEP survey - Connecting MRL with the SEP Quadrants

4. SEP Methodology – Sustainable exploitation for HE EOSC-related projects

The SEP was initially developed as a questionnaire to help projects outline a business model for the exploitation of their results. By “business model” the process is referred to that is required to sustain the addition of value from the products generated by the project. The SEP questions were articulated into three main sections (input, process and output), to define the elements of the model (Fig. 1):

- **Input** – the resources that are available to exploit the results (during and after the project lifetime), in terms of competences and shareholder support;
- **Process** – the governance and the management structure and the production activities to run the planned exploitation; and:
- **Output** – the envisaged products of the exploitation process, in terms of both financially and non-financially evaluated items.

Fig. 1 - Flowchart diagram of the general Input-Process-Output model (from: *The Outline Business Model Template for ERICs*).

The questionnaire was presented and discussed during the EOSC Winter School 2024. The feedback comments gathered from the participants of the session on ‘Sustainability for Impact’, spread over the three days of the School, were taken into account to adapt the questionnaire.

4.1. Application of the SEP methodology

Once refined, the SEP was transposed to a survey platform, in order to allow for a more interactive tool and support the SEP-user experience. The new interface was piloted with the support of two projects: FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-Impact; then, it was distributed to the projects of the HE Impact WG for a voluntary testing exercise.

A number of five projects participated in the exercise, providing a population size of eight KERs (Table 1), to which the SEP was applied. The majority of the KERs were services (62,5%) but most of the other types of results mapped on the EOSC Macro-Roadmap⁵⁷ were also represented, including: Software (36,5%); Infrastructure (25%); and: Toolkits, Networks, Training and Reports, with one occurrence (12,5%, each).

The survey results were analysed by EOSC Focus (WP4) and discussed with the survey respondents, during the group’s online meeting of 10 June 2024.

Table 1 – Name of EOSC-related Horizon Europe projects, which applied the SEP questionnaire to some of their Key Exploitable Results, in June 2024, as an exercise of the HE Impact Working Group.

Project acronym	Name of the Key Exploitable Results (KER)	Type of result
AI4EOSC	AI4EOSC Platform	Service
FAIR-IMPACT	Component and services for increased legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability within and across disciplines	Report
FAIR-IMPACT	FAIR assessment of Software	Tool
FC4EOSC	FC4EOSC – MSCR	Software; Service; Tool
FC4EOSC	Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)	Software; Infrastructure; Toolkit; Service
FC4EOSC	FC4EOSC RDGraph	Software, Service
PaNOSC	PaNOSC Data Portal	Software; Infrastructure; Service
Skills4EOSC	Competence Centre and support network	Network; Training

A summary of the information submitted by projects to the SEP is provided in the following section, accompanied by cross-cutting analytical considerations, for each of the SEP questionnaire parts. Project-specific considerations are drawn after the presentation of the summary, in section 4.3.

⁵⁷ https://eosc.eu/eosc-macro-roadmap/?_mrm_catalogue=roadmap

4.2. Overall Analysis of Results

Input

The project consortia were asked to evaluate the adequacy of the skillset of their team to the envisaged exploitation process, during and after the project lifetime (Fig. 2). Most projects are adequately resourced in terms of skillsets, or even over-resourced, during the project lifetime; the need for additional competences to support the envisaged exploitation phase is highlighted in few cases, regarding legal (FAIR Impact, FC4EOSC, AI4EOSC) and project management skills; however, additional communication resources are a requirement for most projects.

Fig. 2 – Adequacy of the skillset of the exploitation team, as a percentage of the skillset levels during the project lifetime (current) Vs. the required levels after the project end.

Regarding the financial support for the exploitation phase (Table 2), most projects envisage further project funding from the European Union Research Framework programmes, and/or additional public funding at the national/regional or institutional level. In two cases (FAIR Impact, Skills4EOSC), the projects have been unable to identify the source of funding for a specific KER.

Table 2 – Funding sources for the exploitation phase

Name of the Key Exploitable Results (KER)	Shareholders/Funding Sources
FC4EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit	EC (HE-project funding); Own Institution (Institutional funding)
FAIR IMPACT Component and services for increased legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability within and across disciplines	EC (HE-project funding); Additional public funding: national/regional
FAIR IMPACT FAIR assessment Software	EC (HE-project funding)
FC4EOSC MSCR	No response
PaNOSC Data Portal	EC (HE-project funding); Additional public funding: national/regional
FC4EOSC RDGraph	Additional public funding: national/regional
Skills4EOSC Competence Centre and support network	No response

Process

The project teams were asked to evaluate various aspects of the management of the exploitation phase, including the governance of the process ('who owns the exploitation plan, who will be making decisions?'), HR roles and availability; they could also choose the activities that the exploitation team would most likely perform from a pre-defined list, which include project management, technical development, IPR/legal activities, and others. The SEP further invites the projects to reflect on the main challenges envisaged and to formulate the Key Performance Indicators, according to the SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound)⁵⁸ for monitoring the exploitation process. The results obtained are shown in the following sections.

Governance

In some cases (FC4EOSC, CAT; Skills4EOSC), a clear governance structure, different with respect to that of the project governance, was envisaged; in most cases, however, the question may have been not fully understood, and the projects provided a description of the current (project-based) governance. In some cases, the projects indicated that this would be defined at a later stage. The results are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 – Description of the envisaged KER exploitation process

Skills4EOSC – Competence Centre and support network	During project lifetime, it's the Skills4EOSC Technical Board and Competence Centres representatives. Eventually, a lightweight mechanism was conceived, involving an assembly made of a couple of representatives from each Competence Centre.
FAIR-Impact – Component and services for increased legal, organisational, semantic, and technical interoperability within and across disciplines	Task lead, WP manager, Project Coordinator, Project Coordination Office
PaNOSC Data Portal	Andy (ESRF) has the leadership having the vision of the data portal, Max and Fredrik (ESS) have the ownership of the federated infrastructure, which includes the data portal, the search, and the scoring service. Max (ESS), as project leader of the SciCat collaboration, owns the search API interface between PaNOSC and the SciCat data catalogue. The iCAT project owns the implementation of the equivalent service for iCAT collaboration. Each RI owns the access to and the curation of their data.
AI4EOSC Platform	Currently it is the project PMB, to be defined in the agreement document of the platform maintenance
FC4EOSC – MSCR	CSC
FC4EOSC – Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT)	Until project completion, project governance. An operationalisation project with start-up governance will be required after completion to transition to permanent staff and structures.

The lack of a governance structure poses a serious threat to the sustainability of any process. An early definition of this aspect is essential to set the team's expectations and avoid delays at the onset of the exploitation phase.

⁵⁸ Doran, G. T. (1981). *There's a S.M.A.R.T. way to write management's goals and objectives* (PDF). *Management Review*. 70 (11): 35-36.

HR Availability and Roles

The availability of Human Resources was referred to rely almost exclusively on staff already part of the organisation, and mostly on a part-time basis. This may be a good choice in terms of sustainability, because internal personnel are already on-boarded and salaried, independently of the project. Only in one case, the exploitation process would utilise external service providers. The roles of the team components, however, are rarely fully defined (only one occurrence in eight examples) at this stage.

Activities

The exploitation of a KER will entail different activities, which may include project management, legal/IPR support, engagement/marketing/business development, technical development, communication/dissemination (Fig.3). The projects have expressed a varied relevance of these activities for the exploitation of each KER, highlighting that it is as a stand-alone process suited to the specificity of each KER. Only engagement/marketing/business development is recurrently a very relevant activity for the exploitation phase.

Challenges

The projects were invited to freely convey their concerns regarding the exploitation process. The question was particularly appreciated. The challenges indicated were related to different aspects of the process, including the difficulties of engaging relevant stakeholders and donors, the quality/functionality of the product, the labour-intensive relations with the users/customers, and the uncertainty of the EOSC governance.

Fig. 3 – Relevance of activity types to be performed during the exploitation phase, on a scale 1-5 (where 1 is the minimum and 5 is the maximum)

KPIs

The SEP nudged the projects to describe their own Key Performance Indicators for monitoring the exploitation process. The suggestion was to formulate those indicators based on the SMART-KPI criteria (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound). The question was not understood, however, and the projects could not address it appropriately. During the restitution workshop on 10th June 2024 in the framework of the HE Impact WG activities, the EOSC Focus project committed to improve the administration of this question.

Output

NON-Financially Evaluated output

The most recurring **non-financially evaluated output** items (table 4), chosen from a list of options, were: Free Access to Data/Service/Facility (75%); Dissemination activities like publications and workshops were also rather frequently mentioned (37,5% each); marketing and user strategies were only mentioned in one occurrence.

*Table 4 – Recurrence of NON-Financially Evaluated Output products, in the sampled KERs (n=8).
The items are ranked in a cardinal order from the most to the least recurrent. Per each item, the number and frequency of occurrences is also indicated.*

NON-Financially Evaluated output products	
•	Free Access to Data/Service/Facility – 6 occurrences (75%)
•	Publications – 3 occurrences (37.5%)
•	Workshops – 3 occurrences (37.5%)
•	User/Marketing Strategy – 1 occurrence (12.5%)
•	Other (enter your answer below) – 1 occurrence (12.5%)

Financially Evaluated Output

The most recurring financially evaluated output product, chosen from a list of options (Table 5), was Training (66.67%); Education and Consultancy were also represented options, in half of the population of the KERs; Paid Access to Data/Service/Facility and Contract research were options in 16.67% of the cases (1 occurrence).

*Table 5 – Recurrence of Financially Evaluated Output products, in the sampled KERs (n=8).
The items are ranked from the most to the least recurrent. Per each item, the number and frequency of the occurrences is also indicated.*

Financially Evaluated output products	
1.	Training – 4 occurrences (66.67%)
2.	Consultancy – 3 occurrences (50%)
3.	Education – 3 occurrences (50%)
4.	Other (enter your answer below) – 3 occurrences (50%)
5.	Paid Access to Data/Service/Facility – 1 occurrence (16.67%)
6.	Contract research – 1 occurrence (16.67%)

4.3. Project-specific considerations (examples)

The data shown above should be analysed by the projects after becoming familiar with the principles of the SEP methodology. To this end, we provide an example of the analytical process for three

projects, by organising the received information into tables (Tables 6, 7, 8). These tables represent the exploitation model across the three typical phases (input, process, output) of the transformation of the resources into value. In each table, the cells represent key elements of the model and are coloured according to their level of refinement: green for fully resolved details; orange for partially defined details; and red for elements undefined. A description of the analytical considerations is summarised below each table, with recommendations for potential areas of improvement.

It must be noted that one extra column (Destination) was added, *ex post*, by the SEP authors, as a result of the discussions on KER sustainability during the EOOSC Winter School 2025. The identification of potential destinations (i.e. potential adopters) adds depth to the model and allows for a more effective envisioning of the exploitation pathways for each KER. The choices would require a validation from the project consortia, which we could not perform at this late stage of the EOOSC Focus project.

Table 6 – AI4EOOSC Platform – Exploitation model, represented along the three columns: input, process, output. The cells in the table represent key elements of the model and are coloured according to their level of refinement, as emerged from the application of the SEP methodology to the KER by the project. Largely and credibly resolved details are in green; orange for partially defined details; and red for undefined elements.

Project acronym: AI4EOOSC			
KER name: AI4EOOSC Platform			
Type of result: Service			
INPUT	PROCESS	OUTPUT	Destination
WorkingTeam: team established but capacity needed in business development and communication	Governance post project not identified	\$ Free Access to Data/Service/Facility; Publications; User/Marketing Strategy; Workshops	<input type="checkbox"/> EOOSC EU Node <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EOOSC Nodes <input type="checkbox"/> Handbook <input type="checkbox"/> Guidelines
Shareholders: Public money identified: EU -project funding)	Activities cover the proposed range and tech development is particularly relevant. For that, roles and responsibilities in the internal working team are defined as well as their availability.	\$: Paid Access to Data/Service/Facility; Contract research; Training; Consultancy; Education.	<input type="checkbox"/> EOOSC-A <input type="checkbox"/> MAR
Private investment: not considered			<input type="checkbox"/> External users
Overall considerations and recommendations			
<p>The AI4EOOSC Platform is envisaged to be exploited as a service within the EOOSC Federation. In terms of resources, the working team is established within the consortium and can work from their home institutions, on a part time basis; only a limited additional capacity will be needed for communication and marketing. Financial resources are expected from EU Project funds or Institutional funds. Private investment may not be required to exploit this product, but further exploitation pathways may be scoped through market research, and pursued, if suitable, or in case the expectation of further public funding is low. Economic returns are expected from Access to Data/Service/Facility consultancy, education and training. Non-economic products, which may increase the visibility and leadership of the project consortium, are to be found in the knowledge dissemination areas of free access to the products, publications and workshops. A critical point in the presented plan is the lack of a potential governance scheme. An early definition of this aspect may avoid conflicts and delays, and ultimately facilitate the exploitation process.</p>			

Table 7 – Skills4EOOSC Competence Centre Network – see Table 6 caption for details

Project acronym: Skills4EOOSC
KER name: Competence Centre Network
Type of result: Network, Training

INPUT	PROCESS	OUTPUT	Destination
WorkingTeam: A diverse team is established without additional skillsets required	A credible light post-project governance is identified	\$ Free Access to Data/Service/Facility; Publications; Workshops	<input type="checkbox"/> EOSC EU Node <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National/Thematic Nodes <input type="checkbox"/> Handbook <input type="checkbox"/> Guidelines <input type="checkbox"/> EOSC-A <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MAR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External users
Shareholders: Public money is the pillar, mainly from National/regional funds	Roles and responsibilities in the working team are defined but uncertainty related to the maintenance of the data infrastructure and to data curation	\$: Paid Access to; Training; Consultancy; Education.	<input type="checkbox"/> EOSC EU Node <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National/Thematic Nodes <input type="checkbox"/> Handbook <input type="checkbox"/> Guidelines <input type="checkbox"/> EOSC-A <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> MAR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External users
Private investment: not considered			

Overall considerations and recommendations

The Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network is envisaged to be exploited as a network of educational resources and training service providers within the EOSC Federation. In terms of resources, the working team is established within the consortium, without additional skillsets required. Financial resources are expected from national/regional and institutional public funds. A credible light post-project governance is identified, involving an assembly made of a couple of representatives from each Competence Centre. Economic returns are expected from Access to Data/Service/Facility consultancy, education and training. Non-economic products, which may increase the visibility and leadership of the project consortium, are to be found in the free-access to Data/Service/Facility, publications; workshops. The case for this network to exist is made, but commitment to the maintenance of the data infrastructure still needs to be defined, jeopardising the credibility of this plan. A consultation with the relevant stakeholders aimed at the subscription of a Memorandum of Understanding may address this issue.

Tab. 8 – PaNOSC Data Portal – see Table 6 caption for details

Project acronym: PaNOSC			
KER name: PaNOSC Data Portal			
Type of result: Software; Infrastructure; Service			
INPUT	PROCESS	OUTPUT	Destination
WorkingTeam: team established but capacity needed in business development and communication	The post-project governance of this distributed system is not identified, but in the short term a parallel project is implementing the exploitation plan.	\$ Free Access to Data/Service/Facility; Publications; User/Marketing Strategy; Workshops	<input type="checkbox"/> EOSC EU Node <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National/Thematic Nodes <input type="checkbox"/> Handbook <input type="checkbox"/> Guidelines <input type="checkbox"/> EOSC-A <input type="checkbox"/> MAR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External users
Shareholders: Public money identified: National/regional funds;	Activities cover the proposed range. Roles and responsibilities in the working team are defined as well as their availability.	\$: Paid Access to Data/Service/Facility; Contract research; Training; Consultancy; Education.	<input type="checkbox"/> EOSC EU Node <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National/Thematic Nodes <input type="checkbox"/> Handbook <input type="checkbox"/> Guidelines <input type="checkbox"/> EOSC-A <input type="checkbox"/> MAR <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> External users
Private investment: not considered	Leadership on the maintenance and development of the technical components is clearly established.		
Overall considerations and recommendations			
The PaNOSC Data Portal is envisaged to be exploited partly as software, partly as infrastructure, and also as a service, within the EOSC Federation and possibly to outside users. In terms of resources, the working team is established within the consortium and can work from their home institutions, on a part time basis, without requirements for additional capacity. Financial resources are expected from public national/regional/institutional funds. Private investment may not be required to exploit this product but further exploitation pathways may be scoped through a marketing investigation,			

and pursued, if suitable, at a fuller development stage. The distributed ownership of the segments of this KER is clearly described, as it is the leadership in the product technological development. The process governance however is provided by a project, apparently lacking a longer time commitment, outside the EU project dimension. Also, some of the team capacity for the foreseen activity still needs to be hired or defined. Economic returns are expected from education and training. Non-economic products, which may increase the visibility and leadership of the project consortium, are to be found in the knowledge dissemination areas of free access to the data/service/facility. A critical point in the presented plan is the multiple nature of the KER description, which represents both a software, infrastructure and a service. The 'atomisation' of the KER into more uniform items may simplify the description of this plan and enhance the exploitation potential of the project's output.

4.4. Impact generated by the SEP application

The impact of the collaborative work produced by the HE Impact WG and the application of the SEP methodology became soon evident with the articulation of mature considerations regarding common KER sustainability issues, which the projects delivered at the 'EC/REA meeting with projects', in June 2024. The session on sustainability in that event allowed the projects to present and debate the dynamism of the EOSC-related policy environment and the uncertainties of the EOSC deployment, as major bottlenecks for the realisation of exploitation models for the project KERs, and to call for support mechanisms by the EOSC Partnership.

In response, the identification of destination areas for the project output and support measures, such as the roadmap for the EOSC Tripartite Governance to facilitate the uptake of the KERs, were discussed at the 2025 EOSC Winter School. As an outcome, a number of landing opportunities were defined, including the EOSC EU Node, the National/Thematic Nodes, the EOSC Federation Handbook, the EOSC-A, the EOSC Multi Annual Roadmap (MAR), and external users (including the commercial environment). These destinations for the project outputs will be added to the SEP methodology, as one step towards the assessment of the project impact within the EOSC Federation, as well as in the broader societal and economic spheres.

As further tangible evidence of progress towards impact, some projects have already started to implement their plans at the time of writing. For example, some consortia have submitted their candidacy to become thematic nodes of the EOSC Federation (PaNOSC, Blue Cloud, Escape). For some other projects, a line of conversation is open with EOSC-A to adopt their recommendations, methodologies and exchange of practices (FAIR Impact, EOSC Focus). One noteworthy example of pursuing a commercial exploitation pathway is RAISE, who reported their experience of engaging in an accelerator program and planning a commercial spin-off, during the WS 2025.

4.5. Lessons Learned from the SEP application and next steps

The projects were appreciative of the exercise endured by the application of the SEP and referred that it stimulated a deeper insight on modelling the process of exploitation of their KERs, allowing for self-reflection and improvement of the initial concepts of the KER exploitation plans, upon iterations.

A critical aspect that resulted from applying the SEP methodology is that its full benefit only emerges through an interpretation of the input by experts in strategic business-management. However, automatic completion of the questionnaire and analysis of responses, without the mediation by EOSC Focus or EOSC-A, would be desirable. This automatic processing of the SEP responses would return a critical analysis of the exploitation-process model, utilising a theoretical framework as a benchmark.

To remediate the missing automation of the analysis, not possible with the resources available in EOSC Focus, WP4 leveraged the activities conducted by WP5 described in deliverable D5.1⁵⁹. Using the conceptualisation of the business models for EOSC described in that deliverable has resulted in the strengthening of the SEP methodology and provided further insight and business modelling options to SEP users. The combined thinking of WP4 with WP5 led to maximise the initial work by both WP5 and WP4 and expand its scope. The next chapter (Chapter 5) of this document describes the work that WP4 conducted, with the support of the resources available in WP5, and how these may be integrated in the SEP methodology.

5. Wardley Maps

In January 2024, EOSC Focus WP4 leveraged the output of WP5 on business models and enhanced the SEP, by: i) guiding the projects in positioning their Key Exploitable Results, in an ideal exploitation space, through Wardley maps; and: ii) providing options for applicable business models, anchored in the EOSC environment, for the KER exploitation.

A Wardley Map is a strategic tool used to position components (the KER or their parts, in our case), in a value chain, and relate them to user needs. The technique is named after Simon Wardley, who created it in 2005. Its primary objective is to help visualise the strategic environment of an organisation in an intuitive, informative, and co-creative manner. Wardley identified the need for a method to link an organisation's value chain to market forces and the impacts of new technological trends, facilitating more informed strategic decisions based on the real context in which the organisation operates⁶⁰.

The Structure of a Wardley Map

Wardley maps offer a two-dimensional visualisation space that allows positioning KERs, needs, resources, technologies, assets, services, and activities in a Cartesian coordinate system (Box 1):

- The vertical (Y) axis (Value Perception Positioning), utilised for positioning a KER (or its components) within a value chain, which represents the user perception of KER's Value; and:
- The horizontal (X) axis (Evolutionary Stages), which describes the evolution of the level of maturity of the KER, during the exploitation process.

⁵⁹ Rey Mazón, M., Dietrich, M., Garavelli, S., Picard, J., & Robertson, D. (2024). EOSC Focus - D5.1 - EOSC Resourcing models. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931890>.

⁶⁰ More resources on Wardley Maps can be found on [Wikipedia](#), and on the free training [How to Wardley Map - IT Revolution](#). Some additional reference resources are: [Getting Started with Wardley's Doctrine Is Easier Than You Think; Tools](#)

The coordinate axes of Wardley maps

Vertical Axis - Value Perception Positioning
 The vertical axis represents the visibility of the value, as perceived by key users. Components that generate more value for consumers are placed towards the top of the map, while those that support the internal offerings are positioned towards the bottom. This helps distinguish activities more directly related to the needs of the value-consumers from those that satisfy internal process and operational needs, which, although essential, may not immediately be visible to the customer. For example, customer-oriented services or products would be positioned higher up the Y-axis, while back-end operations, capacity building, or internal processes would be placed lower.

Horizontal (X) Axis - Evolutionary/Maturity Stages
 The horizontal axis indicates the degree of maturity and commoditisation of the output produced (e.g. activities, technologies). Close to the axis' origin are innovative and highly customised elements, representing areas of new development and differentiation; moving towards the centre, the components (i.e. products and services) become more standardized and accessible through the market; farther from the axis origin, the components are fully commoditized, becoming industry standards or widely adopted without significant customisation. An emerging technology or a newly developed custom solution would be placed close to the origin, while well-established, commoditized services or products, like cloud-computing, would be on the far right.

Box 1 – Description of the axis of Wardley maps.

In the space defined by the two axes, Wardley maps identify four main quadrants (Fig.4), where each KER (or subcomponent) may be positioned, according to the specific perceived value and degree of maturity. A description of the general characteristics of the products that may be mapped in each quadrant is provided in Figure 4. By examining each quadrant in detail, we aim to comprehensively understand their specific objectives, key points of attention, types of services, and applicable business models. This structured approach will help guide the mapping of projects, results, and activities to their appropriate quadrants, ensuring strategic alignment and maximising value creation within EOSC.

Fig. 4 - The four main quadrants in Wardley maps. Each quadrant is an area in a Cartesian coordinate system defined by the perceived KER's value to users (vertical axis) Vs the KER's degree of maturity and commoditisation level (horizontal axis)

To facilitate the mapping, a set of questions (data not shown) are provided to guide the project and determine the most suitable quadrant for their KERs. The questions and the keywords associated with each quadrant provide a clear and straightforward method to categorise the KER effectively. Mapping the KERs against the quadrants will provide insights on the critical points of attention, relevant types

of services, and business models essential for achieving financial sustainability and maximising the impact potential of the KER.

Even if mapping items and actions in the Wardley maps can be difficult for inexperienced users, there exist many learning opportunities, mostly open source⁶¹. Some key resources are the “Doctrine mapping tables”, which explain where an item should be placed (especially in the horizontal axis)⁶², by using keywords, guiding questions and examples.

A limitation remains in the need to place on the map only the KER’s ‘atoms’, i.e. its basic components: the process of atomising each KER is not trivial and requires expert support.

5.1. Business Models against Wardley map position

In the dynamic landscape of EOSC, identifying sustainable business models is crucial for ensuring long-term viability and maximizing the impact of research projects. EOSC aims to provide an integrated environment where researchers, institutions, and stakeholders can collaborate, share data, and access a wide range of services. To support this vision, a robust set of business models is essential to facilitate interactions, enable services, and ensure financial sustainability.

This section provides suggestions on applicable business models that the exploitation teams may consider to utilise for the exploitation of their KERs. These models not only provide pathways to monetise services and resources but also enhance the ecosystem's overall value proposition by fostering collaboration, innovation, and resource efficiency.

The business model suggestions are different in each quadrant. The correct mapping of the KER/s in the Wardley space is crucial to obtain adequate suggestions on business model applicability. The tables below (Tables 9 - 12) describe the applicable business models for the different quadrants; they also provide indication on the associated market readiness levels (MLR)⁶³ and integrated life-cycle stages (further details can be found in Annex II).

Tab. 9 - List of business models and Market Readiness Levels applicable to KERs in Quadrant 1 of the Wardley maps.

WARDLEY Q 1	
Applicable BUSINESS MODELS	Applicable MARKET READINESS LEVELS
<p>Expert Consulting: This model is ideal for the top left quadrant as it leverages deep expertise and specialized knowledge, which is critical in environments characterized by high IP and expert advisory needs. Consultants can provide tailored advice and solutions, charging premium rates for their high-value services on an hourly rate, project fee, or retainer basis.</p>	<p>Applicable MRLs are limited to preliminary gathering of information, which may be of use for the research activity itself and may be “re-used” in the later stages (and quadrants), e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MRL 1 - Identification of Market Opportunity: Initial market research is conducted to identify potential markets and customer segments. • MRL 2 - Market and Customer Needs Understanding: Detailed understanding of market
<p>Project Management Services: Given the complex and bespoke nature of needs in this quadrant, project management services offer structured support for intricate projects, which can be monetized through fixed price or</p>	

⁶¹ <https://medium.com/wardleymaps/on-being-lost-2ef5f05eb1ec>

⁶² More resources are available here <https://learnwardleymapping.com/landscape/>

⁶³ Market Readiness Levels: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313063121_TRL_and_MRL_of_C-ITS_as_lessons_learned_from_the_Austrian_C-ITS_Corridor_ECo-AT/figures?lo=1 – Fig 10

size-based fees. This aligns well with the requirement for expert oversight and management in high-stakes environments.	<p>needs, customer pain points, and potential demand.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MRL 3 - Competitive Analysis: Analysis of the competitive landscape and identification of differentiators. <p>-----</p> <p>Relevant activities for Quadrant 1 are:</p> <p>i) Feasibility study: Focus: Assess the overall feasibility of the project, including technical, financial, and market aspects. Activities: Initial research, feasibility studies, risk assessment, and stakeholder analysis.</p> <p>ii) Technical Proof of Concept (PoC): Focus: Demonstrate the technical feasibility of the concept.</p> <p>Activities: Laboratory tests, initial prototyping, technical validation, and proof of concept.</p>
Project Evaluation Services: This model fits well where high uncertainty and IP are involved, allowing for a thorough assessment of project performance and outcomes. It can be monetized through consulting fees on a project basis or via a subscription for ongoing evaluation, ensuring high-value projects meet their strategic goals.	
Custom Service Development: This quadrant's core feature is developing tailored services to meet specific, high-value client needs. This model can be monetized through project-based fees, hourly rates, or value-based pricing, reflecting the services' bespoke nature and high intellectual content.	
Consulting Services: Similar to expert consulting, this model offers specialized advice to improve client performance and is suitable for high IP and high uncertainty environments. It's monetized by charging per hour, per project, or on a retainer basis, allowing flexibility and high-value alignment with client needs.	
Co-development: In cases where there is collaborative development of products or technologies, this model allows for sharing high IP content and expertise with clients or partners, monetized through shared revenue models, upfront fees, or equity stakes. This fits well in scenarios where innovative, bespoke solutions are created in partnership with clients.	
Pay-per-use: Customers only pay for the services or resources they use, encouraging flexible pricing based on actual consumption. Here, it's important not to bind to contracts and supply that are too constraining or long-term.	
Funding Consultancy: Advising on funding opportunities monetized through a percentage of funding secured, fixed consulting fees, or a retainer model.	

Tab. 10 - List of business models and Market Readiness Levels applicable to KERs in Quadrant 2 of the Wardley maps.

WARDLEY Q 2	
Applicable BUSINESS MODELS	Applicable MARKET READINESS LEVELS
Service Subscription: This model is suitable as customers pay a recurring fee for ongoing access to standardised services. It's ideal for products and services that benefit from regular use and can be standardised across a broad customer base.	<p>In this quadrant, most of the MRL results can be explored and achieved.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MRL 1 - Identification of Market Opportunity: Initial market research is conducted to identify potential markets and customer segments. ● MRL 2 - Market and Customer Needs Understanding: Detailed understanding of market needs, customer pain points, and potential demand.
Volume Discounting: Offering reduced prices based on the quantity purchased aligns with this quadrant's high-volume, low-margin nature. It incentivizes bulk purchases and helps in capturing larger segments of the market.	
Service Fee: Charging a fixed or percentage-based fee for each standardised service rendered fits well in scenarios	

<p>where services can be efficiently replicated across many customers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MRL 3 - Competitive Analysis: Analysis of the competitive landscape and identification of differentiators. ● MRL 4 - Market Strategy Development: Development of a market strategy, including value proposition, positioning, and go-to-market plan. ● MRL 5 - Business Model Validation: Validation of the business model through pilot testing, customer feedback, and market trials. ● MRL 6 - Early Customer Engagement: Engagement with early customers and initial sales, refinement of product based on feedback. ● MRL 7 - Scaling Market Presence: Expansion of market presence through targeted marketing, partnerships, and scaling sales efforts. <p>Relevant Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Financial Viability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Focus: Validate the financial aspects of the project, ensuring it is economically viable. ○ Activities: Cost analysis, funding strategy, financial modelling, and securing initial funding. ● Market Testing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Focus: Test the project in a real-world market environment to validate market assumptions. ○ Activities: Pilot testing, early customer engagement, feedback collection, and market trials. ○ Adoption and Scaling: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Focus: Achieve market penetration and scale the project for widespread adoption. <p>Relevant Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Full-scale deployment, marketing campaigns, sales strategy implementation, and scaling operations.
<p>Group Buying: This model leverages the collective purchasing power of a group to offer products or services at a lower price, suitable for standardised goods that attract similar customer groups.</p>	
<p>Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) and Platform as a Service (PaaS): These models offer cloud-based resources and platforms that are highly standardised, allowing customers to use them as needed without significant customization. They are monetized through usage-based billing, perfect for this quadrant's scalable and efficiency-focused nature.</p>	
<p>Pay-per-use: This model fits well in contexts where customers prefer paying only for what they use, aligning with the standardised, scalable services typical of this quadrant. It encourages flexibility and can be highly competitive.</p>	
<p>Data as a Service (DaaS): Providing standardised data sets or data streams over the Internet fits well here, particularly if the data can be commoditized and delivered uniformly to multiple customers.</p>	
<p>Cloud Service Subscription: Similar to IaaS and PaaS, this model offers standardised cloud-based services on a subscription basis, allowing businesses to scale services according to customer demand.</p>	

Tab. 11 - List of business models and Market Readiness Levels applicable to KERs in Quadrant 3 of the Wardley maps.

WARDLEY Q 3	
Applicable BUSINESS MODELS	Applicable MARKET READINESS LEVELS
<p>Project Management Services: Providing structured management services for organisational improvements and technology integration projects, which can be monetized through fixed price or size-based service fees. This model aligns with the need for specialised skills and project oversight in implementing complex systems.</p>	<p>Here, only MRL levels that can input elements for the evaluation of strategic investments to achieve more efficiency in the long term are relevant:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MRL 3 - Competitive Analysis: Analysis of the competitive landscape and identification of differentiators. ● MRL 4 - Market Strategy Development: Development of a market strategy, including value proposition, positioning, and go-to-market plan.
<p>Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) and Platform as a Service (PaaS): These models offer scalable and customizable computing resources or platforms that can enhance an organisation's technological infrastructure.</p>	

<p>They are monetized through usage-based billing, ideal for organisations looking to modernise without large upfront investments.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MRL 6 - Early Customer Engagement: Engagement with early customers and initial sales, refinement of product based on feedback.
<p>Data as a Service (DaaS): This model involves making specific data sets accessible over the Internet, which can be crucial for organisations looking to improve decision-making processes or enhance operational efficiencies. It is typically monetized through subscription fees or pay-per-use models.</p>	<p>Relevant objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical Proof of Concept (PoC): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Focus: Demonstrate the technical feasibility of the concept. ○ Activities: Laboratory tests, initial prototyping, technical validation, and proof of concept.
<p>Consulting Services: Expert advice tailored to improve organisational processes, systems, or technology integration. This service is monetized by charging on a per-hour, per-project, or retainer basis, providing flexibility in how organisations can engage with and benefit from expert knowledge.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Financial Viability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Focus: Validate the financial aspects of the project, ensuring it is economically viable. ○ Activities: Cost analysis, funding strategy, financial modelling, and securing initial funding.
<p>Custom Service Development: Developing bespoke services tailored to an organisation's specific needs, especially in terms of technology and process improvement. This can be charged through project-based fees, hourly rates, or value-based pricing.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Market Testing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Focus: Test the project in a real-world market environment to validate market assumptions. <p>Activities: Pilot testing, early customer engagement, feedback collection, and market testing</p>
<p>Grant Administration: As organisations often invest in new technologies or infrastructure projects through grants, this model involves managing these funds per grant conditions, monetized by charging a management fee.</p>	

Tab. 12 - List of business models and Market Readiness Levels applicable to KERs in Quadrant 4 of the Wardley maps.

WARDLEY Q 4	
Applicable BUSINESS MODELS	Applicable MARKET READINESS LEVELS
<p>Service Subscription: This model is suitable for providing ongoing access to standardised services that require regular use and maintenance, such as security updates, compliance monitoring, and other operational tools.</p>	<p>In this quadrant, actions to achieve greater sustainability and thus more penetration can be performed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● MRL 8 - Market Penetration: Significant market penetration achieved, with growing sales and market share. ● MRL 9 - Market Leadership: Establishment as a market leader with widespread adoption and strong market position.
<p>Volume Discounting: Encouraging bulk purchases by offering discounts can be effective in a quadrant where standardised solutions are sold to a broad customer base, maximising sales volume.</p>	<p>Relevant objectives are:</p>
<p>Service Fee: Charging a fixed or percentage-based fee for each standardised service rendered is straightforward and aligns well with this quadrant's commoditized nature of products and services.</p>	<p>Market Testing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focus: Test the project in a real-world market environment to validate market assumptions. ● Activities: Pilot testing, early customer engagement, feedback collection, and market trials.
<p>Pay-per-use: This model aligns with operational services that may not be needed continuously but are essential when used, such as specific compliance checks or usage-based software tools.</p> <p>Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) and Platform as a Service (PaaS): Providing foundational services and platforms that support the standardised operational needs of various businesses, charged based on usage to align costs directly with customer consumption levels.</p>	<p>Adoption and Scaling:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focus: Achieve market penetration and scale the project for widespread adoption.
<p>Cloud Service Subscription: Similar to IaaS and PaaS, this model offers cloud-based services tailored to the</p>	

operational needs of businesses, with pricing often based on the level of service and features required.	Activities: Full-scale deployment, marketing campaigns, sales strategy, implementation, and scaling operations
Usage-based Billing: Charging customers based on their actual usage of services or products fits well with operational needs that vary in intensity and frequency among users.	

5.2. Wardley Mapping application to KERs – Examples

To complete this chapter, three examples of mapping the EOSC-related project KERs onto a Wardley Map are presented. In the first example, the general KER categories, as described in a previous exercise⁶⁴, have been mapped onto the Wardley space, instead of the single specific KERs. In the second and third examples, we applied the mapping to the specific KERs reported by AI4EOSC and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects.

KER-category mapping

In this example (Fig. 5), general KER categories have been mapped onto the Wardley space, instead of the single specific KERs. This approach provides a framework for most KERs to be mapped and allows for a general understanding of how the mapping can be executed, encompassing the diversity of outputs that the EOSC-related projects may cover, i.e.

- Technical Harmonisation
- Policy Harmonisation
- Discovery/Access Platform
- Virtual Research Environment (VRE)
- Training Resource
- Knowledge Centre
- Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI)
- Validation Tool or Other

Some KER categories are in Q1, like VREs and, partly, the Training and the Discovery /Access Platform. This implies that every time a research project needs a VRE, it has to be configured and deployed according to the custom requirements coming from the project itself, while it's hard to provide a common VRE for all. Being a bespoke service is embedded in its nature, even if it's always possible to prepare some templates for the most frequent cases.

Training facilities typically need to be built ad hoc, but there is more room for becoming standardized and being deployed at scale by using e.g. online training formats or "self-service journeys". That's why it's going towards the Q2. A Knowledge Centre is a good approach to scale the dissemination of knowledge and related outputs.

⁶⁴ Ilaria Nardello, et al. *Delivering for EOSC: Key Exploitable Results of the Horizon 2020 EOSC-related Projects (summary Report)*, 14 Nov. 2022, doi:10.5281/zenodo.7404164.

Fig. 5 – General Wardley mapping of KER categories for EOSC-related EU projects. [Click on the image to download of a high-resolution picture.](#)

The Discovery/Access platform is between Q1 and Q2, since it has to be customised according to the vertical domain of the catalogue it manages, while it can possibly become a program-wide platform where all the sub-projects’ output can be indexed and presented to the end users, supporting the adoption of results at scale.

Validation tools are a typical example of Q3 items that are planned as a way to increase the efficiency of the research infrastructure and to streamline the research processes. Building it starts as an investment in Q3, and when it is ready it can provide the value of Q4, increasing the standardization and replicability of the results and processes.

For the same reason, Technical Harmonization follows the same pattern. A policy harmonization output instead, is something that every player in that industry must comply with, thus it is directly mapped in Q4 (assuming that if we have a policy, the case is already replicated several times and needs the policymaker’s attention).

AAI infra is another example of a Q4, a commodity service that has to be simply used and adopted by everyone, since it is necessary for the coherence of the whole system, but it is not an area where to focus multiple diversified investments, since it will be hardly sustainable being the “competition” based mainly on price convenience.

AI4EOSC Mapping

In this example (Fig. 6), the AI4EOSC project KERs have been mapped.

Fig. 6 – Wardley map of the KERS produced by the AI4EOSC project. Click on the image to download a high-resolution picture

As this is a project mostly focused on the exploitation of artificial intelligence (AI) agents applied to research projects, it is normal that most of the KERS are towards the right quadrants. This is based on the assumption that the core of the research is not the AI agent itself, but rather the application of existing, market ready agents to improve the research process, the quality of the outputs, etc. The discovery platform is between Q1 and Q3 since it is tailor made on the types of research outputs to be indexed, and it is case-specific.

Developing a software stack is an investment to improve the impact and adoption of these tools in the long run, thus it is in Q3, and it needs also to develop tools like the provenance tracking tools, in order to function correctly.

In Q2 you can find all the tools and interfaces that increase the fruition of these AI-agent outputs, like training materials, reports, guidelines to aggregate recurring cases into recommendations.

In Q4 there are all the artifacts that are standardizing the adoption of AI tools in the research ecosystem of EOSC, and of course the sub parts needed to deploy an open standard (metrics, data frameworks, tools, software, interoperability APIs and frameworks, AI cloud service providers). When available, the catalogue of AI4EOSC standardised outputs shall be placed between Q2 and Q4.

FAIRCORE4EOSC KER Mapping

In this third example, we consider the KERS produced by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project (Fig. 7). This project has similar features than AI4EOSC, with only a few KERS on the left-hand side of the Wardley map, about the ideation of activity-specific assessment tools (which, by their nature, are custom-built in the initial phase of the development, and become standardised interfaces, once fully operational).

Fig. 7 – Wardley map of the KERs produced by the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. Click on the image to download a high-resolution picture

5.3. SEP Integration with Wardley mapping routines – a step-by-step guided approach to the combined use of the methodologies

This section describes how the SEP and Wardley maps can work together. This innovative approach means to guide every project coordinator in the clear understanding of how a single KER is part of a complex system, and how this complexity can be managed to maximise the impact potential and accelerate its achievement. In addition, connecting the SEP approach with the business model suggestions integrated in the quadrant-positioning provides additional tools to project coordinators to identify the financial sustainability strategies adoptable in each and every maturity stage of the KER. In short, the SEP process for each project entails the following steps:

1. Run a First Iteration of the SEP Tool

Conduct an initial analysis using the SEP tool to identify any "blind spots" or areas lacking clarity or focus.

2. Map All Key Explorable Results (KERs) to Wardley Map Quadrants

This step ensures that each output is understood within the broader context of the value chain and its stage of maturity. Guiding questions are provided in Annex II to correctly position the KERs in the appropriate quadrant of the Wardley Map. Quadrants' keywords and detailed descriptions may also help define the KER coordinates in the Wardley space.

3. Utilise Quadrant Features and Sustainability Models

Once all KERs are mapped, refer to the key features and sustainability models suggested for each quadrant. These features and models provide guidance on how to further detail the answers provided in the SEP, enhancing the understanding of long-term sustainability and impact.

4. Refine and Iterate on Project Outputs

5.4. Lessons learned from the Wardley mapping application and next steps

The application of Wardley mapping may involve a lot of work for users who lack experience in business management, and be limited by the difficulties of “atomising” each KER (i.e. reducing each KER to a number of basic components). Among the limitations that emerged, the business models indicated for the exploitation of the KER would benefit from becoming more clearly related to the specificity of the EOSC environment. This initial work may be continued and further expanded in the EOSC Gravity project, where the activities of HE Impact WG will be further supported.

6. Conclusions

The experience of the HE Impact Working Group has confirmed that EOSC-related projects need support to define an exploitation route for their key results. Finding viable pathways to exploit results would enable project consortia to fulfil their obligations towards funders and society of achieving the highest possible impact with the money invested. The approach provided by the SEP methodology was appreciated by the projects as a useful tool to envisage and own a strategy to respond to that responsibility tailored to the characteristics of the project, the consortia, and the results.

While the EOSC Macro-Roadmap remains the start and the endpoint of this awareness-creation process, and while the onus legally for sustaining those exploitation endeavours lies with the projects, the support of the policy environment remains essential to translate the conceptual framework of the EOSC Federation into a tangible asset, to which the consortia may direct their products. The SEP methodology provides a valuable tool to support the translation of intentions by the projects into real action plans, and stimulated the formulation of tangible impact among the projects. In the current development of the EOSC Federation with the establishment of the EOSC Nodes, project results should aim at becoming useful tools for the implementation of the Federation, indicating established practices and services relevant to the scientific community that deserve to be continued after the projects’ end, even becoming in some cases commercial solutions.

The legacy of this experience will be handed-over to the EOSC Gravity project, creating a continuum in the EOSC-A support action towards the HE INFRAEOSC projects in planning a sustainable process for the exploitation of their KERs towards the creation of added value and the manifestation of the impact envisaged in the grant allowance.

7. References

Description/Link
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Doran, G. T. (1981). "There's a S.M.A.R.T. way to write management's goals and objectives" (PDF). <i>Management Review</i> . 70 (11): 35–36.normal
'Getting Started with Wardley's Doctrine Is Easier Than You Think'. https://learnwardleymapping.com/2020/12/07/getting-started-with-wardleys-doctrine-is-easier-than-you-think/
Market Readiness Levels: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313063121_TRL_and_MRL_of_C-ITS_as_lessons_learned_from_the_Austrian_C-ITS_Corridor_ECo-AT/figures?lo=1 – Fig 10

Annex I: Sustainable Exploitation Planning Survey (version: 2.1)⁶⁵

Sustainable Exploitation Planning Tool - Sustainable Pathways to Exploitation of Key Result

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

SEP SURVEY

Details of Key Exploitable Result (KER)

• **Name of the KER**

• **Project acronym**

• **Project title**

• **Type of result**

- Network
- Training
- Report
- Software
- Social impact demonstrator
- Infrastructure
- Toolkit
- Service
- Tool

Problem addressed

⁶⁵ Prepared by: Ilaria Nardello (EOSC-A), and Aneta Pazik-Aybar (NCN) for the EOSC Winter School 2024 – “HE INFRAEOSC Projects: Sustainable Pathways to the exploitation of key result, for Impact”

KER description

KER's objective (Value Proposition)

Added Value

Why is this activity important for the target group; what would the EOSC ecosystem look like before/after this addition? (max 150 words)

KER's potential impact on EOSC

- Core
- Exchange
- Data Federation
- Other (enter your answer below)

Please enter other

SEP - Input (after the project's lifetime)

Shareholders

- EC (HE-project funding)
- Other public institutions (additional public funding: national/regional)
- Own Institution (Institutional funding)
- Private Donors (funding from commercial or not for profit donors)
- Other (enter your answer below)

Please enter other

Work Team / Expertise of staff working on KER

Please tick the team expertise and their current/required level of experience on a scale from 0 (no experience) to 5 (expert).

<input type="checkbox"/>	1	2	3	4	5
--------------------------	---	---	---	---	---

TECHNICAL - Current level of skills related to the technical aspects of the project	<input type="radio"/>				
TECHNICAL - Required skills related to the technical aspects of the project	<input type="radio"/>				
LEGAL - Current level of expertise in legal matters, including compliance and intellectual property rights	<input type="radio"/>				
LEGAL - Required level of expertise in legal matters, including compliance and intellectual property rights	<input type="radio"/>				
COMMUNICATION - Current ability to effectively communicate and disseminate information and results	<input type="radio"/>				
COMMUNICATION - Required ability to effectively communicate and disseminate information and results	<input type="radio"/>				
ENGAGEMENT - Current skills in stakeholder and community engagement	<input type="radio"/>				
ENGAGEMENT - Required skills in stakeholder and community engagement	<input type="radio"/>				
PROJECT MANAGEMENT - Current expertise in project management	<input type="radio"/>				
PROJECT MANAGEMENT - Required expertise in project management	<input type="radio"/>				
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT - Current expertise in commercialization and market analysis	<input type="radio"/>				
BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT - Required expertise in commercialization and market analysis	<input type="radio"/>				

Comments on this section

SEP - Process

Governance: Who owns the exploitation plan, who will be taking decisions?

(Describe briefly the governance structure taking into account leadership, ownership and the decision-making process related to exploiting your KER)

Work Team: What is the HR availability to work on the project?

- Internal: Full time
- Internal: Part time
- External service providers

Work Team: Are the roles and responsibilities defined?

- Yes, they are fully defined
- They are defined partially, some of them (might) lack clarity
- They are defined partially, some of them are not defined
- No, none of the roles is defined

Activities: Which activities are required to exploit your KER?

Please rate the importance of specific categories of activities for the successful exploitation of the KER on a scale from 0 (activity is not required) to 5 (activity is indispensable).

	1	2	3	4	5
Strategic Planning	<input type="radio"/>				
Project management	<input type="radio"/>				
Technical development	<input type="radio"/>				
Financial Resourcing	<input type="radio"/>				
IPR protection and other legal frameworks (e.g.: regulations)	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality certifications	<input type="radio"/>				
Communication/Dissemination	<input type="radio"/>				
Engagement/Business development/Marketing	<input type="radio"/>				
Other (enter your answer below)	<input type="radio"/>				

Please enter other

Activities: List 1 to 3 main challenges related to the three most important activities checked above and how you plan to manage the associated risks.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs should be defined according to one of the internationally recognised standards for developing indicators and measures, such as, e.g.:

- SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) criteria;
- RACER (Relevant, Acceptable, Credible, Easy and Robust) criteria developed as part of the European Commission's Impact Assessment Guideline
- CREAM (Clear, Relevant, Economic, Adequate, and Monitorable).

Pick and choose from the list provided in the table;
or: Create your own in the field provided below

CONSIDER: different target values and timelines

KPI name	Baseline value (project end)	Target value +1 year	Target value +2 years
TRL achieved			
Value proposition formulated			
Resources organised			
Legal framework for exploitation			
Recognition achieved			
Dissemination achievement			
Communication			
Available to the user community			
Availability on EOSC Marketplace/ Thematic Nodes/ Institutional Cloud			
Uptake by research			
Uptake by commerce			
Uptake by society			
Scale (geopolitical/technological/disciplinary) achieved			
Scalability			

Please enter below your own KPIs following the above format: KPI name; Baseline value, Target value +1 year and Target value +2 years

Comments on this section

SEP - Outputs

What non-financially evaluated output is expected from the exploitation of the KER?

- Free Access to Data/Service/Facility
- Publications
- User/Marketing Strategy
- Workshops
- Other (enter your answer below)

Please enter other

What financially evaluated output is expected from the exploitation of the KER?

- Paid Access to Data/Service/Facility
- IP License
- Contract research
- Training
- Consultancy
- Education
- Other (enter your answer below)

Please enter other

Comments on this section

Wardley map

Work in progress! You may now skip to the submission section

Submission - Thank you very much for completing the survey

Contact

[Contact Form](#)

Annex II: Guiding questions to map KERs onto the Wardley Maps

Before delving into the characteristics of the four quadrants, each *researcher* must accurately map the Key Explorable Result (KER) of their project. This preliminary step is essential to position the KER within the appropriate quadrant, to ensure that the subsequent analysis and strategic planning are aligned with the specific goals and requirements of the project.

To facilitate this process, we have developed a set of guiding questions to help researchers determine the quadrant most suitable for their KER. These questions and the keywords associated with each quadrant provide a clear and straightforward method to categorise the KER effectively.

Researchers can explore the insights provided once the KER is mapped to a specific quadrant.

Quadrant 1: Research and New Solutions (Q1) (Top-Left)

Keywords:

- High Value for End Users
- Bespoke / Advisory Approach
- Expert Guidance Highly Valuable
- Building Products / Outcomes for Specific Needs
- High Marginal Value / Low Volume

Key Questions:

1. Is the project focused on creating a highly customised, bespoke solution tailored to unique needs? (Yes: Quadrant 1 No: Proceed to the next question.)
2. Does the project involve significant experimentation, research, and development with a high tolerance for failure? (Yes: Quadrant 1 No: Proceed to the next question.)
3. Is direct interaction and partnership with the client necessary to co-design and implement the solution? (Yes: Quadrant 1 No: Proceed to the next quadrant.)

Quadrant 2: Scaling and Adoption (Q2) (Top-Right)

Keywords:

- Scalability and Impact Increase
- Adoption and Dissemination of Results
- Average Marginal Value / High Volumes
- Tech Transfer, Training, Publishing
- Open Source

Key Questions:

4. Is the project focused on making a previously developed solution scalable and widely adoptable? (Yes: Quadrant 2 No: Proceed to the next question.)
5. Does the project aim to introduce Do-It-Yourself or self-service interfaces to reduce customization needs or increase the reach/adoption of the value generated? (Yes: Quadrant 2 No: Proceed to the next question.)
6. Are you introducing modularity, composability, and vertical or horizontal scalability to match performances according to market traction? (Yes: Quadrant 2 No: Proceed to the next quadrant.)

Quadrant 3: Digital Transformation and Efficientising (Q3) (Bottom-Left)

Keywords:

- Interoperability Setup
- Process Design with Future Standardization
- Automation and Streamlining of Processes
- Investment for Future Efficiency

Key Questions:

7. Is the project aimed at enhancing and scaling internal processes for better efficiency and scalability? (Yes: Quadrant 3 No: Proceed to the next question.)
8. Does the project focus on digital transformation, including automation and process reengineering? (Yes: Quadrant 3 No: Proceed to the next question.)
9. Is the primary goal to integrate new technologies with existing organisational structures to improve internal operations? (Yes: Quadrant 3 No: Proceed to the next quadrant.)

Quadrant 4: Interoperability and Compliance (Q4) (Bottom-Right)

Keywords:

- Compliance and Regulatory Needs
- Standardization
- Common Tools and Resources
- Interoperability Adoption
- Cost Reduction and Efficiency
- Open Source

Key Questions:

10. Is the project primarily focused on ensuring compliance with industry standards and regulatory requirements? (Yes: Quadrant 4 No: Proceed to the next question.)
11. Does the project emphasise using standardised, universally accepted solutions with minimal customization? (Yes: Quadrant 4 No: Proceed to the next question.)
12. Is the project aimed at operational continuity, cost reduction, and using common tools and technologies? (Yes: Quadrant 4 No: Proceed to the next quadrant.)

Annex III: Connecting MRL with the SEP Quadrants

While Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) are widely used to measure the maturity of a technology up to its operational deployment (TRL 9), there are additional frameworks and scales to assess commercialisation and adoption beyond TRL 9. One such framework is the Market Readiness Level (MRL) scale, which focuses on market and business aspects necessary for successful commercialization and widespread adoption. Here is a brief overview of the MRL scale:

- **MRL 1 - Identification of Market Opportunity:** Initial market research is conducted to identify potential markets and customer segments.
- **MRL 2 - Market and Customer Needs Understanding:** Detailed understanding of market needs, customer pain points, and potential demand.
- **MRL 3 - Competitive Analysis:** Analysis of the competitive landscape and identification of differentiators.
- **MRL 4 - Market Strategy Development:** Development of a market strategy, including value proposition, positioning, and go-to-market plan.
- **MRL 5 - Business Model Validation:** Validation of the business model through pilot testing, customer feedback, and market trials.
- **MRL 6 - Early Customer Engagement:** Engagement with early customers and initial sales, refinement of product based on feedback.
- **MRL 7 - Scaling Market Presence:** Expansion of market presence through targeted marketing, partnerships, and scaling sales efforts.
- **MRL 8 - Market Penetration:** Significant market penetration achieved, with growing sales and market share.

- **MRL 9 - Market Leadership:** Establishment as a market leader with widespread adoption and strong market position.

It is possible to connect TRL with the MRL scale and combine them into a “lean thinking” integrated scale that accounts for the entire lifecycle of a research project. This results in an **Integrated Project Lifecycle Scale:**

1. Feasibility Analysis

- Focus: Assess the project’s overall feasibility (technical, financial, and market aspects).
- Activities: Initial research, feasibility studies, risk assessment, and stakeholder analysis.

2. Technical Proof of Concept (PoC):

- Focus: Demonstrate the technical feasibility of the concept.
- Activities: Laboratory tests, initial prototyping, technical validation, and proof of concept.

3. Financial Viability:

- Focus: Validate the financial aspects of the project, ensuring it is economically viable.
- Activities: Cost analysis, funding strategy, financial modelling, and securing initial funding.

4. Market Testing:

- Focus: Test the project in a real-world market environment to validate market assumptions.
- Activities: Pilot testing, early customer engagement, feedback collection, and market trials.

5. Adoption and Scaling:

- Focus: Achieve market penetration and scale the project for widespread adoption.
- Activities: Full-scale deployment, marketing, sales strategy implementation, and scaling operations.

Appendix 2: Note on Virtual Access

Dale Robertson, EGI Foundation

Table of contents

1. Introduction	777
2. How the Mechanism Works	78
3. Experience with use of the VA mechanism	79
4. Assessment of VA as a funding instrument	80
5. Conclusions	82

1. Introduction

1.1. The VA Funding Mechanism, and Forms of Access

Virtual Access (VA) is primarily the name of a form of access to research resources, but the term is also used to refer to the financial instrument used in a subset of calls in the Research Infrastructures Work Programme of Horizon Europe (and previously in Horizon 2020) to reimburse providers for the cost of provisioning virtual access to services⁶⁶. VA enables the use of Framework Programme grant funding in a way which directly matches the actual cost of resource provision: providers' costs are reimbursed based on the consumption of their resources. It thus differs from public procurement, in which providers bid amounts in a competitive selection process. As a funding mechanism, it is intended for widening use of resources to researchers who may not otherwise use them; in its current form, it is not fundamentally intended for sustaining resources on a longer-term basis.

VA is primarily aimed at (digital) services. It is suited for mature services (TRL 8-9), because it is focussed on consumption of delivered services/resources. It is not suitable for development work (TRL < 8) since their delivery and consumption may not be assured.

In examining the Virtual Access mechanism within EOSC Focus, the focus is on VA as a funding mechanism, rather than as a form of access to resources⁶⁷. Similar financial instruments exist for use with different forms of access:

- Virtual access (VA) means open and free access through communication networks to digital resources and services needed for research, without selecting the users to whom access is provided. VA is intended for use with “non-rivalrous” (also referred to as “non-depletable”) resources: those which can be used simultaneously by an unlimited number of users, and without

⁶⁶ The resource providers can be Research Infrastructures or e-Infrastructures, and in the remainder of this note the term “Research Infrastructure” should be understood to also include e-Infrastructures

⁶⁷ Further discussion on access modes is included in the *ESFRI Report on Access to Research Infrastructures and Charter on Access to RIs*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10533244>. See also https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/partners-networking/access-research-infrastructure/access-european-research-infrastructures_en

selection of users. Typical services envisaged include provision of access to databases available via the Internet, or data deposition services.

- Trans-national access (TNA) means “free of charge” access to Research Infrastructure services to selected users, who usually work in a country other than that where the services or facilities (or distributed resources) are located. The access can be physical or remote. In the former, users *physically* visit an infrastructure, facility or equipment. Under this model, the available services or resources are not unlimited, and a competitive process may be required following a defined procedure and criteria for the selection of users. Alternatively, access can also be *remote*, where the user does not physically visit the facility, but as with physical access the resources are not unlimited, and competitive selection is required. Such resources often require some user support to be physically present at the site of the resource.

These different types of access can be stimulated by use of the same underlying funding mechanism. VA was the access mode deployed in the Horizon 2020 EOSC-hub and INFRAEOSC-07 projects which have been studied in EOSC Focus to date, hence the discussion here mentioning VA in particular. In practice, “remote access” is a more accurate description of the form of access to many e-Infrastructure services (which were the main type of services used in EOSC-hub and the -07 projects) than “virtual access”, because the resources are not unlimited, and also because some technical user support local to the resource is often required.

1.2 Relevance of a VA-like Mechanism to EOSC

EOSC encourages secondary use of data and cross-disciplinary research. This entails access to and (re-)use of resources by users who are outside of the resource providers’ primary communities. Such usage is likely to be cross-border and/or cross-domain, or even cross-institutional within a single country. Resource providers are typically funded, however, only for provision within their primary user communities. Provision to users more widely than this requires a mechanism to fund the extra costs incurred. A financial mechanism similar to that used for VA is a possible candidate for addressing this need, because

- resources are open (at least to the community specified in the call text);
- resources are free at the point of use;
- funding is targeted at making resources available beyond primary user communities.

2. How the Mechanism Works⁶⁸

As a financial instrument, VA has been used within Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects as a way of paying for providing access to resources of Research Infrastructures (RIs) or e-Infrastructures.

⁶⁸ The description here includes excerpts from the decision of DG RTD and DG CNECT about the use of unit costs in Horizon Europe: *DECISION authorising the use of unit costs for the costs of providing trans-national and virtual access in Research Infrastructures actions under the Horizon Europe Programme (2021-2027) and the Research and Training Programme of the European Atomic Energy Community (2021-2025)* https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/unit-cost-decision-research-infrastructures_horizon-euratom_en.pdf, May 2022.

The VA mechanism reimburses the costs incurred by an RI for providing access to users (also “cost of access provision”)⁶⁹.

The cost of access provision can be determined either by calculating eligible *actual costs* incurred, or by use of *unit costs* (i.e. the cost of the unit of access to each RI service) defined in the project’s grant agreement, combined with data about the number of units used to calculate the total cost. Where unit costs are used, the access costs are calculated by multiplying the unit cost by the quantity of access (i.e. number of units) provided. The unit costs must be indicated in the proposal, to then be reflected in the grant agreement. A combination of actual and unit costs can also be used.

RIs must publicise widely the access offered under the grant agreement to ensure that researchers are made aware of the possibilities open to them.

The EU financial support to VA covers the cost of access provision incurred by the RI under the project, including the technological and scientific support researchers need to effectively use the services. Capital investments (including depreciation costs of equipment, infrastructure or other assets) and internally invoiced goods and services are not eligible costs unless otherwise specified under the specific call or topic, in which case only the portion used to provide VA under the project can be eligible. Periodic assessment by an external board during the project lifetime is required.

3. Experience with use of the VA mechanism

EOSC Focus T5.3 has examined the experience of the INFRAEOSC-07 and EOSC-hub projects with use of Virtual Access. These were all projects funded under Horizon 2020, and involved experience of e-Infrastructure service providers in particular. The perspective and experience of these service providers may be somewhat different from that of RIs, which also make use of the VA or TNA model, and on which T5.3 plans to conduct further work in the remaining few months of EOSC Focus, after the publication of this deliverable.

3.1 EOSC-hub (2018-2021)

EOSC-hub experimented with the use of VA to collect input on its advantages and disadvantages that could help evolve the mechanism in Horizon Europe. The experiment was successful, in that the services made available with VA funding saw significant increases in their usage. The mechanism’s rules however didn’t allow service providers to recover the full marginal costs of the service provision (capital investment and depreciation costs were not eligible to be claimed), nor to limit the user base to specific communities. For these reasons, several service providers in EOSC-hub felt unable to participate in the experiment, for example because they would not be able to fully cover their costs in doing so, or because they would be unable to respect their service’s access policy. Those who did take part found that they incurred significant overheads for service coordination, cost calculation and reporting. Collection of the actual cost information of service usage was new to the providers, and hence non-automated and time-consuming.

3.2 INFRAEOSC-07 Projects (2021-2023)

The VA rules were updated for these projects, to allow the inclusion of capital costs, which made more service providers willing to participate. The INFRAEOSC-07 projects concluded overall that the VA

⁶⁹ The methodology for calculating unit costs is defined in the Decision of the previous note.

mechanism was useful and worked well to fund the extra delivery costs of providing services to new/non-primary user groups, despite being rather inflexible.

The 07 projects were required to form an External Advisory Board for VA assessment. Its findings were, in summary

- Actual costs were in general easier to calculate and claim than unit costs, whose calculation required a significant up-front effort and learning curve;
- More flexibility to update unit costs or reallocate budgets during the course of the project would be desirable, in the interests of ensuring that budget was allocated in such a way as to respond to demand;
- Clearer information is needed on the VA auditing process and requirements;
- A longer-term support to the VA mechanism (i.e. rather than the mechanism only being available within projects, limiting its use by communities to 2-3 years at a time) would encourage its use and increase uptake of services by researchers.

4. Assessment of VA as a funding instrument

Based on the experiences of the EOSC-hub and INFRAEOSC-07 projects, the following strengths and weaknesses can be identified.

4.1 Strengths of VA

- VA provides users with a mechanism for consumption of resources or services they cannot otherwise access;
- VA funding can be employed when a user is not otherwise eligible to consume resources (i.e. they have no other eligible source of funding, or have already exhausted their other sources). This means VA is well-suited to funding “orphaned” communities’ access to resources⁷⁰. In the interests of efficient use of public funding, significant effort needs to be invested in the correct identification of eligibility, for example ensuring that other potential funding sources are exhausted first before the VA funding is used⁷¹, but overall VA is very valuable as, in essence, a funding of last resort, supporting research activities which would otherwise not be possible;
- VA is helpful in ensuring efficient use of public investment, since it helps with utilisation of unallocated capacity from RIs;
- Procurement issues are avoided: installations provided comply with their local procurement rules;
- Services are free at the point of use, so transactions with end users do not incur VAT.

4.2 Weaknesses of VA

- The VA mechanism was inflexible in terms of the ability to reallocate unused budget to alternative providers participating in the same project. For example, where demand for a particular service was lower than expected, it was difficult to reallocate budget to another, more in-demand service and thus ensure that the project’s VA budget was consumed.

⁷⁰ Indeed, this achieves the EC’s fundamental objective with the VA or TNA instruments

⁷¹ See the experience of EGI-ACE, summarised for example in its [Impact Report](#). See Chapter 4, page 18 “Resource Allocation Approach”.

- Use of the mechanism entailed a high admin burden. Calculation of unit costs required reference to the previous financial year⁷², but adjusting them during the course of the project required a Grant Agreement amendment. The specific issue experienced by the 07 projects was the dramatic increase in electricity prices following the invasion of Ukraine.
- The mechanism has, to date, been used within EC-funded research projects, so service provision can be funded for 2-3 years at most, which is shorter than many users require⁷³.
- Use of VA with data services in particular (i.e. services for sharing and preserving data) raises the issue of the need for associated longer-term data storage solutions.
- The usage and costs reported by the projects were not subjected to an audit, which might have helped to identify areas for improvement and accelerate the evolution of more standardised methods for costing and reporting.

Overall, despite the issues encountered, VA was considered by e-Infrastructure providers to be a very good mechanism for sustaining cross-border and cross-domain access to digital resources, whose use should be continued for the time being as there is currently no better alternative. e-Infrastructures would very much like to be able to rely on a source of VA funding being available, to provide greater confidence that they could serve the needs of research groups.

4.3 Potential of a VA-like Mechanism in EOSC

A motivation for EOSC Focus to examine previous experience with the use of VA was to gain some insights into its potential to be adapted for use on a longer-term basis in EOSC, i.e. in conjunction with the future governance and funding model which will be defined for EOSC post-2027. As described in section 1.2 above, a solution is required for funding the additional costs incurred by cross-border or cross-domain resource provision.

The representatives of the EOSC-hub and INFRAEOSC-07 projects who were interviewed by EOSC Focus felt that the VA mechanism had potential to be adapted for use in EOSC, and no reasons were identified for why the mechanism should not inherently be provided, in future, on a longer-term basis. The audience at the EOSC session at the EGI 2024 conference⁷⁴ also appeared generally supportive of this possibility.

It may be of interest for EOSC-A to consider the possible use of a VA-like financial mechanism in the post-2027 EOSC, for example as a longer-term funding mechanism as part of a “programme”, such as within a European Partnership, for 7-10 years; It may be worth bearing this in mind when considering the future legal form for EOSC, to ensure it would be able to support such a mechanism.

Such an instrument would require a transparent (e.g. demand-driven) mechanism, by which the programme/EOSC legal entity would select the resources eligible to be offered/consumed with funding from the VA budget, with clear, simple usage tracking, and auditability - the more automated, the better.

⁷² Note: which would not be possible for a new service.

⁷³ See EGI-ACE D2.10 Final Recommendations, Chapter 4, recommendation commentary 2, calling for a dedicated funding mechanism.

⁷⁴ <https://indico.egi.eu/event/6441/sessions/5188/#20241002>

- It is important to recall that VA is not under discussion here as a funding mechanism for all resource consumption which takes place via EOSC, but only to pay for the marginal costs of the additional cross-border or cross-domain usage which arises as a result of EOSC.
 - The VA budget should be used to pay for resource consumption in cases where the user is not otherwise eligible to consume them (and/or alternative funds - e.g. national or project funds - are spent first) - so-called orphaned communities
 - Service providers' policies currently restrict their ability to offer services outside of their national borders or traditional communities, meaning the likely level of demand which would arise from orphaned communities for services (e.g. compute, storage, data as a service) through EOSC is currently unknown
 - Automation would also be a benefit here, but may require simplification and harmonisation of the funding landscape
- Clarity is required about which resources are suited to use with the VA mechanism; some types of resources or services may not be compatible with the costing and accounting methods required
 - Services with high fixed costs, and open software, are examples which might fall into this category. This requires further study.

5. Conclusions

The interviews conducted with the EOSC-hub and INFRAEOSC-07 project representatives show that there is support within the EOSC community for the use of a VA-type mechanism in the post-2027 EOSC. Despite its imperfections it is regarded by many as the best mechanism currently available for funding consumption of services outside of their usual domains. More work is required however to investigate more thoroughly the potential for use of VA, if it is to be seriously considered as a candidate funding model for use in the EOSC landscape on a longer-term basis than its previous use within projects. EOSC Focus plans to contribute further work in this direction in the remaining months of EOSC Focus.

The EC (DG RTD Unit A4) is understood to be currently collecting information related to possible use of the Virtual Access instrument for Research Infrastructures on a more sustained basis in FP10⁷⁵. Many stakeholders from the EOSC community have relevant experience to input to this discussion. Also interesting is the related question of the implications of an EOSC-dedicated VA instrument, which could potentially attract RIs to provide their services/resources through EOSC, helping to clarify the EOSC value proposition.

Other work which could be performed includes

- Additional information about experience with VA: the work has only examined a limited number of projects so far. This could be broadened by interviewing some research infrastructures which have made use of VA or TNA⁷⁶. It is also of interest to gather information from projects which are using VA in Horizon Europe projects, such as iImagine⁷⁷, to understand how the rules have evolved

⁷⁵ The HE Research Infrastructures Work Programme 2025, is also expected to include a call to explore a new sustained scheme for access to Research Infrastructures.

⁷⁶ Although [this Open Letter](#) has been reviewed, which provides a good assessment of the broader experience of use of remote and virtual access in RIs.

⁷⁷ <https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

since Horizon 2020.

- Examining potential scenarios and requirements arising through potential use of a VA-like instrument in EOSC, such as
 - the implications of the VA budget “pot” involving contributions from multiple different funding agencies
 - use of VA together with user credits (e.g. as used in a basic form currently in the EOSC EU Node) as a form of virtual currency, and any issues of compatibility which may arise
 - usage monitoring requirements to support such a mechanism, and whether these are currently met by the EU Node’s monitoring service.
- Gaining insights into VA as seen from the perspective of EC and Research Executive Agency officials who have had involvement with projects in which it has been used.
- Further consideration of the potential mechanisms for and automation of service selection and budget allocation relating to use of VA in EOSC.

Appendix 3: Institutionalised European Partnerships under Article 185 TFEU

Miguel Rey Mazón, Graz University of Technology

Table of contents

1. Introduction	84
2. Funding model: contributions from EC and Participant States	84
3. Differences in the financial settings between Art. 185 and Co-Funded European Partnerships	86
4. Conclusion	88
5. Examples of Art 185 Partnerships	88

1. Introduction

Institutionalised European Partnerships (IEPs) under Art 185 TFEU were launched to bring together public funding bodies from relevant MS to fund activities on a topic of strategic interest for the EU and MS at an intensity or scale capable of making an impact at EU level. Article 185 TFEU enables the EU, represented by the EC, to agree with MS to implement Horizon Europe through R&I programmes jointly undertaken by several MS. It also enables MS to participate in the partnership's legal entity that executes those programmes (by contrast, the EC cannot participate in the entity).

In practical terms, by aligning MS national strategies with the EU's strategy (indicated in the approval by the European Council or the European Parliament), and using national and EU funding for a common goal through joint activities, European partnerships can achieve a higher impact, optimise the use of public resources, and overcome fragmentation of funding sources for research.

Art 185 IEPs can be formed with just 40% of EU MS. However, since the procedure to add new MS to the Partnership is lengthy and complex, involving decisions by the EU Parliament and/or the European Council, the preference is to include from the beginning as many MS as possible. Non-Associated Countries (ACs) are excluded by default, but they may be included "through a specific derogation in the basic act". Eligibility for participation and funding follows HE rules.

There are currently two Art 185 IEPs running: the Metrology Partnership⁷⁸, managed by EURAMET e.V., and the IEP for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA)⁷⁹. A third one, EDCTP2, has evolved into a Joint Undertaking (i.e. HE Partnership under Art 187 TFEU).

2. Funding model: contributions from EC and Participant States

Art 185 IEPs require MS who take part in the Partnership (also known as Participating States) to commit cash from national sources, via national research programmes, or national/regional budgets. Other activities funded and organised by MS in the Partnership provide additional leverage to the efforts made by partners (MS/AC governments, or national Research Funding Organisations to which

⁷⁸ <http://metpart.eu>

⁷⁹ www.prima-med.org

MS/AC delegate their participation in the Partnership) and are counted as in-kind contributions. *The total contribution committed by the partners other than the EC has to be at least 50% (MS:EC funding ratio 1:1), and may reach up to 75% (MS:EC funding ratio 3:1) of the Partnership's aggregated budgetary commitments.*

A maximum of 5% of the cash contributions from Participating States can be dedicated to cover administrative costs and coordination and support and other non-competitive activities, while the remaining 95% is used for (competitive) R&I activities. Funding from the EC is used exclusively for competitive activities. The EC delegates the management of the funding it provides to the Dedicated Implementation Structure (DIS), which is the legal entity created to manage the Partnership. In turn, the DIS delegates to the Partnership's Participating States the management of those activities funded exclusively by national programmes that are aligned with the Partnership's goals and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA).

2.1. How is the funding implemented?

The main instrument to fund activities is grants to projects, selected following open and competitive calls for proposals managed by the DIS. According to the Decisions by which the two existing Art 185 partnerships were started, the activities that can be funded by them comprise

1. Activities funded with EC money managed directly by the DIS. Grant Agreements are signed between the awardees and the DIS;
2. Activities funded by the Participating States (i.e. not by the Partnership) that contribute to the Partnership's objectives, or that are directly linked to the uptake of results from projects funded by the Partnership, with Grant Agreements signed between awardees and national RFOs, comprising:
 - 2.1. activities selected following transnational open and competitive calls for proposals organised by the DIS, but managed by the national RFOs under national programmes of the Participating States, mainly in the form of grants;
 - 2.2. activities organised and funded under national programmes of Participating States, including transnational projects, called Participating States Initiated Activities (PSIAs), and other activities intended to support the implementation of the Partnership's programme (e.g. an event to assist applicants to prepare applications to calls issued by the DIS).

The difference between 2.1 and 2.2 is that, in the former, "activities are evaluated and selected based on rules... analogous to the Rules for Participation of [the running Framework Programme]", using common funding principles; additionally, applicants have to comply with the participation and funding criteria set by the Participating States, which may be more restrictive. PSIAs and other support activities follow entirely the eligibility and funding criteria of the relevant Participating State(s). The benefits of counting national activities as activities of the Partnership are twofold:

- Participating States have an incentive to collect information about all activities relevant to the Partnership in which organisations in the country at all levels are involved, including those that involve cooperation with other countries;
- for the EC, including these activities in the Annual Work Programme is seen as a further contribution towards the objectives of the Partnership (at no cost to the EC).

PSIAs have to be aligned with the Partnership's objectives (as defined in the SRIA), and must be validated by international external experts and the EC (see below).

Horizon Europe funding rules apply unless otherwise specified in the Decision by which the Partnership was established, so entities from non-co-funding countries (i.e. those that are not in the Partnership) also have the right to apply and receive co-funding at the same level as in standard (i.e. not Partnership-related) Horizon Europe activities. Project co-funding cannot exceed the funding rates of HE.

2.2. How are in-kind contributions dealt with?

PSIAs, i.e. activities organised, managed and funded by Participating States and monitored by the DIS aligned with the Partnership’s objectives as defined in the SRIA are counted as in-kind contributions (IKC). PSIAs are included in the Partnership’s Annual Work Programme after acceptance by the EC, which is also responsible for assessing/evaluating the value (cost) assigned to these activities by Participating States.

PSIAs comprise activities (national, bilateral, multilateral programmes, spanning from research actions to mobility actions) in topics aligned with the objectives of the Partnership, thus indirectly supporting its implementation. With the PSIAs, Participating States demonstrate their efforts “to foster the alignment of national programmes and interoperability of national regulations”; moreover, they “enhance active participation from researchers from non-EU countries members of the Partnership, technological transfer and commercialisation of research results” in activities done in cooperation with third countries (MS, AC, or other non-members of the partnership) that also contribute to the partnership’s objectives.

Valuation

IKC are valued according to usual accounting practices and applicable standards of the Participant States, or their national RFOs and applicable International Accounting and Financial Reporting Standards. Further criteria and processes might be established by the Partnership’s governing body. The Partnership’s DIS is also the ultimate responsible for certifying/verifying and auditing the value of IKC. Compliance with reporting procedures of the HE Regulation is also to be sought.

What are they used for / what do they pay?

IKC comprise the costs of any activity carried out by Participant States using their own (national) funding sources that are aligned with and support the Partnership’s objectives.

In the case of PRIMA, the PSIAs planned for 2022 were valued at 49.7 million €, which can be compared with the 32.1 and the 28 million € (including 8 million € from non-EU countries) spent in the Partnership by the EC and the Participant States, respectively.⁸⁰ Further analytics on funding and projects can be found in the [PRIMA Intelligent Analytical Tool](#).

3. Differences in the financial settings between Art. 185 and Co-Funded European Partnerships (CFEP)

In this section, we compare Co-Funded European Partnerships (CFEPs) and IEPs under Art 185, because they both aim at pooling national resources to carry out transnational activities. Both partnership types use EC funding as leverage against funding from national research programmes,

⁸⁰ See PRIMA’s 2022 Annual Work Programme, Table 10 on page 57, with full description in section 6, pages 86-103, <https://prima-med.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/AWP22.pdf>.

and both require broad geographical coverage. Also, the scale of the total investment is similar. There are however notable differences between them worth noting:

- At difference with IEPs, which require a Decision by the European Parliament and Council, CFEPs result from competitive HE calls to which MS governments, funding agencies, or other public authorities in MS, can apply, to address “societal grand challenges and, specifically, areas of high public good where EU action will add value while reflecting national priorities and/or policies”. The corresponding calls for proposals in HE’s Work Programme are then issued.
- The funding committed by the EC (typically 30%, up to 50% in some cases) and thus the expected contribution from participating MS are specified in the calls.⁸¹
- In CFEPs, calls for proposals are launched by the Partnership, but the implementation of the projects (i.e. the management of the EC funding) is *distributed* among Participating States via national/regional funders. Besides the common Rules for Participation set by HE, each research partner funded by the Partnership’s research programmes must comply with the eligibility criteria and rules of its corresponding national/regional funding organisation. EC funding rates for projects vary from 30% to 70%.
- In IEPs Art 185, the implementation of the EC’s budget is *centralised* (i.e. managed by the DIS). The EC:MS budget ratio is defined individually for each partnership, with the minimum of 1:1, i.e. the contribution from MS must be at least as high as that of the EC, but is often higher (up to 1:3, i.e. MS funding is 75% of the total Partnership’s budget).
- In CFEPs, the Work Programme is excluded from HE, and is prepared and fully implemented by representatives of the participating MS. Calls are only launched after negotiation on budget, to ensure absorptive capacity among MS and willingness to co-fund. External advice from stakeholders (MS, industry) also foreseen.
- In IEPs Art 185, the Work Programme is prepared by participating countries. Parts of the Partnership’s WP may be included in HE WP so that the Partnership receives further funding from the EC.
- Art 185 IEPs issue calls for proposals for projects that are entirely organised and managed by the participating MS, but following the HE Rules for Participation; additionally, Art 185 IEPs count as in-kind contributions all other activities in line with the Partnership’s objectives funded by Participating States, but organised and managed according to their respective criteria and eligibility conditions. There are no in-kind contributions in CFEPs.
- In Art 185 IEPs, the funding rate of awarded projects is not related to that of the overall partnership, and depends on the type of action. For example, in the Metrology Partnership, funding rates for applicants depend on whether the MS/AC they are from has committed contributions in cash to the partnership. PRIMA established its funding rates in accordance with Horizon 2020 (and subsequently with HE): it funds up to 70% of the costs in general, and up to 100% for not-for-profit entities.

In a case of an R&I topic of general interest to most or all MS, CFEP co-funding from the EC enables the alignment of national resources and investment at scale. IEPs under Art 185 are more appropriate

⁸¹ E.g. in HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-16 Co-Funded Partnership *Driving Urban Transitions to a sustainable future*, the EC set 37 million € out of the foreseen total for the partnership of 130 million €, i.e. 28%. See https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-8-climate-energy-and-mobility_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf

for topics that require high integration, since they bring all relevant MS together to fund and execute all actions required to realise a strategic challenge or opportunity, and have the EU commit large enough co-funding to attract investment by the private or public sector. Art 185 IEPs fund interconnected activities at an intensity or scale capable of making an impact at the EU level.

4. Conclusion

IEPs under Art 185 show how funding from EC and MS/AC can be coordinated to address complex problems that involve a large number of stakeholders from many different countries, very much like is the case for EOSC. This type of European Partnership grants the participating countries a high degree of autonomy in shaping and developing the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), the annual work programmes, and the call topics. However, all of this is still subject to the approval of the EC, since part of the activities within the partnership can also be funded via the running Framework Programme (i.e. Horizon Europe). The choice of topics for the activities funded with the IEP's own resources (i.e. cash contributions from partners other than the EC) is left entirely to the partnership's decision.

5. Examples of Art 185 Partnerships

5.1. European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP2)⁸²

Activities managed by the Partnership governing entity (the EDCTP Association) include those funded by the EC via H2020 and others funded by the participating countries. These cash contributions also pay for admin costs (in 2020 the EC paid 78 million € for projects and 5.3 million € for admin, with countries contributing with 6.6 million € and 600 000 € respectively). To match the EC contribution, countries can co-label other activities they fund through national programmes (not managed by the Partnership) in relevant topics as "part of the EDCTP2 programme supported by the EU". These are the PSIAAs that are counted as in-kind contribution. To justify the co-labelling, "PSIAAs are set up, funded and managed by [countries] according to national rules, but the implementation follows a set of common principles, in particular the principles of equal treatment, transparency, independent peer review evaluation and selection".

The EDCTP2 has evolved into a JU under Art 187 for the next iteration, EDCTP3, in which the partners are the EC and the EDCTP Association. This suggests the Art 185 IEP was not considered as the right tool to drive the R&I programme forward, or maybe its advantages had been exhausted, and the JU model is better going forward.

5.2. Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA)⁸³

PRIMA received 220 million € from H2020 (Parts II and III), and is getting 105 million € from HE, Pillar II "Global challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness" (i.e. a total of 325 million €). The Participating States commit to spending at least the same amount between 2017 and 2031 (initial period set for the Partnership) ("compliance with the formal financial commitments should be closely

⁸² www.edctp.org/

⁸³ www.prima-med.org.

monitored by PRIMA-IS on a regular basis”). The annual financial reports do not specify the national funding sources used by each Participating State to fund the projects.

In its interim evaluation, the EC “concluded that PRIMA is a successful instrument with an added value for the Union”, and recommended that “the Union should continue to provide financial support to allow PRIMA to fund R&I actions under the same thematic scope until 2027, and to synchronise PRIMA with the Union’s multiannual financial framework (MFF) and MFF-aligned programming cycles of R&I programmes”.

The PRIMA Foundation manages two research programmes:

- Section 1: projects selected for this section are funded under H2020/HE via Transnational Calls. The projects are managed directly by the PRIMA Foundation.
- Section 2: funding for these projects comes from and is managed by the national RFOs of the member countries of the PRIMA consortium, also awarded via competitive Transnational Calls organised by the Foundation, but managed by the Participating States (the corresponding grant agreement is signed between awardees and the national RFOs).

PRIMA’s DIS has taken the legal form of a foundation under Spanish law (the PRIMA Foundation). In 2023, PRIMA received a grant from the Spanish Ministry for Science and Innovation (117 000 €) under the *Programa de Actuación Anual 2023* to pay for the costs of running the office in Barcelona. The grant is justified by the alignment of PRIMA’s goals with those of the Spanish national science and technology plan.

Projects funded under both Sections are called “indirect actions” (because it is not PRIMA-IS who implements them).

5.3. European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET)

EURAMET is the IEP under Art 185 on metrology. The partnership is managed by EURAMET e.V., an entity under German law formed by the National Metrology Institutions (NMIs) of the participant MS. The EC participates as an observer in the Metrology Partnership Committee (the decision-making body); it also has a representative in the Steering Group. The Decision by which the Partnership was established states that the EU’s contribution to the partnership will be managed by EURAMET e.V. alone. MS have to designate EURAMET e.V. “as the structure responsible for implementing the Metrology Partnership and for receiving, allocating and monitoring the Union’s financial contribution”.

Appendix 4: Institutionalised European Partnerships under Art. 187 TFEU: the example of EuroHPC Joint Undertaking

Dale Robertson, EGI Foundation

Table of contents

Executive Summary	89
1. EuroHPC Objectives and Activities	90
2. EuroHPC Set-up	91
3. Funding and Capacity Allocation	94
4. Assessment of the EuroHPC vehicle	100
5. Conclusions	102

Executive Summary

EuroHPC JU is a legal entity which allows the EU and the participating countries to coordinate efforts and pool resources for world-class High Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure at European level. EuroHPC provides financial support, in particular in the form of grants and procurement following open and competitive calls for proposals and calls for tenders. It is created by a dedicated EU Council Regulation, which provides the procurement framework to support its operational model. The EuroHPC Governing Board (GB), the senior governing body, is composed of representatives of the EU and participating states; the EU holds an indivisible 50% of the voting rights in the GB; the remaining 50% of the votes are distributed amongst the countries.

For the acquisition and operation of the supercomputers and quantum computers, only the subset of countries which forms the hosting consortium for (and thus contributes to paying for) a particular machine has voting rights for matters relating to that machine, alongside the 50% EU voting right. The countries' votes are distributed in proportion to their financial contributions to that supercomputer.

EuroHPC is jointly funded by its members through financial contributions, paid in instalments and in-kind contributions. It has a total budget of approximately € 7 billion for 2021-2027, and will operate until 2033. The EU provides match funding to the participating states' contributions. The EuroHPC Access Policy, defined by the GB, allows for commercial users to get pay-per-use access to up to 20% of the EC's portion of the access time. This provides a revenue stream to the EuroHPC budget.

The EuroHPC JU successfully acts as the vehicle for achieving the EuroHPC objectives as part of a wider EU policy and legislative programme. Key cornerstones of the model are

- The dedicated JU Regulation providing the required procurement framework
- Capacity is free at the point of use, avoiding cross-border issues relating to purchasing or consumption
- The EU is allocated 50% of the computing capacity for use to support EU policy aims

- The 50% EU funding contribution provides an incentive to countries to participate and acts as a “glue”
- Countries benefit from increased compute capacity at lower risk than if they acted individually
- A policy and legislative programme provides a wider framework in support of EuroHPC.

The use of a Joint Undertaking as a possible legal model for EOSC post-2027 is worth considering due to the specific legal protections and allowances which can be afforded to Joint Undertakings. A possible analogy may be drawn between EuroHPC and a future EOSC legal entity (“EOSC LE”) as a legal and funding vehicle to coordinate efforts and pool resources at European level, to develop and deploy services to exploit the full potential of research data. Such an analogy is worth further exploration.

1. EuroHPC Objectives and Activities

The EuroHPC Joint Undertaking (in the following, referred to as EuroHPC) is a legal and funding entity composed of public and private members. It allows the EU and the participating countries to coordinate efforts and pool resources at European level, to develop and deploy a world-class HPC infrastructure for processing big data. Countries acting individually would struggle to deploy world-class HPC infrastructure.

EuroHPC’s main objectives are to

- Develop a world-leading federated supercomputing, quantum computing, service and data infrastructure ecosystem;
- Stimulate a technology supply industry;
- Widen use of the supercomputing infrastructure and support the development of HPC skills;
- (Added in 2024) Develop and operate AI Factories to support development of a European AI ecosystem.

The main activities of EuroHPC are to

- Acquire classical supercomputers (high-end⁸⁴, industrial-grade and mid-range⁸⁵) and quantum computers (hybrid classical-quantum computers, quantum computers or quantum simulators);
- Provide financial support, in particular in the form of procurement or research and innovation grants to participants following open and competitive calls for tenders and calls for proposals, based on annual work programmes;
- Support a network of national HPC Competence Centres to promote and facilitate access to supercomputers and quantum computers and provide training and outreach.

EuroHPC complements the European Chips Act⁸⁶ to boost Europe’s competitiveness and resilience in semiconductor technologies and applications.

⁸⁴ Also known as exascale or post-exascale (10^{18} or more operations per second).

⁸⁵ Also known as petascale or pre-exascale (10^{15} operations per second).

⁸⁶ European Parliament and Council Regulation 2023/1781 *Establishing a framework of measures for strengthening Europe’s semiconductor ecosystem*.

Section 1 Key Points

EuroHPC is a legal and funding entity which allows the EU and the participating countries to coordinate efforts and pool resources at European level. Countries acting individually would struggle to deploy world-class HPC infrastructure.

2. EuroHPC Set-up

2.1 Regulatory Framework

A 2017 Communication on the Digital Single Market⁸⁷ proposed the creation of a legal instrument to provide a procurement framework for an integrated exascale supercomputing and data infrastructure. The EuroHPC Council Regulation⁸⁸ serves as the legal instrument, and it defines the EuroHPC JU as the vehicle to implement the procurement framework⁸⁹. The Regulation makes the case for the collective effort for HPC by member states, the EU and the private sector, and argues that a market failure is responsible for Europe's relative "underperformance" in HPC compared to countries such as China and the USA.

2.2 EuroHPC Membership, Governance and Voting Rights

EuroHPC has **public members** (the EU, and **participating states** which currently include all 27 EU member states and also 8 associated countries) and **private members** ([ETP4HPC](#), [BDVA](#) and [QuIC](#)).

Joint Undertakings are public-private partnerships. In EuroHPC, however, the participating states play a strong role, whereas in other Joint Undertakings the private partners are the key entities in the Governing Board along with the EC, and (unlike in EuroHPC) the countries have no direct voting rights in the GB⁹⁰.

EuroHPC's senior governing body is the Governing Board (GB), composed of representatives of the EU and participating states. The GB is responsible for strategic policy making and funding decisions,

⁸⁷ *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions on the Mid-Term Review on the implementation of the Digital Single Market Strategy: A Connected Digital Single Market for All (COM/2017/0228 final)*, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2017:228:FIN>

⁸⁸ The original Regulation was Council Regulation 2018/1488 *Establishing the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking*, amended by Council Regulation 2021/1173. That was amended again by Council Regulation (EU) 2024/1732 *As regards a EuroHPC initiative for start-ups in order to boost European leadership in trustworthy artificial intelligence*, but the main reference text describing EuroHPC continues to be Regulation 2021/1173. Other Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe are regulated collectively by Council Regulation 2021/2085, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2021.427.01.0017.01.ENG.

⁸⁹ Lenovo Belgium brought a legal challenge against EuroHPC on 3 Dec 2020 - *Lenovo Global Technology Belgium v EuroHPC Joint Undertaking* (Case T-717/20) (2021/C 53/61) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A62020TN0717>. In response, in 2022 the European Court of Justice confirmed that EuroHPC procurements, which include the EU added value concept, are in line with EU procurement rules. For EU added value concept, see <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?text=&docid=267372&pageIndex=0&doclang=EN&mode=lst&dir=&occ=first&part=1&cid=5655186>, accessed 26 November 2024.

⁹⁰ For example, the Smart Networks and Services JU, <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/>.

including all the public procurement activities. The EU holds an indivisible 50% of the voting rights in the GB⁹¹. The other 50% of the voting rights are distributed as follows:

- For the general administrative tasks of EuroHPC, the voting rights of the participating states are distributed equally among them;
- For the tasks corresponding to the setting up of the part of the work programme related to the acquisition of supercomputers and quantum computers, the selection of the hosting entity, the federation and connectivity activities, and the research and innovation activities of the Joint Undertaking (see section 2.3 below for more details about the “pillars” under which the activities are organised), the voting rights of those participating states which are EU Member States are based on the principle of qualified majority⁹². The participating states that are third countries associated to Horizon Europe, the Digital Europe Programme, or the Connecting Europe Facility, also hold voting rights for the respective activities that are supported with funding from each of those programmes; the voting rights vary depending on the specific activity, and are defined in the EuroHPC statutes⁹³;
- **For the tasks corresponding to the acquisition and operation of the supercomputers and quantum computers, only those participating states which contribute resources to those tasks, and the EU, have voting rights**, i.e. the subset of countries which forms the hosting consortium for (and thus contributes to paying for) a particular machine has voting rights for matters relating to that machine, alongside the 50% EU voting right. The countries’ votes are distributed in proportion to their financial contributions to that supercomputer.

The GB is supported by an Industrial and Scientific Advisory Board (ISAB), which is made up of two advisory groups

- Research and Innovation Advisory Group (RIAG) and
- Infrastructure Advisory Group (INFRAG)

ISAB includes representatives of academia and industry as users and technology suppliers. It provides independent advice to the GB on the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) and on the acquisition and operation of the supercomputers owned by EuroHPC, the capability building and widening activities programme and the federation, connectivity and international cooperation activities programme.

EuroHPC has a staff, which is led by the Executive Director who is responsible for implementing the decisions adopted by the GB.

⁹¹ It is standard under the JU Regulation for the EC to hold 50% of the voting rights in the GB, although a small number of JUs derogate from this rule. For example, in the Governing Board of the Key Digital Technologies JU (KDT JU, renamed in 2023 to the [Chips JU](#)) the votes are distributed one-third each to the EC, the private partners, and the Participating States, whilst the Single European Sky ATM Research 3 JU requires that the EC and Eurocontrol each hold at least 25% of the votes.

⁹² Currently defined in Art 6(4) of the EuroHPC statutes as at least 55% of EU member states, comprising at least 65% of the total EU population

⁹³ The statutes are defined in the Annex of EuroHPC Regulation 2021/1173

2.3 Organisation of activities and decision-making process

EuroHPC pools EU resources, national resources and private investment to interconnect and federate regional, national and European HPC supercomputers and other computing systems. It acquires supercomputers and quantum computers which are located at and operated by supercomputing centres (hosting entities) in the EU. EuroHPC also funds a research and innovation programme to develop a European supercomputing supply chain, from processors and software, to applications to be run on the supercomputers, and know-how to develop strong European expertise.

EuroHPC's activities are structured into one administrative and seven technical pillars:

- Administrative pillar
- Infrastructure activities (acquisition, deployment, upgrading and operation of supercomputers)
- Activities federating the supercomputing services
- Technology-related activities (R&I activities relating to supercomputing)
- Supercomputing applications related activities
- Activities to widen the usage and skills
- International cooperation activities
- Artificial Intelligence factory (pillar added in 2024)

EuroHPC provides financial support in particular in the form of grants and procurement following open and competitive calls for proposals and calls for tenders based on annual work plans.

The strategy and plans for achieving the objectives of the Joint Undertaking are specified in its multiannual strategic programme (MSP)⁹⁴, which includes

- the acquisition of supercomputers
- the research and innovation activities including the strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA)
- the capability building and widening activities
- the federation, connectivity and international cooperation activities.

The MSP also includes the multiannual financial perspectives received from the participating states and the Commission.

The private members perform the initial drafting of the SRIA and submit it to the RIAG; the ISAB consolidates the MSP, which is used by the Executive Director as the basis for the annual work programme⁹⁵. The annual work programme describes the activities proposed for the year to come, and the corresponding expenditure estimates.

⁹⁴ The latest version, adopted by the GB in April 2024, is available at https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/document/download/651bd231-52c6-4a46-9f53-d832122a1d98_en?filename=Decision%2009.2024_2nd%20Amendment%20to%20MASP.pdf .

⁹⁵ The latest annual work programme is available from https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/about/key-documents_en#multi-annual-strategic-programme.

The GB is ultimately responsible for approving the MSP, the annual work plans and budgets, the calls for proposals, the calls for tenders and their subsequent procurement activities. In practice, the countries make significant input into the MSP and its resulting plans and proposals.

Section 2 Key Points

- EuroHPC pools EU resources, national resources and private investment to interconnect and federate regional, national and European HPC supercomputers and other computing systems. It acquires supercomputers and quantum computers which are located at and operated by supercomputing centres (hosting entities) in the EU;
- EuroHPC provides financial support in particular in the form of grants and procurement following open and competitive calls for proposals and calls for tenders;
- It is created by a dedicated EU Council Regulation, which provides the procurement framework to support its operational model;
- Joint Undertakings are public-private partnerships, but in EuroHPC the participating states play a strong role, and contribute significantly to the formulation of EuroHPC plans, proposals and tenders
 - The Governing Board (GB), the senior governing body, is composed of representatives of the EU and participating states.
 - The EU holds an indivisible 50% of the voting rights in the GB; the remaining 50% of the votes are distributed amongst the countries
- For the acquisition and operation of the supercomputers and quantum computers, only the subset of countries which forms the hosting consortium for (and thus contributes to paying for) a particular machine has voting rights for matters relating to that machine, alongside the 50% EU voting right. The countries' votes are distributed in proportion to their financial contributions to that supercomputer.

3. Funding and Capacity Allocation

3.1 Funding

EuroHPC is jointly funded by its members through financial contributions paid in instalments and in-kind contributions. Initially jointly funded by its members to a total of around € 1 billion⁹⁶, EuroHPC now has a total budget of approximately € 7 billion for 2021-2027, and will operate until 2033. This consists of

- € 3 billion from the EU (MFF 2021-2027)
 - € 1.9 billion from the Digital Europe Programme
 - € 900 million from Horizon Europe
 - € 200 million from Connecting Europe Facility
- € 3 billion match funding from the participating states - in-kind and cash contributions
- € 900 million from private members (in-kind and cash contributions).

⁹⁶ Regulation (EU) 2018/1488 establishing the European high-performance computing joint undertaking, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/1_european-high-performance-computing-joint-undertaking.html, accessed 27 November 2024.

The EU contribution to a Joint Undertaking is always between 25% and 50% of the total budget⁹⁷. In the case of EuroHPC, the EU provides match funding to the participating states' contributions.

3.1.1 EU Contributions

The EU's contributions to EuroHPC's activities are cash contributions, funded as follows:

Pillar	Funding Programme
Administrative pillar	The administrative costs (max €92 million ⁹⁸) are covered by the EU contribution ⁹⁹
Infrastructure activities (acquisition, deployment, upgrading and operation of supercomputers)	Digital Europe
Activities federating the supercomputing services	Digital Europe and Connecting Europe Facility
Technology-related activities (R&I activities relating to supercomputing)	Horizon Europe
Supercomputing applications related activities	Horizon Europe
Activities to widen the usage and skills	Digital Europe
International cooperation activities	Horizon Europe
Artificial Intelligence factory (pillar added in 2024)	Digital Europe

Note that the EU funding for infrastructure activities comes from the Digital Europe programme, not from Horizon Europe.

Funding rates for the eligible costs of beneficiaries of research and innovation grants issued in response to calls for proposals, vary according to the types of organisation (non-profit or for-profit) receiving EuroHPC funding, and are specified in the grant agreement. EuroHPC has adopted the Horizon Europe (and previously Horizon 2020) rules of participation.

3.1.2 Contributions from Participating States and Private Members

The participating states arrange amongst themselves their collective contributions to EuroHPC and how they will deliver them. Participating states and private members can make contributions in cash and, for operational activities (as opposed to administrative activities) also in-kind.

In-kind contributions to operational activities (IKOP) are investments to acquisitions and operational activities from the private members and the participating states consisting of the eligible costs¹⁰⁰ incurred by them in implementing such actions, less the contributions by the Joint Undertaking, the participating states or any other EU contribution to those costs. IKOP are in-kind contributions made to EuroHPC linked to its work plan and co-financed by the EU.

⁹⁷ See Council Regulation 2021/2085, Recital 19.

⁹⁸ See EuroHPC Regulation 2021/1173, Art 5(1).

⁹⁹ Note that for other JUs the administrative costs are usually split 50-50 between the EU and the other members. See Council Regulation 2021/2085, Article 28(4).

¹⁰⁰ Eligible costs are as defined in the programme which is funding any particular action: Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, Digital Europe or Connecting Europe Facility

In-kind contributions to additional activities can also be made by participating states. These relate to activities which do not receive financial support from EuroHPC but which contribute to its objectives. They may include non-eligible costs of indirect actions funded by EuroHPC. These costs do not form part of EuroHPC's budget.

Relevant eligible costs of beneficiaries in participating states in Horizon Europe projects and actions funded from the Digital Europe Programme or the Connecting Europe Facility can be counted as national financial (cash) contributions of the participating states to EuroHPC.

Member States' use of financial contributions under programmes co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund+ (ESF+), the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) for EuroHPC activities may be considered as national contributions to EuroHPC¹⁰¹.

Participating states thus have a strong incentive to participate in EuroHPC, particularly as a hosting entity or within a hosting consortium, due to the ways in which funding from various EU programmes can be used to count towards the national cash contributions, and given that a significant portion of the cost of a supercomputer in a country can be considered as an in-kind contribution. Section 3.3 below includes indications of the contributions made to the EuroHPC budget.

3.2 Activities

3.2.1 Acquisitions

As described in section 2.3, EuroHPC draws up multi-annual plans, and annual plans and budgets. These are approved by the GB, in which the EC and the participating states are the voting members. EuroHPC's activities are structured into the seven pillars listed in section 3.3. The plans include identifying which supercomputers or quantum computers will be acquired or upgraded. For this, EuroHPC publishes¹⁰² calls for expressions of interest to host a supercomputer or quantum computer, from which the hosting entity or hosting consortium is selected. Calls for procurement are then published to proceed with the process of acquisition, deployment, or upgrading.

EuroHPC supercomputers and quantum computers are located in EU MS. They are fully owned or jointly owned by EuroHPC. Each is acquired and operated by a hosting entity or a hosting consortium on behalf of EuroHPC. A hosting entity represents an EU MS or a hosting consortium of participating states, and is the entity or site where the funded EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer will be installed. Other participating states can join a hosting consortium, on agreement of its financial contribution with the other consortium members. For industrial-grade supercomputers or partitions, the hosting consortium consists of a consortium of private partners.

Ownership of EuroHPC supercomputers and quantum computers, and the EU's contribution to their costs, can be summarised as follows:

Type of Supercomputer	EuroHPC ownership	EU Contribution to Total Cost of Ownership
High-end supercomputers	EuroHPC acquires and owns	Up to 50% of acquisition costs and up to 50% of operating costs

¹⁰¹ There are some restrictions on the use of Recovery and Resilience Fund money.

¹⁰² https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/index_en

Type of Supercomputer	EuroHPC ownership	EU Contribution to Total Cost of Ownership
Quantum computers	EuroHPC acquires and owns	Up to 50% of acquisition costs and up to 50% of operating costs
Industrial-grade supercomputers ¹⁰³	EuroHPC acquires and owns or co-owns with the consortium or private partners	Up to 35% of acquisition costs and up to 35% of operating costs ¹⁰⁴
Mid-range supercomputers	EuroHPC acquires and jointly owns with the hosting entity or consortium	Up to 35% of acquisition costs and up to 35% of operating costs

The EuroHPC Regulation also contains provisions for transfer of ownership of the supercomputers, after a specified period (four or five years, or after full depreciation in the case of the mid-range supercomputers), to their respective hosting entities¹⁰⁵ on reimbursement to EuroHPC of the residual value, or sold to another entity, or decommissioned.

3.2.2 R&I Activities

Funding rates for the eligible costs of beneficiaries of research and innovation grants issued in response to calls for proposals, vary according to the types of organisation (non-profit or for-profit) receiving EuroHPC funding, and are specified in the grant agreement. EuroHPC has adopted the Horizon Europe (and previously Horizon 2020) rules of participation.

The 2022 Annual Activity Report shows that participating states made financial contributions of € 14.6 million to indirect R&I actions.

3.3 Income

An IKOP is recognised in the net assets of EuroHPC only once the activities are concluded, reported and certified, which can take a considerable time. The EU's contributions, however, are made in cash and paid in advance (at the beginning of a project implementation), and recognised in the EuroHPC accounts when paid. This causes a large gap between the recognised amounts of the EU cash contributions and the in-kind contributions. This gap will close gradually during the remainder of EuroHPC's lifetime.

To provide some illustration, the 2022 and 2023 annual cash and (unverified) in-kind contributions can be summarised as follows¹⁰⁶:

	Cash 2022 (€ million)	(Unverified) IKOP 2022 (€ million)	Cash 2023 (€ million)	(Unverified) IKOP 2023 ¹⁰⁷ (€ million)	IKOP Cumulative 2021-2023 (€ million)
EU contribution (cash)	407	n/a	489	n/a	n/a

¹⁰³ These supercomputers/partitions must be hosted in a hosting entity of a EuroHPC supercomputer.

¹⁰⁴ The remainder of the total cost of ownership is borne by the private partners.

¹⁰⁵ Or, in the case of the industrial-grade supercomputers, to the consortium of private partners.

¹⁰⁶ Figures are approximate due to some adjustments in the budgets which are not shown here.

¹⁰⁷ Note that the 2023 Consolidated Annual Activity Report shows, in section 2.3.1, significantly higher IKOP contributions, of €51.9m and €19.1m for the participating states and the private members respectively.

Participating states contribution (acquisitions)	123	25	93	14	52
Private members	-	6.8	-	4	15
Total revenue	531	31.8	582	18	67

The total contributions of the participating states and the EU need to match by the end of the lifetime of EuroHPC. The annual cash contributions of the participating states are verified, which gives some insight into the total proportion of their contributions which will be reported as cash, and therefore what proportion (i.e. the remainder) will be IKOP, during EuroHPC's lifetime.

3.4 Allocation of Capacity and Access Policy

For each EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer acquired, the EU and each country in the consortium for that particular machine are allocated access time in proportion to what they each paid in¹⁰⁸. The EC's access time is allocated using published open calls and the EuroHPC Access Policy¹⁰⁹, governed by the Governing Board; the individual countries agree amongst themselves the distribution of the remaining access time (i.e. the non-EU portion), and each country is at liberty to allocate its slices of the access time as it wishes¹¹⁰, including for commercial purposes. A user may thus have different - and potentially multiple - possible ways of accessing the EuroHPC capacity:

- Applying, via the nationally-designated process(es), for their country's national capacity allocation to a particular EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer
- Submitting an expression of interest to use some of the EC's allocated capacity
- (In many countries) via their involvement in a project whose principal investigator is based in a country which participates in the consortium for a EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer, meaning the project participants can apply to use that country's allocated capacity.

In all three cases, the EuroHPC capacity is free at the point of use: the EC and the countries pay for the costs of acquisition, deployment, upgrading and operation (as well as activities in other pillars of EuroHPC), and HPC capacity is allocated to them in return, but at the point where users are involved, the capacity is pre-paid, so no money flows, avoiding cross-border issues such as VAT.

To ensure coherence with their national strategic priorities, the participating states are provided with a right of veto over the use of their national financial contributions for applicants established in those participating states.

User allocation of the EC's share of time in the EuroHPC supercomputers and quantum computers is primarily carried out through continuous open calls for expressions of interest, published on the EuroHPC website and evaluated by independent experts. The hosting entities are responsible for

¹⁰⁸ For high-end and quantum supercomputers, the EU's share is in proportion to its contribution to the total cost of ownership; for industrial-grade and mid-range supercomputers, the EU's share is in proportion to its contribution to the acquisition costs.

¹⁰⁹ *Access Policy of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking Supercomputers*, <https://bit.ly/EuroHPC-access-policy>.

¹¹⁰ Subject to the terms of the EuroHPC regulation. For example Art 16 of Regulation 2021/1173 stipulates that use of EuroHPC supercomputers should focus on civilian applications.

ensuring the allocation of the EU's access time to the selected applicants. In principle, the percentage of access time allocation is averaged over a period of one year of provisioning - i.e. within this period, each Hosting Entity needs to ensure the agreed levels of time allocation are respected.

The EuroHPC Access Policy, defined by the GB, provides the main principles and core characteristics (access modes, selection criteria) for the allocation of the EU's share of the supercomputers co-funded by EuroHPC. It is focussed on the allocation of access time for Open Research and Innovation activities but also covers specific allocation conditions to support industry uptake with focus on SMEs. Evaluation is primarily based on scientific excellence, along with criteria for impact, quality and efficiency of implementation.

The GB may also grant access time for projects and activities considered as strategic (for example, Destination Earth or the European Green Deal), and to other entities, for example in third countries or to international organisations.

The Access Policy allows for commercial users to get pay-per-use access to up to 20% of the EC's portion of the access time. This provides a revenue stream to the EuroHPC budget.

Section 3 Key Points

- EuroHPC is jointly funded by its members through financial contributions paid in instalments and in-kind contributions. It has a total budget of approximately € 7 billion for 2021-2027, and will operate until 2033.
 - The EU provides match funding to the participating states' contributions. It makes cash contributions from the Digital Europe Programme, Horizon Europe and the Connecting Europe Facility
 - The participating states arrange amongst themselves their collective contributions to EuroHPC and how they will deliver them. Participating states and private members can make contributions in cash and also in-kind. Analysis of EuroHPC accounts suggests that a large proportion (perhaps at least two-thirds) of the contributions are in-kind
- Participating states have a strong incentive to participate in EuroHPC, particularly as a hosting entity or within a hosting consortium, due to the ways in which funding from various EU programmes can be used to count towards the national cash contributions, and given that a significant portion of the cost of a supercomputer in a country can be considered as an in-kind contribution
- For each EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer acquired, the EU and each country in the consortium for that particular machine are allocated access time in proportion to what they each paid in
 - The EC's access time is allocated using published open calls and the EuroHPC Access Policy, governed by the Governing Board
 - The individual countries agree amongst themselves the distribution of the remaining access time (i.e. the non-EU portion), and each country is at liberty to allocate its slices of the access time as it wishes, including for commercial purposes
- A user may thus have multiple possible ways of accessing the EuroHPC capacity
 - Applying, via the nationally-designated process(es), for their country's national capacity allocation to a particular EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer
 - Submitting an expression of interest to use some of the EC's allocated capacity

- (In many countries) via their involvement in a project whose principal investigator is based in a country which participates in the consortium for a EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer, meaning the project participants can apply to use that country's allocated capacity
- In all three cases, the EuroHPC capacity is free at the point of use: at the point where users are involved, the capacity is pre-paid, so no money flows, avoiding cross-border issues such as VAT
- The EuroHPC Access Policy, defined by the GB, provides the main principles and core characteristics (access modes, selection criteria) for the allocation of the EU's share of the supercomputers co-funded by EuroHPC. It is focussed on the allocation of access time for Open Research and Innovation activities but also covers specific allocation conditions to support industry uptake with focus on SMEs. Evaluation is primarily based on scientific excellence, along with criteria for impact, quality and efficiency of implementation
 - The GB may also grant access time for projects and activities considered as strategic (for example, Destination Earth or the European Green Deal), and to other entities, for example in third countries or to international organisations.
 - The Access Policy allows for commercial users to get pay-per-use access to up to 20% of the EC's portion of the access time. This provides a revenue stream to the EuroHPC budget.

4. Assessment of the EuroHPC Vehicle

The EuroHPC JU successfully acts as the vehicle for achieving the EuroHPC objectives as part of a wider EU policy and legislative programme.

- The EuroHPC JU Regulation provides the procurement framework for EuroHPC and protects against state aid challenges.
- Capacity is distributed free at the point of use, avoiding issues arising from cross-border purchase or consumption of resources: financial contributions are pooled in EuroHPC, and used to acquire and operate the supercomputers and quantum computers, which are owned or co-owned by EuroHPC; the capacity itself is then allocated "for free" to the EC and the countries.
- The access policy for use of the EU's part of the capacity is governed by the Governing Board, in which the EC and the participating states are the voting members. The EU's portion of the capacity is, however, available for allocation to support pan-European activities, programmes of strategic importance, industry activities, and also international activity.
- EuroHPC's budget is based on matching contributions from the EU and the countries during the lifetime of the EuroHPC JU. The countries are able to designate funding received from EU programmes and also other eligible costs incurred in EU-funded programmes, as either financial or in-kind contributions. This potentially significantly reduces the amount of "new" funding a country needs to pay to participate in EuroHPC.
- In addition, the guarantee of a large EU funding contribution, of €3 billion, provides an incentive to countries to participate, to benefit from the matching EU funding. In this sense the EC contribution acts as a kind of glue keeping the countries on board together, and helping to reduce the risk to the countries due to the EC being a reliable funder.
- The countries benefit from availability of an increased amount of compute capacity from more powerful computers than they would be able to afford if they acted individually. Risks are shared between the members of the individual consortia which participate in the acquisition of each EuroHPC supercomputer or quantum computer. Thus, the risk to an individual country in a

consortium is lower than if it built a supercomputer on its own, but overall its researchers and businesses are able to access a greater amount of capacity, on faster supercomputers, than the same national contribution would have been able to purchase if acting individually.

- The model involves countries taking part together in a cross-border collaboration, but each country gets back what it pays in. In becoming involved in EuroHPC, or in a consortium for a specific supercomputer, each country has to trust that the others will deliver on their commitments. The required trust has been built up within the Governing Board, whose members have come to know one another well.
- The wider policy and legislative programme of which EuroHPC is part also helps to provide a complete European HPC industry supply chain.

Section 4 Key Points

- The EuroHPC JU successfully acts as the vehicle for achieving the EuroHPC objectives as part of a wider EU policy and legislative programme
- Key cornerstones of the model are
 - The dedicated JU Regulation providing the required procurement framework
 - Capacity is free at the point of use, avoiding cross-border issues relating to purchasing or consumption
 - The EU is allocated 50% of the computing capacity for use to support EU policy aims
 - The 50% EU funding contribution provides an incentive to countries to participate and acts as a “glue”
 - Countries benefit from increased compute capacity at lower risk than if they acted individually
 - A policy and legislative programme provides a wider framework in support of EuroHPC.

5. Conclusions

The use of a Joint Undertaking as a possible legal model for EOSC post-2027 is worthy of some consideration due to the specific legal protections and allowances this Partnership can be afforded. It is also possible to draw some parallels from EuroHPC which may be of relevance for EOSC.

A top-down push by the member states was required to achieve EuroHPC. Keys to building Member State commitment were (a) making the case that coordinated action by MS working together was more efficient than working individually and (b) persuading them of the strategic importance of the activity. The equivalent for EOSC may be (a) the potential efficiencies the Federation of EOSC Nodes could bring in the face of the increasing cost of sustaining RIs, including the increasing cost of data management and storage¹¹¹, and (b) (re-)stating the strategic importance of European research data and resources, including for European innovation, industry, employment and competitiveness.

A possible analogy may be drawn between EuroHPC and a future EOSC legal entity as a legal and funding vehicle to coordinate efforts and pool resources at European level, to develop and deploy services to exploit the full potential of research data. Such an analogy is worth further exploration.

¹¹¹ For example, by avoiding multiple copies of datasets being stored in different places, or perhaps over time, by a single instance of a service being provided within a Node, whereas possibly at present several individual instances (or at least very similar services) are operated independently by service providers.

Appendix 5: The ERIC funding model

John Picard (CLARIN ERIC) and Miguel Rey Mazón (Graz University of Technology)

Table of contents

Introduction	103
1. ERIC main funding sources	104
1.1. National Contributions - Membership Fees	1055
1.2. EC Funding – Competitive Projects and Grants	1066
1.3 Virtual Access and Transnational Access	107
1.4 In-kind contributions (IKCs)	107
2. Case studies: experience with ERIC funding mechanisms	109
2.1. CERIC-ERIC: Balancing national contributions and EU funding	1099
2.2. EMSO ERIC: Combining EU and national funding for large-scale infrastructure	109
2.3. LifeWatch ERIC: National contributions and regional development	10909
2.4. Instruct-ERIC: Public-private partnerships for innovation	11010
2.5. EPOS: Integrating EU and national funding for Earth science	110
2.6. CLARIN ERIC: EU Funding for pan-European Open Data Services	111
2.7. ELIXIR: scientific excellence and socio-economic impact as keys to sustainability	112

Introduction

European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) are legal entities under the 2009 ERIC Regulation.¹¹² They have pioneered a funding model that supports free-at-the-point-of-use, cross-border access to RIs and their data resources.

As EOSC evolves, there is growing interest in understanding how the ERIC model contributes to the sustainability of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) that populate EOSC with data and services. T5.3 has examined the funding mechanisms employed by a selection of ERICs (CERIC, EMSO, LifeWatch, Instruct, EPOS, and CLARIN), with a focus on the options for ensuring the RI sustainability, while pursuing excellent research that is inclusive and fosters innovation. Because of its relevance for life sciences and its similarities in organisation to ERICs, ELIXIR is also included in the analysis.

The following case studies illustrate the diverse funding mechanisms employed by ERICs to sustain cross-border research services, providing valuable insights for EOSC as it seeks to establish a financially viable and scalable funding model. These ERICs have pioneered strategies that seek to balance national contributions, EU grants, in-kind support, and partnerships to ensure long-term sustainability while maintaining free-at-the-point-of-use access to data and services. Their

¹¹² ERIC Regulation (2009), EC 723/2009, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009R0723>

experiences highlight both the opportunities and challenges of diversifying income streams, managing financial risks, and aligning with evolving national and EU priorities. Examining these funding models in practice can help EOSC identify adaptable approaches to support its own federated research infrastructure while mitigating risks associated with over-reliance on any single funding source.

Aspects analysed

T5.3 has analysed the funding mechanisms used by ERICs. The findings have been validated through review of the literature and informal interviews with ERIC representatives. The topics covered in the analysis can be summarised as follows:

- How do ERICs' main funding sources work? How does the money flow, and for what purposes? Is the funding sufficient to sustain operation of services and, more generally, of the RIs?
- What are the main vehicles to access RIs and services enabled by these funds?
- What costs are involved in the provisioning of cross-border, free-at-the-point-of-use data services, and how do the various funding sources help cover them?
- What do ERICs perceive as their main sustainability challenges, both generally, and in the context of EOSC?
- Which aspects of the ERIC funding model are relevant for EOSC, and why?
- Which aspects do RI representatives consider should be avoided and why?

Section 1 captures the insights collected about the funding mechanisms. Section 2 summarises the findings for the ERICs selected for interviews.

The ERICs selected reflect the diversity in the ERIC landscape that can be summarised as follows:

- Of the over 60 RIs in the ESFRI Roadmap since its inception in 2006, almost half are ERICs¹¹³;
- ERICs are quite diverse: the majority are distributed, i.e. consist of a network of interconnected facilities or digital resources spread across multiple locations, under a unified governance structure, as opposed to relatively few, single-sited ERICs, with centralised facilities located at a single site;
- ERIC budgets vary considerably: many have annual cash budgets of less than 5 million Euros while others have over ten times that amount;
- ERICs span a very wide range of scientific domains, including energy, environment, health and food, physical sciences, and social sciences and humanities, with those in the physical engineering, health and food and materials sciences tending to have closer links to industry.

1. ERIC main funding sources

The EU MS/AC sustain ERICs and their associated national consortia via membership fees and in-kind contributions from national programmes. These funds contribute to the costs of the development of the RI facilities (labs, data repositories, etc.) and the provision of services offered, which are free at the point of use for researchers. Funding from MS/AC is essential to pay for staff costs. EC funding

¹¹³ The most recent overview of RIs operating under ESFRI is the 2024 Landscape Analysis: <https://landscape2024.esfri.eu/>

through competitive grants and public-private partnerships (PPPs) is sizable and essential for R&D activities initiated by ERICs.

The principal funding mechanisms available to and used by ERICs are set out in the ERIC Forum Policy brief on funding models¹¹⁴:

- EC funding – Competitive grants (i.e. projects)
- Virtual Access (VA), Transnational Access (TNA)
- Contributions from MS/AC - Membership fees and in-kind
- Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), International agreements
- Service fees and access charges for non-member users
- Philanthropic and charitable contributions
- Collaboration with industry

In this Appendix the most relevant mechanisms (national contributions and EC funding) are described in some detail in subsections covering EC Project Funding (section 1.1), Membership Fees (section 1.2) and In-Kind contributions (section 1.3). The focus is placed on the models adopted in distributed ERICs, as they are the majority in the RI landscape, and also because they often actively do cross-border provisioning, while for single-sited RIs this is mainly done via TNA (trans-national access) as a dedicated funding instrument.

National Contributions - Membership Fees

As member-based legal entities, ERICs rely in part on financial contributions from their member countries (MS/AC) through membership fees. While these fees are paid by the MS/AC, the individual RI nodes—i.e. national research facilities participating in the ERIC—are typically funded through national sources. The overarching Research Infrastructures (RIs) act on behalf of their respective national nodes, representing them in ERIC governance bodies and daily management. The fee amount is usually determined by dividing the costs of running the central services of the ERIC among the members relative to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or other wealth-based economic indicators that ensure fairness relative to national capacity. Alternatives include flat contributions (less common for larger ERICs), calculations of service usage or benefits (i.e. expected or actual use of services provided by the ERIC, such as the number of researchers benefiting), or a combination of methods. Fees cover only a portion of the overall costs of an ERIC, usually those related to staffing and operations (in many cases including event organisation and provision of mobility grants) of the central office or hub. The activities of the nodes of distributed data-driven RIs which form the majority of ERICs on the other hand must be sustained through revenues from other sources such as local funding, project grants, in-kind contributions, user fees, etc.

Membership fees - where they come from and how they are spent

Member fees are channelled to the ERIC from national budgets, in most cases allocated by the Ministry of Research, Science, or equivalent bodies. Many MS/AC appoint a national entity (e.g. a research council, institute, or similar organisation, like CNRS in France, or CNR in Italy) to represent their interests in the ERIC and act as the intermediary.

¹¹⁴ For an overview of funding sources for ERICs, see *ERIC Forum Policy Brief: Funding Models for Access to ERIC Multinational/Transnational Services* (2020), https://www.eric-forum.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/ERIC-Forum_Policy-Brief.pdf.

The membership fees are used to pay the costs of the ERIC’s central office. This includes staff salaries (Director General, often earning a competitive international salary, and other staff, encompassing administrative, scientific, and technical personnel, either directly employed by the ERIC, or seconded¹¹⁵ by representing entities or MS/AC), and all operational costs (facilities and equipment, i.e. rent, utilities, IT systems, and infrastructure to support daily operations), events for knowledge exchange and training, administrative expenses (e.g. General Assembly meetings, Scientific Advisory Board meetings), and communication.

Membership fees - benefits and risks

Membership fees are predictable and therefore contribute to the stability of the ERIC. They guarantee a certain “baseline funding” in the form of a steady, predictable income stream for core operations, usually with long-term commitment from MS/AC as determined by the statutes. The predictability reduces the reliance on short-term project grants. If properly designed, fees ensure an equitable cost-sharing among ERIC members, since they are tailored to reflect the members’ economic capacities (or other “fair” criteria), thus fostering inclusivity. They moreover introduce a shared responsibility among ERIC members to invest collaboratively in shared infrastructure, spreading financial risks across multiple countries.

Membership fees partially free ERICs from grant cycles, and provide them with some autonomy from national or EU agendas. Since MS/AC Governments or their representing entities—as main investors in the RIs that constitute them—want ERICs to succeed, the fees ensure active participation in governance and strategic planning, which contributes to member accountability and incentivizes engagement. Membership fees present however some potential risks to an ERIC’s financial stability: an MS/AC can reduce its presence or withdraw altogether from an ERIC (if the strategic interest of the MS/AC is reduced, or if an RI node is discontinued due to economic or political reasons). Also, economic disparities between countries (e.g. wealthier countries may bear a disproportionate share of the financial burden) can lead to tensions. Furthermore, financial stability can be compromised if ERICs are over-dependent on MS/AC budgets, due to delays or gaps in payment of fees because of misalignment of national budget cycles with ERICs’ priorities and planning, or due to changes in MS/AC Government priorities or policies, which can affect their willingness to contribute.

1.2. EC Funding – Competitive Projects and Grants

The Regulation provides ERICs with the legal status to apply for competitive funding from Horizon Europe, Digital Decade, Structural Funds, or other funding programmes. Funds awarded to the ERIC are usually distributed to its members as determined by the project budget (i.e. as required by the workload of the project tasks), often as reimbursement for eligible costs.

EC funding is used for R&I activities as allowed by the programme’s characteristics, for infrastructure upgrades, or for collaboration with other RIs or other stakeholders. Importantly, this funding does not pay for the operation of services. Access to EC grants is important for ERICs to keep aligned with cutting-edge research priorities, and by design they promote FAIR data practices to align RI activities with EC’s vision of Open Science and EOOSC. While strengthening the cooperation between MS and the EU to develop and operate RIs is the *raison d’être* of ERICs, the resources made available by the EC

¹¹⁵ Secondments may reduce direct payroll costs for the ERIC, but still constitute a form of in-kind contribution by members.

are intended to cover only part of an ERIC’s activities of ESFRI Roadmap RIs in the start-up phase, not those of the mature ESFRI Landmarks.

1.3 Virtual Access and Transnational Access

Virtual Access (VA) and Transnational Access (TNA) are essential EC-funded mechanisms employed by ERICs to facilitate free-at-the-point-of-use access to research infrastructure services across borders.

VA funding enables remote digital access to data, resources, and services provided by RIs without the need for formal peer review or individual application processes, thus significantly broadening accessibility and fostering inclusivity in research. It is particularly suited to digital infrastructures and data-driven RIs, allowing seamless cross-border usage without administrative hurdles.

TNA, in contrast, typically supports physical access to research facilities located in another country. It covers direct user costs such as travel, accommodation, and usage fees, thereby reducing financial barriers for researchers needing in-person access to unique or advanced infrastructure.

Both mechanisms are funded primarily through competitive EC grants, fostering pan-European research collaboration, innovation, and resource sharing. While VA enhances data accessibility and broadens the user base at scale, TNA directly strengthens international collaboration and promotes equitable access to state-of-the-art research facilities, thus significantly contributing to the sustainability and internationalisation of ERICs. See section 4.4.1 in the main document for more details on the use of VA and TNA, including in EOSC-related EU Projects.

1.4 In-kind contributions (IKCs)

In-kind contributions (IKC) are understood as funding provided by MS from national streams to the RI nodes in an ERIC not directly allocated to the ERIC budget. They are used to build, operate, or improve RIs. While not mentioned in the ERIC Regulation¹¹⁶, IKC are acknowledged as the ERICs’ main capital¹¹⁷, and are thus essential to setup and run ERICs and ensure their long-term sustainability, despite generally not being included in ERIC budgets for lack of common accounting standards. Importantly, IKCs enable collaboration while leveraging local expertise required by the RIs to operate.

IKCs are difficult to cost as countries and organisations have different valuation and accounting systems, which makes it hard to set a “true value” of national contributions and services to users.

Single-site vs distributed RIs

Distributed RIs differ from single-site RIs in one fundamental aspect: in single-site RIs, IKC “imply the transfer [to the ERIC legal entity] of the ownership of the contributions provided” during its construction or operation. This is not the general case for distributed RIs, since in general members of an ERIC will pay to build and install equipment at the facilities placed in their country. In that case, instead of transferring ownership to the ERIC, members make the resources they have paid for available to the ERIC (i.e. they can be used by the ERIC in its research activities).

1.4.1 Types of IKC

¹¹⁶ They appear in the *ERIC practical guidelines – Legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium*, Publications Office, 2015, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/72348>.

¹¹⁷ A. Biljesko et al., *In-kind Contribution Methodology*, <https://bit.ly/ACCELERATE-D1-8>, page 5.

There are four relevant types of IKC in ERICs:

- **Donations:** they either come with a bill documenting the cost of goods and services provided, or they don't. In both cases to decide on the *actual* value a professional assessment is needed.
- **Buying of goods and services by an ERIC member:** in the case of a purchase there is an invoice, so actual costs can be known.
- **Provision by an ERIC member to the ERIC with use of standard facility or instrument:** there *may* be an invoice documenting the actual costs of the service. If there is no invoice, the “fair market value” of the use of the facility has to be estimated.
- **Provision by an ERIC member to the ERIC with the use of a “specific” facility or instrument**¹¹⁸: because they are “specific” (in the sense of “special” or “unique”, like e.g. a particle accelerator) there is no “market” for these facilities or instruments, and the (estimated) value of the service has to be agreed between the hosting member and the ERIC.

1.4.2. Measuring and accounting of IKCs

Since IKCs are essential for ERICs to fulfil their mission and become sustainable, they should be properly measured and accounted for. By including IKCs in their accounts, ERICs can display the “real overall values of the resources involved in an ERIC”¹¹⁹, and demonstrate the financial effort made by member MS/AC, which can in turn show the support they provide to the ERICs. Correct evaluation of resources invested in RIs thus allows all involved to understand the specific and the overall impact of the ERICs’ activities.

The evaluation, reporting, and auditing of IKC contributes to an ERIC’s financial and non-financial goals¹²⁰. On the financial side, IKCs help *assessing the fulfilment of agreed contributions*. IKCs also *demonstrate the capacity of an ERIC to attract additional resources for funding its activities*. This is key to sustainability, since an ERIC should be interested in identifying how much funding has come from where, and to which of its activities a given IKC has contributed. Finally, IKCs *help to define service prices for ERICs’ economic activities*: knowledge of investment in an instrument or facility helps to know total costs of providing a service, and is thus important to set prices.

As for the non-financial goals, IKCs *enable the correct allocation of ownership rights arising from joint inventions* by specifying who paid for what. IKC also *provide information to calculate voting rights and other governance aspects*. Lastly, IKCs *help defining the “real scale” of the activities performed*. A realistic assessment of how many resources are involved in the activities of an ERIC is essential for planning and to frame conversations on long-term sustainability with funders (i.e. MS/AC mainly).

The complexity of implementing a more or less uniform model of accounting across the various RIs has been analysed in a report by the Expert Group on the assessment on the implementation of the ERIC Regulation (EGERIC) led by Carlo Rizzuto.¹²¹

¹¹⁸ Standard facilities or instruments are those that are used in more than one discipline or field, whereas “specific” ones are discipline-specific.

¹¹⁹ ACCELERATE D1.8.

¹²⁰ Andrea Santelli (CERIC-ERIC), *Evaluation, Reporting and Auditing on In-Kind Contributions*, in “In-kind Contributions in the Life of an ERIC”, Workshop organised by the ACCELERATE project on 5 December 2019, http://www.accelerate2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/20191205_IKC-Workshop-by-CERIC_AndreaSANTELLI.pdf.

¹²¹ See <https://bit.ly/EGERIC-Report>.

1. Case studies: experience with ERIC funding mechanisms

1.1. CERIC-ERIC: Balancing national contributions and EU funding

[CERIC-ERIC](#) relies on a mix of national contributions and EU funding, particularly from Horizon Europe (to support transnational access (TNA) and infrastructure upgrades) and structural funds, which support inclusion of RIs in less-developed regions, aligning with EOSC's goal of equitable access. EC project funding thus remains essential as a catalyst of increased pan-EU cooperation.

CERIC has greatly benefited from the early establishment of a central Communications Office, which has been instrumental in raising EU-wide awareness of CERIC's scientific excellence and its socio-economic value and impact. This has undoubtedly helped CERIC to secure the necessary funding from MS/AC. Existing funding sources are however known to be insufficient to cover incremental infrastructure maintenance and services provisioning costs stemming from increased cross-border demand driven by EOSC. Moreover, smaller MS/AC often struggle to meet funding commitments.

CERIC's model demonstrates the importance of balancing EU and national funding for long-term sustainability. The EOSC Federation could aim for a similar model in which a central node is funded in full or partially by membership fees, with additional EU funds helping MS in supporting local nodes and covering incremental operation and maintenance costs.

1.2. EMSO ERIC: Combining EU and national funding for large-scale infrastructure

[EMSO](#) uses HE grants for R&D activities and VA/TNA access programmes, supplemented by national contributions for operational and staff costs via membership fees and in-kind contributions. EU funding supports large-scale infrastructure projects, such as ocean observatories, which is key for EMSO's scalability, more so taking into account the high costs of large-scale infrastructures in its discipline (ocean and marine science) which requires significant long-term investment.

EMSO is however over-reliant on EC funding, since over 60% of its budget comes from EC competitive grants (which also proves EMSO is very competitive here). Coordination challenges: Aligning national and EU funding priorities can be difficult.

In-kind contributions are vital to the sustainability of EMSO's staff costs, but they also pose serious challenges, as facilities whose involvement in EMSO's activities is only in-kind tend to offer only marginal effort to the ERIC, since the objectives are largely local, and salaries are paid from local (national) sources; they may even not accept direction from the ERIC Central Office, which makes it difficult for the ERIC to develop and implement a strategy or action plan.

1.3. LifeWatch ERIC: National contributions and regional development

[LifeWatch ERIC](#) is the European initiative for research on biodiversity and ecosystems. It combines membership fees, in-kind contributions and EU funding via competitive grants similar to other ERICs, and thus shares many of the benefits and disadvantages of mixed funding sources. Maybe an important characteristic of their funding model is how LifeWatch leverages EU Structural Funds (primarily from the European Regional Development Fund) to develop physical and digital infrastructures, capacity building, and regional integration. These funds are accessed through national-level applications and target underdeveloped regions, promoting inclusivity and reducing

disparities across Europe. Structural Funds play a critical role in enhancing LifeWatch’s capacity to provide free cross-border services, while also aligning with EOSC’s inclusivity goals.

LifeWatch receives revenues from training, consultancy, and value-added services provided to industry and external researchers. These revenues are limited and moreover they are hard to predict, which makes them unreliable and insufficient for scaling operations. As with other ERICs, giving transactions more importance in the income structure may conflict with the ethos of providing free and open access to research data.

1.4. Instruct-ERIC: Public-private partnerships for innovation

[Instruct-ERIC](#) is the pan-European distributed RI for structural biology. It provides access to high-end technologies, expertise, and training in structural biology. It supports research into the structure and function of biological macromolecules, essential for advances in medicine, biotechnology, and fundamental biology. Instruct became operational in 2012, and was soon recognised as a Landmark Project on the 2016 ESFRI Roadmap, and it was awarded the ERIC status in July 2017.

The cash contributions from its members, in the range of 60 000 to 100 000 € per year¹²², are used to run the ERIC central office and represent around 20% of total costs in 2021. A larger portion (slightly under 50%) was used to pay for “access costs”. As an example of how IKC are treated in ERICs, in the case of Instruct the monetary value of IKC investment from ERIC members in the facilities of an Instruct Centre (including running costs and the support staff salaries required for Instruct activities) are not measured, in line with other ERICs and more generally with distributed RIs.

In Instruct-ERIC, membership fees are divided in three tiers, determined by the number of persons with tertiary education and/or employed in science and technology. In 2021 they represented around 75% (880 000 €) of the total €1.2 million budget.

Instruct participates in EU-funded projects, representing 25% (320 000 €) of their income in 2021, with very minor additional income from other sources¹²³. EU project funding supports user access programmes like Instruct’s Virtual Access programme, which provides online data resources freely accessible to researchers without formal application or selection processes. Instruct’s TNA programme funds users’ travel, accommodation, and access to state-of-the-art facilities (e.g. cryo-electron microscopy, NMR spectroscopy, or other advanced technologies).

1.5. EPOS: Integrating EU and national funding for Earth science

The [European Plate Observing System \(EPOS\)](#) integrates national infrastructures dedicated to solid Earth sciences, providing unified access to multidisciplinary data, tools, and services. EPOS effectively integrates distributed national infrastructures into a cohesive pan-European platform, leveraging EU project funding for innovation and technical interoperability. EPOS relies on a diversified funding structure that integrates:¹²⁴

¹²² There are three categories among members to define the cash contribution, “determined by the number of persons with tertiary education (ISCED) and/or employed in science and technology (HRST NOCC) of working age (25-64 years)”, see Instruct-ERIC Statutes, 2023, Annex 2, page 21-22, https://instruct-eric.org/download/?file=20230515_Instruct-ERIC+Statutes_with_annexes.pdf&do=do.

¹²³ Figures taken from the 2021 Annual Report, <https://zenodo.org/records/6982942>.

¹²⁴ <https://www.epos-eu.org/sites/default/files/2024-06/EPOS%20ERIC%20Activity-Financial-Report%202023.pdf>

- MS contributions: Core funding is primarily derived from statutory annual membership fees paid by participating MS, including a significant host-country premium provided by Italy, ensuring continuity and core operational sustainability.
- Competitive EU project funding: EPOS leverages EU-funded projects (including ENVRI-Hub NEXT, SKILLS4EOSC, GeoInquire)¹²⁵. Grants represented a relatively modest proportion (approximately 5%) of the total budget in 2023.
- In-kind contributions: National institutions contribute substantially in-kind, including infrastructure, specialised equipment, and technical expertise, accounting for approximately 45% of the total EPOS resource base. These contributions significantly extend EPOS's operational capabilities.

MS fees and Italy's host-country premium provide reliable core operational funding, facilitating strategic planning and service continuity. The expansion of EPOS's membership base in 2023 to 23 MS further enhanced this financial stability. By achieving clear buy-in from participating MS thanks to its socio-economic impact and scientific value, EPOS has been able to reinforce sustained commitment to fees and in-kind contributions, which are both critical for long-term success.

The considerable reliance of EPOS on in-kind contributions, including the host-country premium, introduces however financial uncertainty, as changes in national institutional budgets or scientific and political priorities could directly impact EPOS operations and sustainability. Reduced national financial commitments could substantially threaten core operations.

While it is a positive of socio-economic impact and scientific value, the increase of members and stakeholders carries a significant administrative overhead for EPOS, adding complexity and costs to scale and integrate diverse national infrastructures.

Relevance for EOSC

EPOS's balanced and diversified funding provides a valuable lesson for EOSC's pursuit of long-term sustainability: EOSC should similarly adopt a multi-source funding strategy, balancing reliable national membership contributions and host-country commitments with strategic EU competitive grants to manage financial risks effectively. Also, EPOS's structured approach to accounting and valuing in-kind contributions offers EOSC insights into developing standardized and transparent processes, critical for demonstrating member states' investments clearly.

The experience from EPOS also shows that clear long-term financial commitments from member countries, coupled with transparent governance and demonstration of impact, are essential. EOSC can learn from how EPOS has secured stable commitment from MS while succeeding in securing funding from competitive EU grants to realise its mission should actively manage and mitigate potential financial risks arising from dependency on national funding variability and EU policy changes.¹²⁶

1.6. CLARIN ERIC: EU Funding for pan-European Open Data Services

The ESFRI Landmark [CLARIN ERIC](#) (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure), established as an ERIC in 2012, provides data, tools, and services to support research based on

¹²⁵ <https://www.epos-eu.org/projects>

¹²⁶ For more information, see <https://www.annalsofgeophysics.eu/index.php/annals/article/view/8786/7441>.

language resources. It is rooted in the domain of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) but it also is serving disciplines beyond SSH. CLARIN's Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) provides easy and sustainable access to digital language data and advanced tools to discover, explore, exploit, annotate, analyse, or combine them, wherever they are located. It has 23 full members, 3 observers, and participation from over 100 institutions. CLARIN and four other large SSH ERICs (CESSDA, DARIAH, ESS and SHARE), joined the ESFRI Roadmap in 2006 and were awarded Landmark status in 2016. Two more SSH RIs (E-RIHS, EHRI) were added to the ESFRI Roadmap in 2018, followed by another four in 2021 (GGP, GUIDE, OPERAS and RESILIENCE). The SSH RIs collaborate quite closely in the SSH Open Cluster.¹²⁷

In CLARIN, membership fees are based on the countries' GDP. The contributions fund central coordination (e.g. governance, central services like the Virtual Language Observatory, and technical infrastructure, events) and strategic development. Member countries have a direct stake in CLARIN, fostering alignment with the ERIC's goals. As with other ERICs, CLARIN is aware that MS/AC's willingness and ability to contribute can fluctuate depending on the economic and (geo-)political context, and that dependency on MS national infrastructure and objectives can affect the effectiveness of central coordination efforts. The volume and quality of in-kind contributions can vary greatly between countries, especially given the wide membership .

CLARIN relies in part on EU grants (e.g. Horizon Europe) to support the innovation of free-at-the-point-of-use data services and infrastructure development. EC projects encourage collaboration with other pan-EU research infrastructures, but reliance on EU contributions brings the risk of funding gaps due to shifting EC priorities and/or budget constraints. Also, the competitive nature of EU grants make this income difficult to predict year on year.

1.7. ELIXIR: scientific excellence and socio-economic impact as keys to financial sustainability

[ELIXIR](#) is a distributed research infrastructure that supports life sciences research by coordinating and integrating bioinformatics resources across over 240 research organisations across Europe in 21 MS hosted by the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) and benefitting from its "existing legal personality and its privileges and immunities as an intergovernmental institution"¹²⁸. It has been recognised as ESFRI Landmark. ELIXIR has developed a strong reputation for scientific excellence and socio-economic impact and relevance, resulting in strong EC and MS buy-in and support. While not an ERIC, ELIXIR's funding model shares some characteristics with that of ERICs, in particular regarding the status of countries as members and their contribution via membership fees. ELIXIR offers its resources free of charge as public goods. This ensures widespread access to bioinformatics tools, fostering innovation and public trust, and increasing the impact of ELIXIR for research in life-sciences.

Mixed sources of funding

As in ERICs, MS/AC members of ELIXIR pay annual fees that fund the ELIXIR Hub's operations and coordination activities. Much of this funding is transferred back to the Nodes to collectively deliver

¹²⁷ The model of collaboration at cluster level for the RIs in the SSH domain is detailed here: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-ssh-open-cluster>.

¹²⁸ See ELIXIR Consortium Agreement, clause 2.3, page 11, <https://elixir-europe.org/sites/default/files/documents/elixir-consortium-agreement.pdf>

ELIXIR's five-year Scientific Programme¹²⁹. The ELIXIR Nodes are funded through national investments and in-kind contributions aligned with national infrastructure roadmaps.

Additional funding comes from competitive grants from Horizon Europe and the Innovative Medicines Initiative¹³⁰. Other sources include international and charitable support (e.g. organisations such as the US National Institutes of Health, Wellcome Trust, Wallenberg Foundation, and Novo Nordisk Foundation), collaboration with industry¹³¹ (e.g. the EMBL-EBI Industry Programme¹³²), or service-based revenue for access to depletable resources like cloud computing or data management consultancy. The funding is employed for ELIXIR core services (free at the point of use), innovation and integration (including integration of resources across members to maintain interoperability), and capacity building to ensure users can effectively access and apply ELIXIR services.

Characteristics of the ELIXIR funding model

Similar to ERICs, the mix of public, EU, and external funding provides ELIXIR with stability, and minimizes over-reliance on any one source. Thanks to ELIXIR's proven scientific and socio-economic value and impact, both *EC and MS/AC are committed to providing continuous funding*—an important lesson that should be learnt by ERICs. Also, ELIXIR is fully aligned with EU goals, like the FAIR principles, promotes inclusivity in research, and has an important presence and visibility beyond Europe, all of which contribute to widen its impact. Despite the limited additional revenue it brings and potential conflict with its “free at the point of use” policy for services, *ELIXIR's collaboration with industry is a sign of its awareness of the importance it bears for impact and sustainability*. Charging for depletable resources risks adding complexity and discouraging access if not managed carefully.

Also like in ERICs, membership fees alone are not sufficient to cover the operating costs, and remain vulnerable to shifts in national priorities, so EC funding remains essential. MS/AC contributions are moreover very different, and the variability in investment between countries can create disparities in the quality of resources and services across Nodes. Also, increasing pressures on MS budgets (stemming from e.g. the proliferation of expensive RIs and mounting competitiveness challenges) threaten sustainability. EC project funding may thus become even more vital as EOSC drives increased demand for ELIXIR services. EC grants are however geared to fund innovative results but not operation and maintenance costs of infrastructure and services, so this funding does not entirely contribute to ELIXIR's long-term planning and sustainability.

While multiple funding sources can be good for sustainability (by not having to rely on a single source that may eventually cease), it also entails the risk of having to deal with the different priorities of the funders. Also, managing multiple funding sources and competitive grants increases the overhead for member Nodes and the Hub due to higher administrative complexity.

¹²⁹ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/what-we-do/elixir-programme>

¹³⁰ <https://www.ihf.europa.eu/>

¹³¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/industry>

¹³² <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/industry/industry-programme/>